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EVALUATION OF THE EFFICIENCY OF GREENHOUSES IN GUILAN PROVINCE USING DATA ENVELOPMENT ANALYSIS (DEA)

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ABSTRACT: This research examines the financial performance of greenhouses in Guilan province in Iran. In order to do the research, questionnaires from 60 greenhouses were collected and features such as the general specifications of greenhouses, type of greenhouse covers, surface areas, infrastructure facilities, input raw material, energy and fuel costs, personal cost, production rate, sales prices of the produced products were considered. A financial performance measure developed from data envelopment analysis (DEA). According to the results, 7% of the greenhouses had an efficiency of 20%-40%, 22% between 40%-60%, 33% between 60%-80%, and 38% had more than 80%.

Keywords : *Data envelopment analysis, food security, greenhouse.*

Population growth and consequently, the demand for providing agricultural products and also the seasonal production of these products have caused strategies to be considered for meeting people's needs so that not only the production level is increased, but also producing out-of-season products would be possible. One of these strategies is to cultivate agricultural products (such as fruits and vegetables) in greenhouses. By doing so, besides the increased production rate, some production measures can be taken in all seasons as well.

Using environmental factors - controlling techniques is beneficial especially in regions, where the natural conditions of the essential factors of plant growth (soil and water) can be made suitable only by irrigation, weeding, applying fertilizers, etc. However, controlling and regulating the ambient temperature and light is beyond a farmer's capabilities and interfering with them is not possible; while in greenhouse cultivation, these two factors can be completely controlled and regulated for the desirable growth of a plant. It's been years since greenhouse cultivation is being practiced in Europe with many economic and profitability justifications (Sharifi, 13).

Optimum allocation of resources in an organization, enterprise or industry requires a continuous assessment of the performance of its units. Performance evaluation is one of the elements of the productivity improvement process because without measurement, making judgments would not be feasible and as a result, a proper controlling and planning could be impossible for the organization. Measuring the mentioned concepts have always been as object of

attention for experts of different sciences including management, accounting, economics, engineering and mathematics and many researches have been done in this regard in a way that since 1965, when the first productivity measurement model was proposed by Kendrick-Creamer, many productivity and efficiency - measurement models have been presented by different individuals and global organizations. One of these models is the mathematical model of data envelopment analysis (DEA) (Motameni, 10). This method is based on linear programming and since it's an optimization method, it is advantageous over other efficiency analysis methods. With consideration of the characteristics of DEA and its being capable of providing a comprehensive and conclusive method for every unit of multiple inputs and outputs, it seems to be a suitable method for computing the efficiency of economic enterprises. Moreover, the possibility of considering variables for this model and using shadow prices causes it to be applied for assessing the efficiency of service-providing, non-profit-making and governmental sectors as well (Rahmanian, 12).

Efficiency and Data Envelopment Analysis

Efficiency is the explanation of the concept that with what quality an organization has used its resources for having the best production performance during a given period of time (Piece, 11). In fact, efficiency is the criterion for an organization's performance, which is established upon the amount of resources (inputs). In other words, it is the amount of resources that are used to produce a certain amount of a product. Generally, efficiency is calculated by the

relationship between the output-input proportions (Mehrgan, 9).

Data envelopment analysis is a method which is applied to assess the efficiency and productivity of units that are responsible for using resources to obtain a desirable output. It may include several inputs and outputs without the need for predetermined weights (e.g. index method) and the clear specifications of the relationships between inputs and outputs (e.g. the regression method) (Bowlin, 3). DEA is a linear programming method which forms an efficient frontier using information from organizations and production units as decision-making units (DMUs). The frontier is created based on information in the form of inputs and outputs and according to the results of a consecutive linear programming. In fact, it is the inefficiency degree of each DMU to the distance between this unit and the efficiency frontier (Emami Meibodi, 4). Due to its unique capabilities, data envelopment analysis has become one of the common methods for performance evaluation and many of the researches in this field use it for this purpose and for assessing productivity as well. These capabilities have caused the said model to be used in the industry sector, financial services (banks, insurance, etc) and transportation, educational and research centers, health and treatment centers and so on. 'Measuring the Technical Efficiency in Malaysian Manufacturing Industries Using the Deterministic Production Frontier Function' is one of the researches in which this method was used by Wadonda (14). In this research, the efficiency of several industries including tea-producing factories in Malaysia during 1984-1988 was assessed using DEA technique. Obtained results revealed that the highest efficiency of the tea-producing industry was 72% in 1984, while the lowest efficiency was 44% in 1988 (Wadonda, 14).

Recently, various studies about data envelopment analysis (DEA) were done in Iran. For example, Kavousi and Ebrahimpour (5) conducted a research on effective factors of rice transformation industries productivity' using DEA method and the production function. This research was done on 130 rice transformation enterprises in Iran and its results showed that 19 enterprises were on the efficiency frontier. Some of the factors which affected the efficiency were also analyzed. Ghasemi *et al.* (6) used the same method for alfaalfa production in the Hamedan province, Iran. The results showed that from the total of 80 farmers, considered for the analysis, 46% and 69% were found to be technically and pure technically efficient, respectively. Mousavi *et al.* (8)

studied energy use for barberry production in individual farms. The results indicated that total energy input and yield value of small farms were higher than those of large farms. Mohammadi *et al.* (7), assessed 82 rice paddy fields for spring and summer growing seasons in north of Iran. They used the combined implementation of Life Cycle Assessment (LCA) and Data Envelopment Analysis (DEA). Results showed average reduction levels of up to 20% and 25% per material input for spring and summer systems, leading to impact reductions which ranged from 8% to 11% for spring farms and 19% to 25% for summer farms depending on the chosen impact category. Bolandnaza *et al.* (2) used face to face questionnaire from 60 greenhouse cucumber farmers applying DEA method. The results indicated that greenhouse cucumber production consumed a total energy of 306,117.57 MJ ha⁻¹ from which 58.5% was provided by diesel fuel.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Assessing the efficiency of greenhouses in Guilan province in 2008 was the main objective of this research. In 2004, a total of 284 greenhouses were active in different towns of the Guilan province; however, due to the heavy snow in that year, only 120 of them remained of which 64 greenhouses were active and under cultivation in 2009, when questionnaires were distributed and thus, the required data were collected. These 64 identified active units were considered as the statistical population. After determining the needed population, a questionnaire was designed in which many aspects such as the general specifications of greenhouses, type of greenhouse covers, their surface areas, infrastructure facilities, raw materials to be applied, energy and fuel costs, working manpower number and cost, production rate, sales prices of the produced products, etc. were taken into account. Required data were collected by distributing questionnaires among the said units. Due to not having access to greenhouse owners and some incomplete questionnaires, four questionnaires were eliminated. After processing the data, EMS software was used for the DEA model.

Research Model

The modified BCC envelopment model of the input axis was used in this research. In the model, shows the proportion of the reduction of the studied unit's inputs for improving efficiency. Here, a unit is efficient only when the two following conditions exist:

- (a) $\theta^x = 1$, and
- (b) All the auxiliary variables have zero values.

$$\min y_0 = \theta - \sum_{j=1}^x \lambda_j \varepsilon s_j^+ - \sum_{j=1}^m \lambda_j \varepsilon s_j^- \quad \dots(1)$$

$$\sum_{j=1}^x \lambda_j y_n - s_j^+ = y_{\gamma 0} \quad \dots(\gamma = 1 \dots s)$$

$$\sum_{j=1}^x \lambda_j x_n + s_j^- = \theta x_{10} \quad \dots(i = 1 \dots m)$$

$\sum \lambda_j = 1$ = Free for mathematical signal

$$s_j^+, s_j^- \geq 0 \quad \dots(j = 1 \dots n)$$

By solving the above-mentioned model for the studied units, two 'Efficient' and 'Inefficient' groups were identified. Those units whose efficiency score was 1 were determined as efficient units. Inefficient units could be rated by getting efficiency scores; however, units whose efficiency score was 1 could not be rated using classic DEA models. Therefore, the AP model was proposed by Andersen and Petersen (1), which made determining the most efficient units possible. Using this technique, the score of efficient units could be more than 1 (100%). In order to assess the efficiency by the DEA method, suitable inputs and outputs were selected first. Then, research inputs and outputs were selected to assess the efficiency of greenhouses as follows:

Inputs

L: Manpower cost; a payable value (in Iranian Rials) for rewarding the workers in 2008.

M: Value of production inputs (seeds, herbicides and pesticides, fertilizers and minerals) in Iranian Rials.

E: Energy; total payable cost for energy consumption in 2008.

H: Cultivated area (in meters).

Output

Y: Income; value of various greenhouse products in 2008 (in Iranian Rials).

Objective Function

Q: Efficiency of greenhouses in 2008.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

After distributing and collecting the questionnaires, 60 of the completed and received questionnaires were studied for assessing the efficiency and also for rating greenhouse units. Some of the questionnaires were received as incomplete, which after more visits, they were modified and completed. Of the existing models, the modified BCC envelopment model of the input axis of the data envelopment analysis was selected to assess the efficiency of greenhouse units in

Guilan province. The reason for selecting BCC model was that according to the opinions of experts in this industry, increasing inputs does not lead to output increase in the same proportion, which means the variability of efficiency with scale. Furthermore, since several inputs and only one output is considered for assessing the efficiency, the input axis model, which reduces inputs by keeping the output constant was selected.

By solving the above-mentioned model for greenhouses, the efficiencies of 18 units became 1 or 100% (Q= 1) and formed the efficiency frontier. Forty-two other greenhouses had efficiency values of less than 1 (or <100%) (Q<1), which was an indication of their inefficiency. Then, by solving the AP model for 18 greenhouses, whose objective function equaled 1, the ratings of efficient units was done and therefore, all greenhouses were rated. The output related to solving the aforesaid models is given in Table 1.

Columns 1 and 4 of Table 1 indicate the number of DMUs. Columns 2 and 5 show the efficiency of those units, while columns 3 and 6 show the reference units or the pattern for each unit. In other words, for an inefficient unit in the above table to become efficient and be transferred to the efficiency frontier, a convex composition of its reference units should be found. This composition in the model has the same value of the coefficient of reference units multiplied by the values of the given unit's inputs. As mentioned before, units whose efficiency scores are less than 1 are identified as inefficient and can be rated by getting an efficiency score. However, units whose efficiency score is 1 (100%) can't be rated using classic DEA models. Therefore, efficient units have been rated by the AP model, proposed by Andersen and Petersen (1).

To analyze the software's output, at first, the modified BCC model of the input axis was implemented for all greenhouses (60 units) using EMS software and then, outputs obtained from solving the models were taken. Solving all 60 research models provided different information. As seen, 18 greenhouses, *i.e.*, 3, 4, 13, 15, 20, 23, 27, 28, 31, 32, 35, 39, 40, 41, 48, 51, 52 and 59 with values of 100% or more had the highest efficiencies. Also, the AP model was used for rating 18 units that were on the efficient frontier. Based on this rating, greenhouse number 3 was at the highest level. Average efficiency in this industry is 75.30%.

The efficiency of the existing greenhouses is given in four classifications in Table 2. As per observations (Table 2) no greenhouse has an efficiency less than 20%, 7% of them have an efficiency of 20%-40%, the efficiency of 22% of the greenhouses is at the range of

Table 1: Efficiencies of decision-making units (DMUs).

Reference Units	Efficiency	Greenhouses	Reference Units	Efficiency	Greenhouses
18	120.49%	31	23, 27	80.00%	1
6	102.86%	32	23, 31	79.87%	2
23, 31, 35, 41	74.42%	33	14	1176.47%	3
13, 40, 48, 51	91.93%	34	3	100.00%	4
20	115.37%	35	23, 32, 48	62.66%	5
3, 40, 48	77.78%	36	3, 20, 23, 35, 51	59.34%	6
3, 40, 48, 51	83.29%	37	3, 23, 41, 51	54.92%	7
23, 27, 31	58.18%	38	13, 40, 48, 51	54.06%	8
1	102.59%	39	40, 48, 51	77.90%	9
9	102.42%	40	20, 23, 31	67.04%	10
4	140.88%	41	3, 23, 27, 35	51.48%	11
13, 23, 35, 48, 51	75.25%	42	13, 40, 48, 51	30.40%	12
3, 35, 41, 48, 51	90.54%	43	18	107.55%	13
13, 40, 48, 51	62.98%	44	13, 20, 35, 51	59.39%	14
13, 31, 35, 48	68.32%	45	3	100.00%	15
13, 23, 35, 48, 51	71.12%	46	13, 40, 48, 51	60.11%	16
23, 31, 32	25.69%	47	13, 23, 35, 48, 51	68.68%	17
23	264.67%	48	3, 20, 23, 35, 51	76.08%	18
3, 48, 51, 52	82.34%	49	3, 20, 35, 51	58.10%	19
20, 23, 31	37.94%	50	15	132.03%	20
25	100.00%	51	3, 20, 23, 35, 51	64.12%	21
1	291.67%	52	23, 27, 31, 35	36.52%	22
20, 23, 31, 51	59.74%	53	21	385.26%	23
3, 35, 48	49.57%	54	13, 23, 35, 48, 51	72.55%	24
3, 20, 23, 35, 51	61.73%	55	13, 31, 48, 51	56.86%	25
31, 35, 39	79.31%	56	31	54.28%	26
3, 27, 35	74.12%	57	5	129.69%	27
13, 20, 31, 51	72.81%	58	3	100.00%	28
4, 13, 15, 20, 28, 32, 48	100.00%	59	3, 40, 48, 51	88.66%	29
13, 20, 23, 35, 51	56.17%	60	31, 35, 41	51.84%	30

Table 2 : Classification of the efficiencies of greenhouse units.

Classification	Efficiency (%)	Frequency of Greenhouses (N)	Frequency of Greenhouses (%)
1	0-20	0	0
2	20-40	4	7
3	40-60	13	22
4	60-80	20	33
60	100	Total	

40%-60%, 33% of them have an efficiency of 60%-80%, while the efficiency of 38% of the greenhouses is more than 80%. The following diagram is given for a better comparison.

Regarding the efficiency, most of the greenhouse units are in the 80-100 classification (23 greenhouses, 38%). The detailed is shown is the Figure 1.

Figure 1 : Classification of the efficiencies of greenhouse units.

Then, in order to apply the results obtained from the DEA method, the interpretation of the software's output is expressed. Thus, output information obtained

from solving the model for greenhouse number 5 (DMU 5) is analyzed:

1. The objective function's value, that shows efficiency, is $Q = 62.66\%$, i.e. the company's efficiency is 62.66%. In other words, it is inefficient.
2. With consideration of the model's output shown in Table 2, the reference units of greenhouse number 5 are greenhouse numbers 23, 32 and 48. Thus, inputs of the virtual unit 5 are computed as follows:

D_{23} (inputs of unit 23) + D_{32} (inputs of unit 32)

+ D_{48} (inputs of unit 48)

$$0.81 \begin{bmatrix} 160,000,000 \\ 13,250,000 \\ 2,000,000 \\ 700 \end{bmatrix} + 0.15 \begin{bmatrix} 125,000,000 \\ 2160,000 \\ 20,000,000 \\ 500 \end{bmatrix} + 0.04 \begin{bmatrix} 6,400,000,000 \\ 42,500,000 \\ 30,000,000 \\ 500 \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} 57,310,000 \\ 15,67,250 \\ 5,820,000 \\ 662 \end{bmatrix}$$

This output expresses that for greenhouse 5 to reach the efficiency frontier, it should cause its input values to be equal to that of the virtual unit. In other words, it must reduce its manpower cost to IRR. 5,731,000. Moreover, it should reduce its fertilizer, seeds and minerals consumption to IRR. 1,567,250, its payable cost of energy to IRR. 582,000 and its cultivated area to 662 m compared with the amount of the harvested product. This interpretation is applicable to all DMUs so that managers can be informed of how to efficiently use their production resources.

CONCLUSION

Studying the trend of the population growth in the world and as a result, increased demands for food and agricultural products along with the damages caused by the population growth, mankind's greed and also the intensive destruction of the environment have made the use of new agricultural methods unavoidable. In fact, the global community has no choice but to use methods alternative to traditional agricultural methods including greenhouse cultivation.

However, continuous application of these methods irrespective of the efficiency of production units causes them to become uneconomic and as a result, they cannot be used. Hence, the efficiency of greenhouse units in the geography of Guilan province in Iran has been measured here, the results of which

indicate that only about 30% of the greenhouse units are efficient and that necessary attempts should be made to improve the efficiency of the rest of the greenhouses.

Also, for the research results to be applicable, optimum production input values for inefficient units have been computed and suggested as well.

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HETEROISIS AND INTER-RELATIONSHIP OF MAJOR PHYSIOMORPHIC FRUIT YIELD TRAITS IN CHILLI (*Capsicum annuum* L.)

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ABSTRACT: The seeds of nine hybrids along with national check Pusa Jwala were evaluated in a Randomized Block Design in three replications for M.P. plains. The highest positive and significant correlation coefficient of fresh fruit yield plant⁻¹ was noted with dry fruit yield plant⁻¹, number of fruits plant⁻¹, 1000 seed weight, number of seed fruit⁻¹, plant height at maturity, days to maturity and fruit length. Variation was highest for fresh fruit yield plant⁻¹ followed by number of fruits plant⁻¹. High heritability coupled with high genetic advance for traits like number of secondary branches plant⁻¹ at 30 DAT followed by number of fruits plant⁻¹. An overall observation of standard heterosis the hybrids HPH-2024, NCH-913 and Ujjala were recorded the best hybrids for yield and its component characters.

Keywords : *Capsicum annuum*, genetic variability, heritability, correlation.

Chilli (*Capsicum annuum* L.) is an important spice cum vegetable crop for domestic as well as for export values. The crop was introduced in India by portugues and now cultivated all over India produces nearly 8.5 lakh tones followed by China and Pakistan.

The extent of genetic variation for different traits of economic values and their inheritance are pre requisite to breeder for further upgrading yield (Tembhurne *et al.*, 19). Genetic improvement for traits depends upon the nature and amount of genetic variability present in hybrids and their inheritance are pre-requisite for further upgrading yield. Heritability along with genetic advance gives the best picture of efficiency of selection. Genetic advance on the measure the expected gain from the selection applied in a population.

The scope for utilization of heterosis depends mainly upon the direction and magnitude of heterosis. The magnitude of heterosis provides a basis of genetic diversity and guides to choice of desirable parents for developing superior hybrids. Planning and execution of a breeding programme for the improvement of the various quantitative and quality attributes depends, to a great extent upon the magnitude of genetic variability existing in the population. Hence, studies on heterosis with the help of suitable biometrical tools eg. Coefficient of variability, heritability and genetic advance has become indispensable in breeding programme for tangible results of desire values.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

A field experiment was conducted under at RAK College of Agriculture, Sehore during *Kharif*

2012-13. The experiment was laid out in randomized block design with three replications. Nine hybrids along with national check Pusa Jwala were evaluated under three different conditions. Each hybrid was sown in four rows plot of 3 meter² length with 60 cm row to row and 60 cm plant to plant distances. The fertilizer dose 20t FYM, 150 kg N, 80 kg P₂O₅ and 50 kg K₂O ha⁻¹ was applied uniformly and recommended package of practices were adopted for optimum crop growth and plant protection under rainfed condition. Average data were subjected to analysis of variance following Steel (18). Broad sense heritability [h^2 (bs)] was estimated according to Lush (10) Johnson *et al.* (6) and Hanson (3). Heritability values were categorized as low (<30%), moderate (30-60%) and high (>60%). The expected genetic advance (GA %) on 5% selection intensity was estimated and classified as low (<10%), moderate (10-20%) and high (>20%) following the method given by Lush (10). Genotypic and phenotypic correlation coefficients were calculated by standard procedures (Johnson *et al.* 6) and Hanson (3). The analysis of variance was computed as per method given by Panse and Sukhatme (13).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The analysis of variances for all the characters studied has been presented in (Table 1). Mean squares due to genotypes were highly significantly for all the characters, indicating that the presence of genetic diversity in the existing material. Highest value of mean sum of square were recorded for fresh fruit yield plant⁻¹, number of fruit plant⁻¹, dry fruit yield plant⁻¹, fresh fruit yield hectare⁻¹, number of seed plant⁻¹, plant

Table 1a : Analysis of variance for various yield parameters of chilli (mean square).

Characters	Source of variation			
	Replications	Genotypes	Error	
	d.f. 2	d.f. 9	d.f. 18	
Plant height (cm)	30 DAT	3.841	5.430**	0.537
	60 DAT	1.209	162.398**	0.735
	90 DAT	8.737	228.776**	1.968
	120 DAT	25.257	259.398**	6.266
	150 DAT	32.777	271.443**	8.230
	At maturity	3.089	254.857**	3.260
No. of primary branches plant ⁻¹	30 DAT	0.028	0.528**	0.001
	60 DAT	0.016	1.740**	0.106
	90 DAT	2.601	2.421**	0.085
	120 DAT	1.697	4.874**	0.386
	150 DAT	2.536	8.084**	0.083
	At maturity	6.646	12.151**	1.883
No. of secondary branches plant ⁻¹	30 DAT	0.260	0.875**	0.013
	60 DAT	0.438	0.810**	0.003
	90 DAT	2.052	4.349**	0.075
	120 DAT	0.816	14.218**	0.252
	150 DAT	1.097	4.953**	0.005
	At maturity	1.586	6.984**	0.009

Table 1b : Analysis of variance for various yield parameters of chilli (mean square).

Days to first flower initiation	62.533	8.651**	1.274
Days to first fruit initiation	48.533	10.448**	1.348
Days to first picking	14.933	153.170**	23.748
Number of flower clusters ⁻¹	2.105	7.773**	0.073
Number of fruits clusters ⁻¹	1.242	3.058**	0.045
Days to maturity	48.533	142.759**	1.348
Number of fruits plant ⁻¹	1597.38	71832.84**	944.43
Fruit length (cm)	0.910	9.328**	0.056
Number of seed fruit ⁻¹	2.884	1022.42**	2.484
1000 seed weight (g)	0.045	1.844**	0.115
Fruit and seed ratio	0.196	6.051**	0.003
Fresh fruit yield plant ⁻¹ (g)	308.23	89532.96**	2.677
Fresh fruit yield plot ⁻¹ (kg)	13.058	10.237**	0.597
Fresh fruit yield ha ⁻¹ (q)	1611.55	1263.63**	73.79
Dry fruit yield plant ⁻¹ (g)	10.228	3181.31**	0.088
Dry fruit yield plot ⁻¹ (kg)	0.440	0.363**	0.020
Dry fruit yield ha ⁻¹ (q)	54.364	44.830**	2.562

height at 150, 120 DAT, at maturity and 90 DAT (Table 2a, 2b and 2c). Variability is the most important characteristic feature of any population. Estimation of variability is an important prerequisite for realizing response to selection as the progress in the breeding depends upon its amount, nature and magnitude. The genetic proportion of this variability measured in terms of genotypic coefficient of variation (GCV) alone represents the heritable component of total variability (Kumar *et al.*, 7; and Jabeen *et al.* (5).

Genotypic (GCV) and phenotypic (PCV) coefficient of variation

Estimation of components of genetic parameters of variation for yield and its attributes exhibited a wide range of variation for the characters studied ((Table 3a and 3b). High genotypic coefficient of variation was noted for number of secondary branches plant⁻¹ (48.36%), number of fruits plant⁻¹ (44.60%), number of fruits cluster⁻¹ (35.74%) and number of flower cluster⁻¹ (34.13%) Results are in line of Datta and Jana (2) for number of fruits plant⁻¹, Ukkund (20) for number of secondary branches plant⁻¹. While it was found to be lowest in the characters *i.e.*, days to maturity (3.22%) followed by days to first fruit initiation (3.92%), plant height at 30 DAT (4.15%), days to 1st flower initiation (4.36%), number of secondary branches plant⁻¹ at maturity (7.01%), at 150 DAT (7.61%), and at 60 DAT (8.41%), plant height at maturity (10.13%), days to first picking (9.11%), number of secondary branches plant⁻¹ at 90 DAT (11.62%), plant height at 150 DAT (11.41%), plant height at 120 DAT (11.58%), number of primary branches plant⁻¹ at 90 DAT (11.71%), plant height at 90 DAT (12.43%), 1000 seed weight (11.61%), plant height at 60 DAT (13.56%), number of primary branches plant⁻¹ at 120 DAT (12.17%), number of primary branches plant⁻¹ at 150 DAT (14.55%) and number of

Table 2a : Mean performance of morphological parameters of chilli.

Genotypes	Plant height (cm)						No. of primary branches plant ⁻¹					
	30 DAT	60 DAT	90 DAT	120 DAT	150 DAT	At maturity	30 DAT	60 DAT	90 DAT	120 DAT	150 DAT	At maturity
T ₁ -NCH-913	32.47	62.33	79.93	87.47	91.47	100.15	1.85	5.33	8.24	11.40	13.15	15.20
T ₂ -GEN-445	30.00	52.13	62.47	72.67	75.13	86.25	1.10	4.27	7.44	9.93	10.27	11.90
T ₃ -MHCP-317	31.33	54.47	70.20	83.07	86.20	93.85	1.60	5.07	7.85	10.33	11.78	13.70
T ₄ -US-642	29.47	50.47	62.13	71.67	73.60	81.75	1.01	4.20	7.15	9.80	10.05	11.43
T ₅ -Sitara	31.47	57.40	74.87	85.60	89.87	96.45	1.77	5.20	8.02	10.60	12.02	14.37
T ₆ -Ujjala	31.60	59.53	79.53	85.73	90.07	98.05	1.83	5.20	8.12	10.93	12.35	14.87
T ₇ -HPH-2024	32.67	64.40	83.20	95.20	95.47	103.35	1.86	5.47	8.5	11.53	13.55	15.53
T ₈ -DCx-3160	30.80	53.47	64.93	75.87	78.13	86.98	1.31	4.87	7.74	10.13	10.99	12.87
T ₉ -Indam Jwala	29.00	39.53	60.60	68.07	70.20	76.40	0.78	3.13	5.4	7.67	8.30	9.80
T ₁₀ -Pusa Jwala (Check)	29.07	47.53	61.87	68.20	70.73	80.65	0.98	3.87	6.9	8.13	9.80	10.67
C.D. (P=0.05)	1.25	1.47	2.40	4.29	4.92	3.09	0.07	0.55	0.50	1.06	0.49	2.35

Table 2b: Mean performance morphological traits of chilli.

Genotypes	No. of secondary branches plant ⁻¹						Days to first flower initiation	Days to first fruit initiation	Days to first picking	No. of flowers cluster ⁻¹	No. of fruits cluster ⁻¹	Days to maturity
	30 DAT	60 DAT	90 DAT	120 DAT	150 DAT	At maturity						
T ₁ -NCH-913	1.80	6.80	11.20	16.87	18.17	23.57	34.33	43.00	71.00	6.47	3.53	220.67
T ₂ -GEN-445	0.82	5.93	10.27	15.40	16.23	20.87	36.33	44.67	75.67	4.43	2.63	209.33
T ₃ -MHCP-317	1.00	6.27	10.63	15.93	16.93	21.97	35.67	43.67	72.67	4.93	3.23	212.67
T ₄ -US-642	0.70	5.75	9.60	13.47	15.80	20.42	36.67	45.33	76.33	7.60	4.73	207.33
T ₅ -Sitara	1.20	6.36	10.93	16.07	17.40	22.50	35.33	43.33	72.33	3.57	2.87	216.67
T ₆ -Ujjala	1.50	6.55	11.20	16.33	17.87	22.90	35.33	43.33	71.33	3.30	2.30	218.33
T ₇ -HPH-2024	2.10	6.93	11.70	17.47	19.17	24.13	33.33	41.67	69.67	6.47	3.60	224.00
T ₈ -DCx-3160	0.90	6.12	10.43	15.53	16.57	21.47	35.67	44.67	73.67	3.13	2.10	210.67
T ₉ -IndamJwala	0.40	5.30	7.67	10.97	15.13	19.67	39.67	48.00	79.00	3.67	1.57	202.67
T ₁₀ -PusaJwala (C)	0.67	5.65	9.07	11.80	15.47	20.00	37.00	46.67	77.67	3.37	1.47	206.00
C.D. (P=0.05)	0.20	0.10	0.47	0.86	0.12	0.17	1.93	1.99	8.35	0.46	0.36	1.99

Table 2c : Mean performance of yield parameters of chilli.

Genotypes	No. of fruits plant ⁻¹	Fruit length (cm)	No. of seeds fruit ⁻¹	1000 seed weight (g)	Fruit and seed ratio	Fresh fruit yield plant ⁻¹ (g)	Fresh fruit yield plot ⁻¹ (kg)	Fresh fruit yield ha ⁻¹ (q)	Dry fruit yield plant ⁻¹ (g)	Dry fruit yield plot ⁻¹ (kg)	Dry fruit yield ha ⁻¹ (q)
T ₁ -NCH-913	523.33	10.19	86.47	7.23	9.04	916.00	9.23	102.58	168.07	1.69	18.81
T ₂ -GEN-445	239.80	7.45	75.60	6.11	7.85	647.67	6.27	69.62	117.54	1.14	12.63
T ₃ -MHCP-317	335.53	8.47	76.27	5.56	8.50	719.67	7.30	81.10	133.03	1.33	14.78
T ₄ -US-642	238.33	6.39	61.33	5.39	6.85	645.00	6.15	68.33	116.85	1.11	12.37
T ₅ -Sitara	353.33	10.36	93.20	7.03	8.90	812.33	8.80	97.77	147.97	1.61	17.85
T ₆ -Ujjala	458.33	9.91	63.80	7.17	9.00	870.67	9.22	102.40	158.59	1.68	18.67
T ₇ -HPH-2024	653.33	9.46	74.47	7.48	9.95	970.33	9.64	107.06	181.03	1.80	20.00
T ₈ -DCx-3160	252.67	10.46	118.53	6.92	8.10	730.33	6.74	74.88	130.85	1.22	13.59
T ₉ -IndamJwala	193.00	6.12	58.33	5.64	5.50	380.00	4.72	52.40	68.47	0.85	9.44
T ₁₀ -PusaJwala (C)	198.20	6.59	62.40	6.87	6.10	615.67	4.81	53.40	111.53	0.87	9.67
C.D. (P=0.05)	52.71	0.40	2.70	0.58	0.09	2.80	1.32	14.73	0.50	0.24	2.74

secondary branches plant⁻¹ at 120 DAT (14.40%) confirming to reports of Tembhurne (19). Rest of the

characters viz., number of primary branches plant⁻¹ at 30 DAT (29.74%) followed by fresh fruit yield plot

Table 3a : Genetic parameters in different characters in chilli

Traits	Stages	Grand Mean	Range		Coefficient of variations		Heritability % (BS)	Genetic Advance	GA as % of mean
			Min.	Max.	Phe.	Gen.			
Plant height	30 DAT	30.78	29.00	32.67	4.78	4.15	75.21	2.28	7.41
	60 DAT	54.12	39.53	64.40	13.65	13.56	98.65	15.02	27.75
	90 DAT	69.97	60.60	83.20	12.59	12.43	97.46	17.68	25.27
	120 DAT	79.35	68.07	95.20	12.00	11.58	93.09	18.26	23.01
	150 DAT	82.09	70.20	95.47	11.93	11.41	91.42	18.45	22.47
	Maturity	90.39	76.40	103.35	10.33	10.13	96.26	18.51	20.48
No. of primary branches plant ⁻¹	30 DAT	1.40	0.78	1.86	29.89	29.74	99.02	0.86	61.39
	60 DAT	4.66	3.13	5.46	17.32	15.84	83.66	1.39	29.84
	90 DAT	7.53	5.40	8.50	12.34	11.71	90.11	1.73	22.92
	120 DAT	10.04	7.66	11.53	13.66	12.17	79.48	2.25	22.37
	150 DAT	11.22	8.30	13.55	14.77	14.55	96.97	3.31	29.53
	Maturity	13.03	9.80	15.53	17.67	14.19	64.50	3.06	23.49
No. of secondary branches plant ⁻¹	30 DAT	1.10	0.40	2.10	49.51	48.36	95.42	1.08	98.06
	60 DAT	6.16	5.30	6.93	8.47	8.41	98.67	1.06	17.23
	90 DAT	10.27	7.67	11.70	11.93	11.62	94.98	2.40	23.33
	120 DAT	14.98	10.97	17.47	14.79	14.40	94.86	4.33	28.90
	150 DAT	16.87	15.13	19.17	7.62	7.61	99.67	2.64	15.66
	Maturity	21.74	19.67	24.13	7.03	7.01	99.57	3.13	14.42

Table 3b: Genetic parameters in different characters in chilli

Characters	Grand Mean	Range		Coefficient of variations		Heritability % (BS)	Genetic Advance	GA as % of mean
		Min.	Max.	Phe.	Gen.			
Days to 1 st flower initiation	35.93	33.33	39.67	5.38	4.36	65.87	2.62	7.30
Days to first fruit initiation	44.43	41.67	48.00	4.71	3.92	69.23	2.99	6.72
Days to first picking	73.93	69.67	79.00	11.35	9.11	64.50	10.87	14.70
Number of flower clusters ⁻¹	4.69	3.13	7.60	34.62	34.13	97.21	3.25	69.38
Number of fruits clusters ⁻¹	2.80	1.47	4.73	36.54	35.74	95.65	200.94	71.76
Days to maturity	212.83	202.67	224.00	3.27	3.22	97.22	13.95	6.55
Number of fruits plant ⁻¹	344.58	193.00	653.33	45.49	44.60	96.16	310.52	90.11
Fruit length (cm)	8.53	6.12	10.46	20.77	20.58	98.21	3.59	42.07
Number of seed fruit ⁻¹	77.04	58.33	118.53	24.02	23.93	99.27	37.85	49.12
1000 seed weight (g)	6.54	5.39	7.48	12.72	11.61	83.33	1.43	21.83
Fruit and seed ratio	7.97	5.50	9.95	17.81	17.80	99.84	2.92	36.67
Fresh fruit yield plant ⁻¹ (g)	730.76	380.00	970.33	23.64	23.64	99.99	355.85	48.70
Fresh fruit yield plot ⁻¹ (kg)	7.28	4.72	9.64	26.79	24.60	84.31	3.39	46.58
Fresh fruit yield ha ⁻¹ (q)	80.95	52.40	107.06	26.79	24.60	84.31	37.67	46.54
Dry fruit yield plant ⁻¹ (g)	133.39	68.47	181.03	24.41	24.41	99.99	67.08	50.29
Dry fruit yield plot ⁻¹ (kg)	1.33	0.85	1.80	27.61	25.40	84.60	0.64	48.12

⁻¹ (24.60%), fresh fruit yield ha⁻¹ (24.60%), dry fruit yield plot⁻¹ (25.40%), dry fruit yield ha⁻¹ (25.40%), dry fruit yield plant⁻¹ (24.41%), number of seeds fruit⁻¹ (23.93%), fresh fruit yield plant⁻¹ (23.64%), fruit length (20.58%), fruit and seed ratio (17.80%). Results are in agreement with Sharma *et al.* (16) for fruit and seed ratio, number of primary branches plant⁻¹ at 60 DAT

(15.84%) and number of primary branches plant⁻¹ at maturity (14.19%) were showed moderate genotypic coefficient of variation confirming to Lakhare *et al.* (9) and Singh and Singh (17).

The phenotypic coefficient of variation ranges from 3.27% for days to maturity to 49.51% for number of secondary branches plant⁻¹ at 30DAT. The highest phenotypic coefficient of variation was observed for

Table 3c: Mean performance of yield parameters of chilli

.Genotypes	No. of fruits plant ⁻¹	Fruit length (cm)	No. of seeds fruit ⁻¹	1000 seed weight (g)	Fruit and seed ratio	Fresh fruit yield plant ⁻¹ (g)	Fresh fruit yield plot ⁻¹ (kg)	Fresh fruit yield ha ⁻¹ (q)	Dry fruit yield plant ⁻¹ (g)	Dry fruit yield plot ⁻¹ (kg)	Dry fruit yield ha ⁻¹ (q)
T ₁ -NCH-913	523.33	10.19	86.47	7.23	9.04	916.00	9.23	102.58	168.07	1.69	18.81
T ₂ -GEN-445	239.80	7.45	75.60	6.11	7.85	647.67	6.27	69.62	117.54	1.14	12.63
T ₃ -MHCP-317	335.53	8.47	76.27	5.56	8.50	719.67	7.30	81.10	133.03	1.33	14.78
T ₄ -US-642	238.33	6.39	61.33	5.39	6.85	645.00	6.15	68.33	116.85	1.11	12.37
T ₅ -Sitara	353.33	10.36	93.20	7.03	8.90	812.33	8.80	97.77	147.97	1.61	17.85
T ₆ -Ujjala	458.33	9.91	63.80	7.17	9.00	870.67	9.22	102.40	158.59	1.68	18.67
T ₇ -HPH-2024	653.33	9.46	74.47	7.48	9.95	970.33	9.64	107.06	181.03	1.80	20.00
T ₈ -DCX-3160	252.67	10.46	118.53	6.92	8.10	730.33	6.74	74.88	130.85	1.22	13.59
T ₉ -Indam Jwala	193.00	6.12	58.33	5.64	5.50	380.00	4.72	52.40	68.47	0.85	9.44
T ₁₀ -Pusa Jwala (C)	198.20	6.59	62.40	6.87	6.10	615.67	4.81	53.40	111.53	0.87	9.67
C.D. (P=0.05)	52.71	0.40	2.70	0.58	0.09	2.80	1.32	14.73	0.50	0.24	2.74

number of secondary branches plant⁻¹ at 30DAT (49.51%), number of fruits plant⁻¹ (45.49%), number of fruits clusters⁻¹ (36.54%) and number of flower cluster⁻¹ (34.62%) confirming to the results of Datta and Jana (2) for number of fruits plant⁻¹ and Ukkund (20) for number of secondary branches plant⁻¹. However, it was found lowest for days to maturity (3.27%) followed by days to first fruit initiation (4.71%), plant height at 30 DAT (4.78%), days to 1st flower initiation (5.38%), number of secondary branches plant⁻¹ at maturity (7.03%), at 150 DAT (7.62%), and at 60 DAT (8.47%), plant height at maturity (10.33%), days to first picking (11.35%), number of secondary branches plant⁻¹ at 90 DAT (11.93%), plant height at 150 DAT (11.93%), plant height at 120 DAT (12.00%), number of primary branches plant⁻¹ at 90 DAT (12.34%), plant height at 90 DAT (12.59%), 1000 seed weight (12.72%), plant height at 60 DAT (13.65%), number of primary branches plant⁻¹ at 120 DAT (13.66%), number of primary branches plant⁻¹ at 150 DAT (14.77%) and number of secondary branches plant⁻¹ at 120 DAT (14.79%). The remaining characters such as number of primary branches plant⁻¹ at 30 DAT (29.89%) followed by dry fruit yield plot⁻¹ (27.61%), dry

fruit yield ha⁻¹ (27.61%), fresh fruit yield plot⁻¹ (26.79%), fresh fruit yield ha⁻¹ (26.79%), dry fruit yield plant⁻¹ (24.41%), number of seed fruit⁻¹ (24.02%), fresh fruit yield plant⁻¹ (23.64%), fruit length (20.77%), fruit and seed ratio (17.81%), number of primary branches plant⁻¹ at maturity (17.67%) and number of primary branches plant⁻¹ at 60 DAT (17.32%) were showed moderate phenotypic coefficient of variation by confirming results of Sharma *et al.* (16).

Heritability

Heritability (broad sense) was recorded very high for fresh fruit yield plant⁻¹ (99.99%) followed by dry fruit yield plant⁻¹ (99.99%), fruit and seed ratio (99.84%) and number of secondary branches plant⁻¹ at 150 DAT (99.67%) (Table 3a and 3b). However, it was recorded high for dry fruit yield plot⁻¹ (84.60%) followed by dry fruit yield ha⁻¹ (84.60%), fresh fruit yield plot⁻¹ (84.31%) and fresh fruit yield ha⁻¹ (84.31%). Medium estimate of heritability was recorded for days to first fruit initiation (69.23%), days to 1st flower initiation (65.87%), number of primary branches plant⁻¹ at maturity (64.50%) and days to first picking (64.50%) for plant height, fruit length, number of fruits plant⁻¹ and fresh fruit yield. Findings are in consonance with Ukkund, (20).

Table 4: Estimates of genotypic and phenotypic correlation coefficients among yield and its contributing traits in chilli.

Characters	No. of primary branches plant ⁻¹ at maturity	No. of secondary branches plant ⁻¹ at maturity	Days to 1 st flower initiation	Days to first fruit initiation	Days to first picking	No. of flower cluster ⁻¹	Days to maturity	No. of fruits cluster ⁻¹	Days to maturity	No. of fruits cluster ⁻¹	Days to maturity	Fruit length (cm)	No. of seed fruit ⁻¹	1000 seed wt. (g)	Fruit and seed ratio	Dry fruit yield plant ⁻¹ (g)	Fresh fruit yield plant ⁻¹ (g)
Plant height at maturity	G	0.127	0.434	0.640	0.460	0.530	0.660	0.693	0.660	0.660	0.660	0.284	0.343	-0.496	-0.252	0.470	0.473
	P	0.138	0.342*	0.534**	0.372*	0.521**	0.642**	0.664**	0.642**	0.642**	0.642**	0.286	0.327	-0.434*	-0.244	0.460*	0.463
No. of primary branches plant ⁻¹ at maturity	G		0.487	0.194	-0.312	0.142	0.172	0.352	0.172	0.172	0.172	0.660	0.330	-0.191	0.531	-0.403	-0.394
	P		0.396**	0.234	-0.160	0.140	0.168	0.290	0.168	0.168	0.168	0.541**	0.263	-0.157	0.437	-0.322	-0.315
No. of secondary branches plant ⁻¹ at maturity	G		0.630	0.575	0.380	-0.122	0.436	0.137	0.436	0.436	0.436	0.453	-0.205	0.150	0.060	-0.104	-0.092
	P		0.504**	0.466**	0.317	-0.117	0.425*	0.136	0.425*	0.425*	0.425*	0.445**	-0.201	0.132	0.059	-0.103	-0.092
Days to 1 st flower initiation	G			0.933	0.506	0.321	0.893	0.345	0.893	0.893	0.893	0.041	0.160	-0.597	0.220	-0.651	-0.641
	P			0.861**	0.277	0.268	0.784**	0.303	0.784**	0.784**	0.784**	0.055	0.115	-0.308	0.175	-0.526*	-0.518
Days to first fruit initiation	G				0.705	0.430	0.939	0.530	0.939	0.939	0.939	-0.078	0.136	-0.600	-0.179	-0.508	-0.498
	P				0.441**	0.350*	0.920**	0.416*	0.920**	0.920**	-0.049	0.099	-0.386*	-0.150	-0.421*	-0.413	-0.413
Days to first picking	G					0.128	0.637	0.103	0.637	0.637	-0.012	-0.644	0.150	-0.366	-0.005	-0.004	-0.004
	P					0.145	0.496**	0.090	0.496**	0.496**	0.004	-0.512*	0.093	-0.294	-0.004	-0.003	-0.003
No. of flower cluster ⁻¹	G						0.406	0.914	0.406	0.406	-0.13	0.582	-0.780	0.116	0.116	-0.425	-0.42
	P						0.394*	0.888**	0.394*	0.394*	-0.12	0.571*	-0.693*	0.116	0.419*	0.416	0.416
No. of fruits cluster ⁻¹	G						0.509		0.509	0.509	0.101	0.649	-0.730	-0.02	-0.437	-0.42	-0.42
	P						0.486**		0.486**	0.486**	0.101	0.630*	-0.665	-0.021	0.427*	0.420	0.420
Days to maturity	G										-0.024	0.136	0.565	0.267	0.476	0.469	0.469
	P										-0.019	0.130	0.488*	-0.263	0.469*	0.462	0.462
No. of fruits plant ⁻¹	G										0.069	-0.542	0.654	-0.507	0.834	0.829	0.829
	P										0.065	-0.530*	0.609*	-0.497	0.818*	0.813	0.813
Fruit length (cm)	G											-0.050	0.251	0.350	0.374	0.372	0.372
	P											-0.057	0.240	0.349	0.370*	0.368	0.368

Genetic advance

Genetic advance as percentage of mean ranged from 6.55% for days to maturity to 98.06% number of secondary branches plant⁻¹ at 30 DAT. The highest estimate of genetic advance as percentage of mean was recorded for number of secondary branches plant⁻¹ at 30 DAT (98.06%), followed by number of fruits plant⁻¹ (90.11%) (Table 3a and 3b). Whereas, low estimates were recorded for days to maturity (6.55%), days to first fruit initiation (6.72%), days to 1st flower initiation (7.30%) and plant height at 30 DAT (7.41%) High heritability coupled with low genetic advance as percentage of mean was observed for days to maturity, plant height at 30 DAT, number of secondary branches plant⁻¹ at maturity, number of secondary branches plant⁻¹ at 150 DAT and number of secondary branches plant⁻¹ at 60 DAT. Revealed that the predominance of non-additive gene action in the expression of these characters The results are in line of Jabeen *et al.* (5) and Singh and Singh (17).

Correlation Coefficient analysis

Genotypic correlation coefficients, in general, were of higher magnitude than the corresponding phenotypic correlation coefficient for all the characters.

The results of phenotypic correlation coefficients have been discussed only as the genotypic and environmental correlation were mostly influenced by the environmental conditions, hence phenotypic correlation will give the correct idea about the association between two variables (Table 4).

Correlation coefficient of fresh fruit yield plant⁻¹ was recorded strong positive and significant with dry fruit yield plant⁻¹ (0.999), number of fruits plant⁻¹ (0.813), 1000 seed weight (0.594) and number of seed fruit⁻¹ (0.510). Plant height expressed significant and positive correlation with number of fruits cluster⁻¹ (0.664), days to maturity (0.642) and days to first fruit initiation (0.534). Number of primary branches plant⁻¹ at maturity was observed significant and positive with number of secondary branches plant⁻¹ at maturity (0.587) and fruit length (0.541). Number of secondary branches plant⁻¹ at maturity was observed significant and positive with days to 1st flower initiation (0.504) and days to first fruit initiation (0.466). Days to 1st flower initiation was exhibited significant and positive with days to 1st flower initiation (0.861) and days to maturity (0.784). Significant and negative association of this character was recorded with dry fruit yield plant⁻¹ (-0.526), fresh fruit yield plant⁻¹ (-0.518) and number of

fruits plant⁻¹ (-0.457). Days to 1st fruit initiation was found positive and significant with days to maturity (0.920) and days to first picking (0.441). Significant and negative association of this character was recorded with dry fruit yield plant⁻¹ (-0.421) and fresh fruit yield plant⁻¹ (-0.413). Days to first picking was observed significant and positive with days to maturity (0.496) and it was significant and negative with number of seed fruit⁻¹ (-0.512). Number of flowers cluster⁻¹ was observed significant and positive with number of fruits cluster⁻¹ (0.888) and number of seed fruit⁻¹ (0.571) and it was significant and negative with 1000 seeds weight (-0.693). Number of fruits cluster⁻¹ was observed significant and positive with number of seed fruit⁻¹ (0.630) and days to maturity (0.486) and it was significant and negative with 1000 seed weight (-0.665). Days to maturity expressed a significant and positive association with and 1000 seed weight (0.488) and dry fruit yield plant⁻¹ (0.469). Number of fruits plant⁻¹ was recorded positive and significant with dry fruit yield plant⁻¹ (0.818), fresh fruit yield plant⁻¹ (0.813) and 1000 seed weight (0.609). Results are in agreement with Chaudhary *et al.* (1), Kumar *et al.*, (7), Manna and Paul (12) and Sharma *et al.* (16) Significant and negative association of this character was recorded with number of seeds fruit⁻¹ (-0.530) and fruit and seed ratio (-0.497). Fruit length expressed a significant and positive association with dry fruit yield plant⁻¹ (0.370) and fresh fruit yield plant⁻¹ (0.368). Number of seed fruit⁻¹ showed positive and significant association with dry fruit yield plant⁻¹ (0.511), fresh fruit yield plant⁻¹ (0.510) and it was observed significant and negative association with 1000 seed weight (-0.746). 1000 seed weight exhibited positive and significant with dry fruit yield plant⁻¹ (0.590) and fresh fruit yield plant⁻¹ (0.594). Fruit and seed ratio exhibited negative and significant with dry fruit yield plant⁻¹ (-0.524) and fresh fruit yield plant⁻¹ (-0.518). Dry fruit yield plant⁻¹ exhibited positive and significant with fresh fruit yield plant⁻¹ (0.999) Chaudhary *et al.* (1), Padhar and Zaveri (14) and Singh and Singh (17) had also reported similar findings.

Standard Heterosis

Heterosis estimates over standard parent have been done the superiority of hybrid over the standard parent is of practical value for the plant breeder. Therefore, only heterosis over standard parents will be discussed. The heterosis for most of the characters was observed in either directions (*i.e.* positive and

Table 5a : Standard heterosis of morphological parameters of chilli.

Genotypes	Plant height (cm) at						No. of primary branches plant ⁻¹ at					
	30 DAT	60 DAT	90 DAT	120 DAT	150 DAT	At maturity	30 DAT	60 DAT	90 DAT	120 DAT	150 DAT	At maturity
T ₁ -NCH-913	11.70*	31.14*	29.19*	28.26*	29.32*	24.18*	88.78*	37.73*	19.42*	40.22*	34.18*	42.46
T ₂ -GEN-445	3.20	9.68**	0.97	6.55	6.22	6.94	12.24	10.34	7.83	22.14	4.80	11.53
T ₃ -MHCP-317	7.77	14.60*	13.46*	21.80*	21.87*	16.37*	63.27*	31.01*	13.77	27.06	20.20*	28.40
T ₄ -US-642	1.38	6.19	0.42	5.09	4.06	1.36	3.06	8.53	3.62	20.54	2.55	7.12
T ₅ -Sitara	8.26	20.77*	21.01*	25.51*	27.06*	19.59*	80.61*	34.37*	16.23*	30.38*	22.65*	34.68
T ₆ -Ujjala	8.70	25.25*	28.54*	25.70*	27.34*	21.57*	86.73*	34.37*	17.68*	34.44*	26.02*	39.36
T ₇ -HPH-2024	12.38*	35.49*	34.48*	39.59*	34.98*	28.15*	89.80*	41.34*	23.19*	41.82*	38.27*	45.55
T ₈ -DCx-3160	5.95	12.50*	4.95	11.25	10.46	7.85	33.67*	25.84	12.17	24.60	12.14*	20.62
T ₉ -IndamJwala	-0.24	-16.83**	-2.05	-0.19	-0.75	-5.27	-20.41**	-19.12	-21.74**	-5.66	-15.31**	-8.15
T ₁₀ -Mean of Standard Parent (Pusa Jwala)	29.07	47.53	61.87	68.20	70.73	80.65	0.98	3.87	6.9	8.13	9.8	10.67

Table 5b : Standard heterosis of chilli.

Genotypes	No. of secondary branches plant ⁻¹ at						Days to first flower initiation	Days to first fruit initiation	Days to first picking	Number of flower clusters ⁻¹	Number of fruits clusters ⁻¹	Days to maturity
	30 DAT	60 DAT	90 DAT	120 DAT	150 DAT	At maturity						
T ₁ -NCH-913	168.66**	20.35*	23.48*	42.97*	17.45*	17.85*	-7.22	-7.86	-8.59	91.99*	140.14**	7.12**
T ₂ -GEN-445	22.39	4.96*	13.23*	30.51*	4.91**	4.35**	-1.81	-4.29	-2.57	31.45*	78.91*	1.62
T ₃ -MHCP-317	49.25	10.97*	17.20*	35.00*	9.44**	9.85**	-3.59	-6.43	-6.44	46.29*	119.73**	3.24**
T ₄ -US-642	4.48	1.77	5.84	14.15	2.13*	2.10*	-0.89	-2.87	-1.73	125.52**	221.77**	0.65
T ₅ -Sitara	79.10*	12.57*	20.51*	36.19*	12.48*	12.50*	-4.51	-7.16	-6.88	5.93*	95.24*	5.18**
T ₆ -Ujjala	123.88**	15.93*	23.48*	38.39*	15.51*	14.50*	-4.51	-7.16	-8.16	-2.08	56.46*	5.99**
T ₇ -HPH-2024	213.43**	22.65*	29.00*	48.05*	23.92*	20.65*	-9.92	-10.71*	-10.30	91.99*	144.90**	8.74**
T ₈ -DCx-3160	34.33	8.32**	14.99*	31.61*	7.11**	7.35**	-3.59	-4.29	-5.15	-7.12*	42.86*	2.27*
T ₉ -IndamJwala	-40.30	-6.19*	-15.44**	-7.03	-2.20*	-1.65	7.22	2.85	1.71	8.90**	6.80*	-1.62
T ₁₀ - Mean of Standard Parent (Pusa Jwala)	0.67	5.65	9.07	11.8	15.47	20.00	37.00	46.67	77.67	3.37	1.47	206

negative). Fresh fruit yield plant⁻¹ (g). Highest significant and positive heterotic effect was recorded in hybrid HPH-2024 (57.61%) followed by NCH-913 (48.78%) and Ujjala (41.42%). While, it was recorded maximum significant and negative heterotic value -38.28% in hybrid IndamJwala. Fresh fruit yield per plot and per hectare yield performance hybrid HPH-2024 was significantly superior over standard check it exhibit 100.42 and 100.49% for plot⁻¹ and ha⁻¹, respectively

heterotic effect followed by NCH-913 (91.89 and 92.10% for plot⁻¹ and ha⁻¹, respectively), Ujjala (91.68 and 91.76% for plot⁻¹ and ha⁻¹, respectively) and Sitara (82.95 and 83.09% for plot⁻¹ and ha⁻¹, respectively). Dry fruit yield plant⁻¹ (g) Highest significant and positive heterotic effect was recorded in hybrid HPH-2024 (62.32%) followed by NCH-913 (50.69%) and Ujjala (42.19%). While, it was recorded maximum significant and negative heterotic value

Table 5c : Standard heterosis of yield parameters of chilli

Genotypes	Number of fruits plant ⁻¹	Fruit length (cm)	Number of seed fruit ⁻¹	1000 seed weight (g)	Fruit and seed ratio	Fresh fruit yield plant ⁻¹ (g)	Fresh fruit yield plot ⁻¹ (kg)	Fresh fruit yield ha ⁻¹ (q)	Dry fruit yield plant ⁻¹ (g)	Dry fruit yield plot ⁻¹ (kg)	Dry fruit yield ha ⁻¹ (q)
T ₁ -NCH-913	164.04**	54.63*	38.57*	5.24	48.20*	48.78*	91.89*	92.10*	50.69*	94.25*	94.52*
T ₂ -GEN-445	20.99	13.05	21.15*	-11.06	28.69*	5.20**	30.35	30.37	5.39**	31.03	30.61
T ₃ -MHCP-317	69.29*	28.53*	22.23*	-19.07*	39.34*	16.89*	51.77	51.87	19.28*	52.87	52.84
T ₄ -US-642	20.25	-3.03	-1.71	-21.54*	12.30*	4.76**	27.86	27.96	4.77**	27.59	27.92
T ₅ -Sitara	78.27*	57.21*	49.36*	2.33	45.90*	31.94*	82.95*	83.09*	32.67*	85.06*	84.59*
T ₆ -Ujjala	131.25**	50.38*	2.24	4.37	47.54*	41.42*	91.68*	91.76*	42.19*	93.10*	93.07*
T ₇ -HPH-2024	229.63**	43.55*	19.34*	8.88	63.11*	57.61*	100.42**	100.49**	62.32*	106.90**	106.83**
T ₈ -DCx-3160	27.48	58.73*	89.95*	0.73	32.79*	18.62*	40.12	40.22	17.32*	40.23	40.54
T ₉ -Indam Jwala	-2.62	-7.13	-6.52	-17.90	-9.84**	-38.28*	-1.87	-1.87	-38.61*	-2.30	-2.38

Table 6 : Categorization of chilli hybrids based on quality parameter.

Genotypes	Shape of fruits	Size of fruits	Flowers colour	Fruits colour	Breaing habit
T ₁ -NCH-913	Straight	Long	White	Dark green	Pendent
T ₂ -GEN-445	Straight	Medium	White	Green	Pendent
T ₃ -MHCP-317	Straight	Medium	White	Dark green	Pendent
T ₄ -US-642	Straight	Medium	White	Dark green	Pendent
T ₅ -Sitara	Straight	Long	White	Green	Pendent
T ₆ -Ujjala	Straight	Long	White	Dark green	Pendent
T ₇ -HPH-2024	Straight	Long	White	Green	Pendent
T ₈ -DCx-3160	Straight	Long	White	Green	Pendent
T ₉ -IndamJwala	Straight	Medium	White	Dark green	Pendent
T ₁₀ -PusaJwala (C)	Indefinitely curved	Long	White	Light green	Upright

-38.61% in hybrid IndamJwala. Hybrid HPH-2024 was recorded maximum positive heterotic effect 106.90 and 106.83% for plot⁻¹ and ha⁻¹, respectively followed by NCH-913 (94.25 and 94.52% for plot⁻¹ and ha⁻¹, respectively) and Ujjala (93.10 and 93.07% for plot⁻¹ and ha⁻¹, respectively). Whereas hybrid Indam Jwala was recorded negative hetrotic effect -2.30 and -2.38% for plot⁻¹ and ha⁻¹, respectively. Similar findings have also been reported by Prajapati and Agalodia (15), Singh and Singh (17), Krishnamurthy *et al.* (8), Chaudhary *et al.* (1) and Hasanuzzaman (4).

An overall observation of standard heterosis the hybrids HPH-2024, NCH-913 and Ujjala were recorded the best hybrids for yield and its component characters. Hybrid HPH-2024 exhibited tall plant, more primary and secondary branches, early flower, fruit initiation and picking, late maturity, more number of fruits plant⁻¹, high seed weight, higher fruit and seed ratio, fresh and dry fruit yield plant⁻¹, plot⁻¹ and hectare⁻¹. While

hybrid DCx-3160 was recorded long fruit and higher number of seeds fruit⁻¹ (Table 5a, 5b and 5c).

Quality parameters

Considerable variability was observed for fruit shape i.e. straight, slightly curved and indefinitely curved. All the genotypes showed straight fruit shape except Pusa Jwala (C) which recorded indefinitely curved fruit shape. Variation was observed among the genotypes for size of fruits i.e. big, medium and small. Size of fruits was observed to be medium in the genotypes GEN-445, MHCP-317, US-642 and Indam Jwala. Rest of the genotypes were found long sized fruits. The colour of flower was observed to be light purple, purple and white. All the genotypes had white flower. Colour of fruits was observed to be dark green, green, light green, purple and yellowish green. Genotypes NCH-913, MHCP-317, US-642, Ujjala and Indam Jwala exhibited dark green fruits. Pusa Jwala (C) was observed light green fruits (Table 6).

Remaining genotypes exhibited green fruits. In all the genotypes bearing of fruits was pendent type except PusaJwala (C) which bears upright fruits (Manju and Sreelathakumary, 11).

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EFFECT OF POST HARVEST TREATMENTS ON QUALITY AND SHELF LIFE OF AONLA CULTIVARS

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ABSTRACT : Freshly harvested mature fruits of aonla (*Emblica officinalis* Gaertn) cultivars namely NA-7, NA-10, Chakaiya and a wild aonla were dipped in GA₃ 100 mg L⁻¹, 200 mg L⁻¹, 300 mg L⁻¹, MH 100 mg L⁻¹, 200 mg L⁻¹, 300 mg L⁻¹ and CaCl₂ 10 g L⁻¹, 20 g L⁻¹, 30 g L⁻¹ solutions. Fruits were surface dried, packed in nylon net bags and kept in room temperature (15.5±4°C) and RH 62.7%. Among the different post harvest treatments, it was found that GA₃ 200 mg L⁻¹ was best in reducing the physiological loss. No pathological loss was observed in all the treatments upto 14 days of storage. The maximum TSS content was recorded with GA₃ treatment. GA₃ 300 mg L⁻¹ treatment gave better retention of ascorbic acid and malic acid during the storage of aonla.

Keywords : *Emblica officinalis*, bioregulators, ascorbic acid, storage life.

Aonla (*Emblica officinalis* Gaertn), popularly known as Indian gooseberry, is a small sized, minor subtropical fruit belonging to the family Euphorbiaceae. It is thought to be native of India, Ceylon, Malaysia and China. It thrives well throughout tropical and subtropical India and is wild or cultivated in the region extending from the base of Himalaya to Ceylon and Malaysia to south China. It can be grown successfully in dry and neglected region owing to its hardy nature, suitability to various kinds of wasteland. The major difference between these wild trees and the large-fruited types cultivated in the plains is of winter-hardiness. Whereas the improved types are highly susceptible to frost injury, the trees of wild aonla are not damaged at all. It is a rich source of vitamin C and its content of ascorbic acid is next to only that of Barbados cherry (*Malpighia glabra* L.). The important varieties grown in India are Banarasi, Chakaiya, Pink tinged, Krishna, Kanchan, Francis, Pratapgarh, Hathijhool, NA-7 and NA-10.

The medicinal properties of aonla have been mentioned in old *Ayurvedic* texts, such as *Charaksamhita* and *Sushrutsamhita* (Kirtikar and Basu, 5). Aonla preserve has the beneficial effect of purifying blood. This also helps in reducing the cholesterol levels in blood and in improving eye sight. It lowers the risk of cancer. Aonla increases the red blood cells and haemoglobin. Leaves of aonla are useful in curing conjunctivitis, inflammation, diarrhoea, dysentery. The aonla preserve is one of the specialties of the Indian fruit-preservation industry. In order to fulfill this demand

the fruit is to be transported to places other than the centre of production as its storage in ambient atmosphere is very limited. Growth regulator and fumigates applied as post harvest treatment have been reported to increase the shelf life of the fruits (Khader *et al.*, 4; Yadav and Singh, 13). Keeping the above facts in mind, present investigation was conducted to evaluate the effect of growth regulators and chemicals on biochemical changes in aonla fruits during storage.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The present investigation was carried out at the Department of Horticulture, HNB Garhwal University, Srinagar (Garhwal) during the year 2010-11. The freshly mature fruits of aonla cultivars namely NA-7, NA-10, Chakaiya and wild aonla were harvested from 5 years old plants standing at Horticultural Research Centre of University in morning hours and brought to laboratory of Horticulture Department and were dipped in GA₃ (100 mg L⁻¹, 200 mg L⁻¹, 300 mg L⁻¹), MH (100 mg L⁻¹, 200 mg L⁻¹, 300 mg L⁻¹) and CaCl₂ (10 g L⁻¹, 20 g L⁻¹, 30 g L⁻¹) solutions. The fruits after treatment were surface dried and then packed in nylon net bags. Each bag was packed with 35 fruits each and all the treatments were replicated 3 times. These bags were kept in room temperature (15.5±4°C) and RH of 62.7%. The treated fruits were kept for recording the observation with the intervals of 7 days up to 35 days. Pathological losses were recorded by visual observation; the physiological loss in weight (PLW) of the fruit was determined on the basis of initial weight of

the fruit and loss in weight that occurred and were expressed in per cent, total soluble solids were recorded by hand refractometer and the values were corrected for 20°C, ascorbic acid and acidity content were determined by titration method according to Ranganna (12). Finally statistical analysis was done for all the data obtained.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Physiological fruit weight loss was increased with the days of storage in all treatment. The minimum fruit weight loss (17.67%) was recorded in GA₃ 200 mg L⁻¹ treatment in NA-7 while maximum fruit weight loss (42.19%) was observed in control (Table 1). In cultivar NA-10, the minimum fruit weight loss (27.729%) was noticed in CaCl₂ 10 g L⁻¹ treatment while maximum fruit weight loss (56.72%) was in control set. In cultivar Chakaiya and wild aonla, the minimum fruit weight loss (19.18% and 36.68%, respectively) was noticed with

Chakaiya (28.57%) in CaCl₂ 30 g L⁻¹ treatment. The maximum pathological loss of fruits was noticed in control under all cultivars studied (Table 2). Yadav and Singh (13) have also reported lowest losses in weight (11.09%) and decay (14.43%) and prolonged shelf life in aonla fruits by two pre harvest sprays of 1% calcium nitrate + 0.1% Topsin-M.

Total soluble solids (TSS) increased with the increase in the duration of storage irrespective of treatments. Among the different treatments, the maximum TSS content (39.82%) was increased in NA-7 fruits treated with GA₃ 100 mg L⁻¹ and 44.48% increased in NA-10 fruits under same treatment after 35 days of storage. In wild aonla, TSS was increased in GA₃ 200 mg L⁻¹ and 300 mg L⁻¹ treatments. In Chakaiya cultivar, the highest TSS was recorded in CaCl₂ treated fruits (Table 3). Increase in TSS due post harvest application of chemicals is line of Nishad *et al.* (10) and Kumar *et al.* (6). Decrease in malic acid

Table 1: Effect of post harvest treatments on physiological loss of fruit weight in aonla (*Emblia officinalis* Gaertn) cultivars.

Treatment	Cultivars											
	NA-7			NA-10			Chakaiya			Wild Aonla		
	Fresh fruit weight (g)	Weight (g) after 35days	% weight loss	Fresh fruit weight (g)	Weight (g) after 35days	% weight loss	Fresh fruit weight (g)	Weight (g) after 35days	% weight loss	Fresh fruit weight (g)	Weight (g) after 35days	% weight loss
GA ₃ 100 mg.L ⁻¹	42.30	32.22	23.83	23.26	15.75	32.29	39.84	32.20	19.18	3.49	2.14	36.68
GA ₃ 200 mg.L ⁻¹	41.32	34.02	17.67	21.28	12.30	42.19	38.86	27.32	29.69	3.60	1.93	46.39
GA ₃ 300 mg.L ⁻¹	40.33	30.40	24.62	23.37	14.63	37.39	40.80	31.20	23.53	3.29	1.77	46.20
MH 100 mg.L ⁻¹	44.34	36.44	17.82	21.39	11.43	46.59	41.83	30.05	28.16	3.19	1.65	48.28
MH 200 mg.L ⁻¹	41.38	31.90	22.03	23.69	13.21	42.97	40.82	30.22	25.96	3.62	1.96	45.86
MH 300 mg.L ⁻¹	42.39	29.33	30.81	22.29	10.40	53.34	38.90	29.86	23.24	3.61	2.01	44.32
CaCl ₂ 10 g.L ⁻¹	44.39	33.84	23.77	21.58	15.60	27.72	37.78	28.73	23.82	3.79	2.13	43.80
CaCl ₂ 20 g.L ⁻¹	43.31	29.19	32.60	20.20	10.84	46.34	38.67	27.40	29.14	3.72	2.10	43.55
CaCl ₂ 30 g.L ⁻¹	1.50	25.49	38.57	24.22	15.50	36.00	39.76	28.10	29.32	3.49	1.77	49.28
Control	40.36	23.33	42.19	23.20	10.04	56.72	37.68	25.53	32.25	3.30	1.66	49.70
CD (P=0.05)	0.001	0.112	0.004	0.075	0.002	0.005	0.001	0.00	0.002	0.006	0.00	0.000

GA₃ 100 mg L⁻¹ treatment and maximum loss was noticed in control sets. Similar findings have also been reported by Gangwar *et al.* (2) and Dhillon and Kaur (1).

There was no pathological loss up to 14th day of storage in all the treatments of the four cultivars. Pathological loss was lowest in wild aonla (6.65%) followed by NA-7 (20.0%), NA-10 (25.21%) and

content was recorded minimum (29.14%) in cv. Chakaiya fruits treated with GA₃ 300 mgL⁻¹ while maximum decrease (96.43%) was observed in fruits of cultivar NA-7 treated with CaCl₂ 30 gL⁻¹ (Table 4). Ascorbic acid content decreased with the duration of storage in all the treatments. The minimum (11.46%) ascorbic acid decrease was recorded in fruits of Chakaiya cultivar treated with GA₃ 300 mg.L⁻¹ and

Table 2 : Effect of post harvest treatments on pathological fruit loss in aonla (*Emblca officinalis* Gaertn) cultivars.

Treatment	Cultivars											
	NA-7			NA-10			Chakaiya			Wild Aonla		
	No. of Fresh fruit taken	Infecte d fruits after 35 days	% fruit loss	No. of Fresh fruit taken	Infecte d fruits after 35 days	% fruit loss	No. of Fresh fruit taken	Infecte d fruits after 35 days	% fruit loss	No.of Fresh fruit taken	Infecte d fruits after 35 days	% fruit loss
GA ₃ 100 mg L ⁻¹	35	12.67	36.20	35	13.00	37.10	35	12.00	34.20	35	8.00	22.85
GA ₃ 200 mg L ⁻¹	35	13.00	37.10	35	16.00	46.65	35	14.00	40.00	35	8.00	22.85
GA ₃ 300 mg L ⁻¹	35	14.00	40.00	35	10.00	28.57	35	13.00	37.10	35	11.00	31.42
MH 100 mg L ⁻¹	35	14.00	40.00	35	15.00	43.80	35	12.00	34.20	35	11.00	31.42
MH 200 mg L ⁻¹	35	16.33	46.65	35	10.00	28.57	35	12.00	34.20	35	7.00	20.00
MH 300 mg L ⁻¹	35	12.00	34.20	35	17.33	49.51	35	10.00	28.57	35	5.00	14.28
CaCl ₂ 10 g L ⁻¹	35	12.00	34.20	35	13.00	37.10	35	10.00	28.57	35	7.00	20.00
CaCl ₂ 20 g L ⁻¹	35	11.00	31.42	35	10.33	29.51	35	11.00	31.42	35	2.66	7.60
CaCl ₂ 30 g L ⁻¹	35	7.00	20.00	35	9.00	25.71	35	10.00	28.57	35	2.33	6.65
Control	35	15.33	43.80	35	17.33	49.51	35	14.00	40.00	35	11.00	31.42
CD (P=0.05)	0.00	1.76	0.000	0.00	1.83	0.004	0.00	1.43	0.002	0.00	1.04	0.002

Table 3: Effect of post harvest treatments on TSS content of fruits in aonla (*Emblca officinalis* Gaertn) cultivars.

Treatment	Cultivars											
	NA-7			NA-10			Chakaiya			Wild Aonla		
	TSS of fresh fruits	TSS after 35days	% TSS increa se	TSS of fresh fruits	TSS after 35days	% TSS increa se	TSS of fresh fruits	TSS after 35days	% TSS increa se	TSS of fresh fruits	TSS after 35days	% TSS increa se
GA ₃ 100 mg.L ⁻¹	7.03	9.83	39.82	9.8	14.16	44.48	6.83	8.46	23.86	11.43	18.73	63.86
GA ₃ 200 mg.L ⁻¹	7.03	9.8	39.40	9.8	11.36	15.91	6.83	8.60	25.91	11.43	18.90	65.35
GA ₃ 300 mg.L ⁻¹	7.03	9.53	35.56	9.8	11.56	17.95	6.83	9.46	38.50	11.43	18.90	65.35
MH 100 mg.L ⁻¹	7.03	8.90	26.60	9.8	12.73	29.89	6.83	8.86	29.72	11.43	18.13	58.61
MH 200 mg.L ⁻¹	7.03	9.43	34.13	9.8	14.13	44.18	6.83	9.50	39.09	11.43	18.63	62.99
MH 300 mg.L ⁻¹	7.03	9.43	34.13	9.8	10.83	10.51	6.83	7.80	14.20	11.43	18.53	62.11
CaCl ₂ 10 g.L ⁻¹	7.03	9.46	34.56	9.8	11.00	12.24	6.83	10.76	57.54	11.43	18.90	65.35
CaCl ₂ 20 g.L ⁻¹	7.03	9.63	36.98	9.8	11.46	16.93	6.83	10.13	48.31	11.43	18.33	60.36
CaCl ₂ 30 g.L ⁻¹	7.03	9.53	35.60	9.8	12.20	24.48	6.83	8.46	23.86	11.43	18.63	63.99
Control	7.03	8.56	21.76	9.8	12.50	27.55	6.83	8.83	29.28	11.43	16.90	47.85
C D (P=0.05)	0.00	0.200	0.004	0.00	0.100	0.006	0.00	0.130	0.010	0.00	0.160	0.003

maximum (92.90%) decrease was noted in wild aonla treated as control on the 35 days of storage (Table 5).

In this study of post harvest treatments in fruits of aonla cultivars, significant variation in physiological loss in weight of fruits, pathological loss of fruits,

decrease in acid and vitamin C content of fruits during storage with chemical treatments were noticed. The variation in these characters between cultivars might be due to differences in composition and morphology of fruits of cultivars. The minimum loss may be due to which it controlled the disintegration of mitochondria,

Table 4: Effect of post harvest treatments on malic acid content of fruits in aonla (*Emblica officinalis* Gaertn) cultivars.

Treatment	Cultivars											
	NA-7			NA-10			Chakaiya			Wild Aonla		
	Fresh fruits	After 35 days	% decrease	Fresh fruits	After 35 days	% decrease	Fresh fruits	After 35 days	% decrease	Fresh fruits	After 35 days	% decrease
GA ₃ 100 mg L ⁻¹	0.140	0.046	67.14	0.156	0.060	61.54	0.171	0.067	60.82	0.344	0.097	71.80
GA ₃ 200 mg L ⁻¹	0.140	0.053	62.14	0.156	0.044	71.79	0.171	0.118	30.99	0.344	0.102	70.35
GA ₃ 300 mg L ⁻¹	0.140	0.053	62.14	0.156	0.067	57.05	0.171	0.154	29.14	0.344	0.102	70.35
MH 100 mg L ⁻¹	0.140	0.048	65.71	0.156	0.044	71.79	0.171	0.067	60.82	0.344	0.009	74.13
MH 200 mg L ⁻¹	0.140	0.064	54.29	0.156	0.011	92.95	0.171	0.060	64.91	0.344	0.080	76.74
MH 300 mg L ⁻¹	0.140	0.005	96.43	0.156	0.019	87.82	0.171	0.078	54.38	0.344	0.089	74.13
CaCl ₂ 10 g L ⁻¹	0.140	0.016	88.57	0.156	0.082	47.44	0.171	0.053	69.00	0.344	0.089	74.13
CaCl ₂ 20 g L ⁻¹	0.140	0.095	32.14	0.156	0.127	18.60	0.171	0.051	70.17	0.344	0.080	76.74
CaCl ₂ 30 g L ⁻¹	0.140	0.084	40.00	0.156	0.117	25.00	0.171	0.058	66.08	0.344	0.076	77.91
Control	0.140	0.067	52.14	0.156	0.055	64.74	0.171	0.079	53.80	0.344	0.062	81.98
CD (P=0.05)	0.00	0.060	0.097	0.00	0.016	0.013	0.00	0.012	0.000	0.00	0.019	0.000

endoplasmic reticulum and cytoplasmic membranes and respiration due to stomata closure (Yadav and Singh,13). Khader *et al.* (4) also reported that post-harvest treatment with gibberellic acid at the rate of 100 or 200 mg L⁻¹ significantly delayed ripening of mango fruits cultivar 'Mallika'. Similarly, Hassan *et al.* (3) observed that treatment of CaCl₂ (4%) + HDPE significantly reduced physiological weight loss, change

in diameter and change in specific gravity of aonla fruits during storage as compared to other treatments. Post harvest treatments of fruits with chemicals prolonged shelf life as well as quality of guava fruits (Nishad *et al.*, 10) and the lowest spoilage incidence in fruits and highest total soluble solids content in fruits (Nigam and Ganesh, 9). Reduced decay loss might be due to its antiseptic nature or reduction of moisture in fruits. The

Table 5 : Effect of post harvest treatments on ascorbic acid content of fruits in aonla (*Emblica officinalis* Gaertn) cultivars

Treatment	Cultivars											
	NA-7			NA-10			Chakaiya			Wild aonla		
	Fresh fruit	After 35days	% decrease	Fresh fruit	After 35days	% decrease	Fresh fruit	After 35days	% decrease	Fresh fruit	After 35days	% decrease
GA ₃ 100 mg L ⁻¹	226.40	82.10	63.73	331.20	111.47	66.34	187.20	114.03	39.08	537.60	76.27	85.81
GA ₃ 200 mg L ⁻¹	226.40	90.57	60.00	331.20	115.13	65.23	187.20	147.40	21.26	537.60	81.40	84.85
GA ₃ 300 mg L ⁻¹	226.40	136.77	39.59	331.20	154.37	53.39	187.20	165.73	11.46	537.60	98.27	81.72
MH 100 mg L ⁻¹	226.40	86.17	61.94	331.20	86.90	73.76	187.20	93.50	50.05	537.60	77.73	85.54
MH 200 mg L ⁻¹	226.40	96.07	57.57	331.20	105.97	68.00	187.20	131.63	29.68	537.60	77.73	85.54
MH 300 mg L ⁻¹	226.40	103.77	54.16	331.20	106.33	67.89	187.20	138.60	25.96	537.60	73.33	86.35
CaCl ₂ 10 g L ⁻¹	226.40	95.33	57.89	331.20	83.60	74.75	187.20	118.43	36.73	537.60	79.93	85.13
CaCl ₂ 20 g L ⁻¹	226.40	101.93	54.97	331.20	100.47	69.66	187.20	97.17	48.09	537.60	76.27	85.81
CaCl ₂ 30 g L ⁻¹	226.40	105.97	53.19	331.20	110.73	66.56	187.20	91.67	51.03	537.60	55.73	89.63
Control	226.40	80.67	64.37	331.20	56.83	82.84	187.20	68.77	63.26	537.60	38.13	92.91
CD (P=0.05)	0.00	4.960	0.000	0.00	4.020	0.002	0.00	6.210	0.098	0.00	9.600	0.313

rapid decrease in acidity under prolonged storage might be due to rapid utilization of organic acid during respiration as reported by Nath *et al.* (8). The maximum retention of vitamin C may be due to the lowering of respiration rate and slow oxidation process. They also reported that ascorbic acid was higher in GA₃ treatment as compared to other treatments., GA₃ treatment retarded the total loss in weight, chlorophyll and ascorbic acid content, and reduced amylase and peroxidase activity during ripening Khader *et al.*, 4) Postharvest calcium treatments tend to reduce the incidence of disorders, lower respiration rates and aid in firmness retention but can be injurious to the skin of some cultivars Meheriuk and Sholberg, 7). Pilai *et al.* (11) concluded that post harvest chemical treatment with GA₃, CaCl₂ and SA has the potential to control decaying incidence, prolong the storage life and preserve valuable attributes of post harvest tomato, presumably because of its effect on inhibition of ripening and senescence processes.

The variation in cultivars for post harvest quality changes with different chemicals is because of the variation in fruit morphology of cultivars. .

CONCLUSION

From the results of this study it can be concluded that shelf life of aonla goes on decreasing with the prolong days of storage. GA₃ (300 mg L⁻¹) treatment was found to be effective in retaining the quality of aonla fruits while CaCl₂ at 30 g L⁻¹ was found to be effective in minimising the pathological loss of fruits in aonlal cultivars studied.

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EFFECT OF N, P AND K ON GROWTH, BULB YIELD AND NUTRIENT CONTENT IN RATOON SPIDER LILY (*Hymenocallis littoralis* L.) CV. LOCAL

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ABSTRACT: A multifactor experiment on ratoon spider lily cv. Local was conducted at Instructional Farm of Horticulture Department, Junagadh Agricultural University during 2011-2012. All the growth parameters were significantly influenced due to different levels of nitrogen. Application of nitrogen @ 400Kg N ha⁻¹ with three equal split doses recorded significantly the highest plant height, number of leaves per plant, leaf area, leaf length, diameter and weight of single bulb, number of bulbs per plant, bulb yield ha⁻¹, N content in leaves and bulbs. Phosphorus also played a significant role in improving growth parameters at higher level except, number of leaves per plant, bulb yield, P content in leaves and bulb. Potassium doses were significantly increased the P content in leaves and bulb. The optimum vegetative growth and bulb yield were obtained with combined application of 400Kg N ha⁻¹ and 200 Kg P₂O₅ ha⁻¹.

Keywords : Spider lily, ratoon, vegetative growth, bulb, NPK, nutrient uptake.

Spider lily (*Hymenocallis littoralis* L.) is an important bulbous flowering ornamental plant, native to South America, belongs to the family Amaryllidaceae. The spider lily is perennial bulbous flower crop and gives economic production up to 7-10 years. The flowers of spider lily are largely used in garland and making *Gajras*, *mandap* and various flower decorations. Spider lily is now emerging as an important commercial flower crop in Gujarat and Maharashtra. The total area under lily cultivation in Gujarat is about 3209 hectare with production of 127779 bundles during 2010-11. Saurashtra have 79ha area under cultivation of spider lily with production of 400 lakh bundles (Anon, 1). The application of nitrogen enhanced most of growth, flowering and yield of flowers and bulb in spider lily (Ghule *et al.*, 9; Koladiya and Dhaduk, 14). Improper nutrition produces nutrient imbalance in plants which is major obstacle for flower yield of many flowering plants. The nutrient supply should be adjusted to the specific requirements of plant during various stages of growth to achieve the maximum production (Mengel, 16). Nutrient status of the plants can be a pointer to the response of plant to the fertilization and internal content of the nutrients determines the fertilizer requirements. The balanced application of macronutrients plays an important role on growth, flowering, corm and cormel production in gladiolus (Bhattacharjee, 3; Borrelli, 4; Deswal *et al.*, 6; Shah *et al.*, 22; Sindhu and Arora, 23). A very little research work has been done for standardization of agro-techniques like planting, manuring, irrigation,

spacing, nutrition, harvesting and post-harvest handling etc. for spider lily. The optimum supply of plant nutrients is an important factor in vegetative growth and bulb production of ratoon crop of spider lily. Therefore, present study was made to standardize NPK doses for ratoon crop of spider lily.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The experiment was laid out in FRBD with three replications and twenty four treatment combinations which were carried out at Horticulture Instructional Farm, College of Agriculture, Junagadh Agriculture University, Junagadh during the year 2011-12. The experimental site was situated between 21°50' N latitude and 70°50' E longitude at an altitude of 60 m above mean sea level. The soil of experimental plot was clayey in texture, calcareous in nature and slightly alkaline in reaction. The soil was moderate in organic carbon, low in available N and P₂O₅ and medium in available K₂O. The treatments consisted of four levels of nitrogen (0, 200, 300 and 400 kg ha⁻¹), three levels of phosphorus (0, 100 and 200 kg ha⁻¹) and two levels of potash (0 and 100 kg ha⁻¹). Nitrogen in the form of Urea was applied with three equal doses (as basal, and two months and three months after cutting) and full quantity of phosphorus as Single Super Phosphate and potash in form of Muriate of Potash as basal application. FYM 10 ha⁻¹ was applied uniformly before first irrigation. The recommended cultural practices were carried out during this investigation. The leaves and bulb were washed firstly in running tap water then with 0.1 N HCl and finally in distilled water. After drying,

perusal of data in Table 1 showed that bulb diameter was increased with increasing levels of nitrogen and it was significantly maximum (5.66 cm) with application of nitrogen at 400kg N ha⁻¹ (N₃) which was followed by N₂ and N₁. The shortest diameter (4.27cm) was registered under zero kg N ha⁻¹ (N₀). Similarly, higher dose of nitrogen (400kg N ha⁻¹) significantly improved weight of a bulb (118.32g) but it was at par with N₁ (300kg N ha⁻¹). The lowest average weight of single bulb (96.25g) was recorded at zero kg N ha⁻¹ (N₀). The bulb yield per hectare was significantly increased with addition of nitrogen from 0 to 400 kg ha⁻¹. Nitrogen @ 400kg ha⁻¹ (N₃) recorded significantly maximum bulb yield (43.16 t ha⁻¹) as compared to 300kg N ha⁻¹ and 200kg N ha⁻¹. The lowest bulb yield of 29.25 t ha⁻¹ was recorded with N₀. This might be due to better availability of nutrients to plant that ultimately leads to quite better vegetative growth of plant which results more accumulation of food in bulbs. The results are closely agreed with the reports of Dahiya *et al.* (5) and Rathore and Singh (21) in tuberose, and Patel *et al.* (19) in gladiolus. Similarly, Devi and Singh (7) also reported that the increased levels of nitrogen produced maximum diameter bulbs.

Addition of nitrogen @ 400kg ha⁻¹ resulted in significantly highest nitrogen content (1.95%) in leaves but it was at par with 300kg N ha⁻¹ (N₂). The lowest nitrogen content (1.69%) in leaves was registered with zero kg N ha⁻¹ (N₀) which was at par with N₁. The nitrogen content of bulb increased significantly at harvest and that too increasing magnitude as nitrogen application rates increased from N₀ to N₃. The highest nitrogen content (1.46 per cent) in bulb was observed with addition of 400 kg N ha⁻¹ (N₃) which was at par with 300 kg N ha⁻¹ (N₂), while the lowest nitrogen content (1.21 per cent) of bulb was noted under N₀ (Table 2). These results are in the accordance with findings of Jana *et al.* (11) in tuberose. Bankar and Mukhopadhyay (2) also reported increased nitrogen content in leaf of tuberose with higher doses of nitrogen.

Effect of Phosphorus

The data summarized in Table 1 showed that phosphorus levels had significantly increased the plant height at flowering. The application of phosphorus @ 200kg P₂O₅ ha⁻¹ (P₂) resulted in significantly the highest plant height (97.58cm) being at par with P₁ (100kg ha⁻¹). Whereas, the lowest plant height

(90.91cm) was measured at zero level of phosphorus. Plant height was also significantly increased with various phosphorus levels at last picking. Results are in accordance with Ghule *et al.* (9) in spider lily and Bankar and Mukhopadhyay (2) in tuberose. The leaf length was significantly maximum (92.22 cm) with higher level of phosphorus (200 kg P₂O₅ ha⁻¹) but it was at par with 100kg P₂O₅ ha⁻¹. The minimum length of leaf was recorded at zero kg P₂O₅ ha⁻¹ (P₀) confirming to reports of Patel *et al.* (19). Similarly, application of phosphorus at 200 kg P₂O₅ ha⁻¹ (P₂) resulted in maximum leaf area (367.11 cm²) which was at par with P₁ level of phosphorus, which supports to the findings of Gangwar *et al.* (8). The lowest leaf area (325.85 cm²) was found with P₀ (control).

The phosphorus fertilization @ 200kg P₂O₅ ha⁻¹ (P₂) resulted significantly the highest number of bulbs per plant (9.12) being at par with P₁. Significantly lowest number of bulbs/plant (8.23) were noted with zero kg P₂O₅ ha⁻¹ (P₀). The application of phosphorus @ 200kg P₂O₅ ha⁻¹ (P₂) produced significantly the largest sizes bulbs having 5.24 cm diameter and 117.42g weight, but it maximum diameter (5.24cm) and weight (117.42 g) being at par with P₁ level of phosphorus. The lowest diameter (4.56cm) and weight of single bulb (97.01g) were noted under P₀. The highest level of phosphorus *i.e.*, 200 kg P₂O₅ ha⁻¹ resulted in significantly maximum bulb yield (38.02 t ha⁻¹) being at par with 100kg P₂O₅ ha⁻¹ (P₁). The minimum yield of bulbs (33.92 t/ha) was observed under treatment of zero kg P₂O₅ ha⁻¹ (P₀). The results are in accordance with Gangwar *et al.* (8).

Phosphorus is essential for plant growth by affecting cell division, root growth and lengthening. It is an important constituent of ADP, ATP, nucleoproteins, purines, pyrimidine and co-enzymes etc. It is also one of structural component of cell membrane, chloroplast and mitochondria which resulted significantly the largest plant height, length and width of leaf, chlorophyll content at full bloom stage, leaf area, fresh and dry weight of bulbs.

Nitrogen and phosphorus content of leaves was significantly affected due to various phosphorus levels. It was observed that nitrogen and phosphorus content of leaves was increased with increasing phosphorus levels. Addition of phosphorus @ 200kg ha⁻¹ resulted in significantly the highest nitrogen and phosphorus content (1.92 and 0.474 per cent, respectively) and it

Table 2: Effect of NPK on nutrient content in leaves and bulbs of ratoon spider lily.

Treatments	Content in leaves (%)			Content in bulb (%)		
	Nitrogen	Phosphorus	Potash	Nitrogen	Phosphorus	Potash
Nitrogen (Kg ha⁻¹)						
N ₀ -0	1.691	0.426	1.46	1.21	0.286	7.28
N ₁ -200	1.778	0.432	1.48	1.37	0.316	7.09
N ₂ -300	1.888	0.439	1.51	1.38	0.320	6.96
N ₃ -400	1.955	0.465	1.52	1.46	0.326	6.71
C. D. P=0.05)	0.12	NS	NS	0.098	NS	NS
Phosphorus (Kg ha⁻¹)						
P ₀ -0	1.75	0.399	1.49	1.28	0.283	6.79
P ₁ -100	1.80	0.449	1.52	1.35	0.315	6.93
P ₂ -200	1.92	0.474	1.53	1.44	0.339	7.34
C. D. (P=0.05)	0.11	0.026	NS	0.085	0.028	0.42
Potash (Kg ha⁻¹)						
K ₀ -0	1.86	0.436	1.40	1.32	0.308	6.58
K ₁ -100	1.79	0.445	1.59	1.39	0.316	7.44
C. D. (P=0.05)	NS	NS	0.072	NS	NS	0.34
C. V. %	11.39	10.01	10.13	10.79	15.53	10.34
Interaction						
N × P	NS	NS	NS	Sig.	NS	NS
N × K	NS	NS	NS	NS	NS	NS
P × K	NS	NS	NS	NS	NS	Sig.
N × P × K	NS	NS	NS	NS	NS	NS

was found at par with 100kg P₂O₅ ha⁻¹ (P₁) in case of phosphorus content in leaves. Whereas, the lowest nitrogen and phosphorus (1.75 and 0.399 per cent) content of leaves was analyzed under P₀ level and it was at par with P₁ in case of nitrogen content of leaves. The nitrogen, phosphorus and potassium content of bulbs were significantly affected due to various phosphorus levels and it was increased with increasing phosphorus levels as compared with P₀ and P₁ level.

The significantly highest N, P and K contents of bulbs (1.44, 0.339 and 7.34 per cent, respectively) were found with 200kg P₂O₅ ha⁻¹ (P₂) level of phosphorus and it was at par with P₁ level with respect to phosphorus and potassium content of bulb. While, the lowest N, P and K content of bulbs (1.28, 0.283 and 6.79 per cent, respectively) were noted with zero kg P₂O₅ ha⁻¹ (P₀) and found at par with P₁ in case of nitrogen content. These findings are closely agreement with Polara *et al.* (20) in tuberose.

Effect of Potash

The vegetative growth and bulb yield parameters as well as N and P content were remained non significant with increased dose of potash. The percent potassium content in leaves (1.59 per cent) and bulb

(7.44 per cent) were significantly increased with increasing dose of potash. These results are in line with findings of Karetha (13) in gaillardia.

Interaction effect of N × P

The data presented in Table 3 showed that significantly the maximum leaf area of 408.75 cm² was found at combination N₃P₁ (400kg N ha⁻¹ + 100kg P₂O₅ ha⁻¹) and it was at par with N₃P₂ (400kg N ha⁻¹ + 200kg P₂O₅ ha⁻¹). The significantly lowest leaf area was (307.93 cm²) was recorded with N₀P₀ combination which was at par with combinations N₁P₀, N₂P₀, N₃P₀ and N₀P₁. Interactions between nutrients occur when the supply of one nutrient affects the absorption, distribution or functions of another nutrient. Thus, depending upon nutrients supply, interactions between nutrients can either induce deficiencies or toxicities and can modify the growth response. The appraisal data shown in Table 3 revealed that combined application of N₂ × P₂ produced the heaviest bulb (123.58g) which was at par with N₃P₁, N₃P₂, N₃P₀, N₁P₁ and N₀P₂. Significantly the lowest weight of single bulb (84.03g) was registered with control which remained at par with N₁P₀, N₂P₀ and N₀P₁. Significantly the highest bulb yield (45.84 t ha⁻¹) was observed in N₃P₂ combination

Table 3: Interaction effects of nitrogen and phosphorus (N x P) on leaf area and weight of bulbs of ratoon spider lily.

Nitrogen (Kg ha ⁻¹)	Phosphorus (Kg ha ⁻¹)					
	Leaf Area (cm ²)			Leaf Area (cm ²)		
	P ₀ - 0	P ₁ - 100	P ₂ - 200	P ₀ - 0	P ₁ - 100	P ₂ - 200
N ₀ -0	307.93	316.75	349.22	84.03	97.61	107.16
N ₁ -200	322.93	340.25	353.60	86.17	118.33	116.57
N ₂ -300	336.45	353.82	360.91	94.75	114.96	123.58
N ₃ -400	336.10	408.75	404.73	109.46	123.15	122.35
C.D. (P=0.05)	29.28			18.45		

Table 4: Interaction effects of nitrogen and phosphorus (N x P) on bulb yield and nitrogen content in bulbs in ratoon spider lily.

Nitrogen (Kg ha ⁻¹)	Phosphorus (Kg ha ⁻¹)					
	Bulb Yield (t/ha)			Nitrogen Content in Bulb (%)		
	P ₀ - 0	P ₁ - 100	P ₂ - 200	P ₀ - 0	P ₁ - 100	P ₂ - 200
N ₀ -0	27.01	28.31	32.44	1.11	1.21	1.31
N ₁ -200	29.53	40.12	33.52	1.39	1.45	1.28
N ₂ -300	37.83	38.22	40.28	1.35	1.32	1.47
N ₃ -400	41.31	42.33	45.84	1.27	1.42	1.71
C.D. (P=0.05)	4.71			0.17		

which was at par with treatment combination of N₃P₁ and N₃P₀ (Table 4). The treatment combination of N₀P₀ (control) recorded the lowest bulb yield (27.01 t ha⁻¹) which was at par with treatment combination N₀P₁ and N₁P₀ (Table 4).

It is apparent from Table 4 that the application of nitrogen at 400 kg in combination with 200kg P₂O₅ ha⁻¹ (N₃P₂) recorded significantly highest nitrogen content (1.71 per cent) in bulb which was followed by N₂P₂ and N₂P₁. Significantly the lowest nitrogen content (1.11 per

cent) was observed in treatment combination N₀P₀ which was at par with by N₀P₁ and N₁P₂.

Interaction effect of P × K

A perusal of Table 5 revealed that the interaction between levels of phosphorus and potash (P × K) was found significant on potash content in bulb after harvest. The treatment combination of P₂K₁ registered the significantly highest potassium content (8.09 per cent) in bulb followed by P₀K₁. Significantly the lowest potassium content (6.33 per cent) was noted in control (P₀K₀) which was at par with treatment combination P₁K₀ and P₂K₀.

It may be concluded that the higher doses of nitrogen and phosphorus and their interactions increased plant growth, bulb production, and N and P contents in leaves and bulbs of ratoon spider lily cv. Local. The higher levels of nitrogen and phosphorus are beneficial to increase economical age of ratoon spider lily.

Table 5: Interaction effects of nitrogen and phosphorus (N x P) on bulb yield and nitrogen content in bulbs in ratoon spider lily.

Phosphorus (Kg ha ⁻¹)	Potash (Kg ha ⁻¹)	
	K ₀ -0	K ₁ -100
P ₀ -0	6.33	7.25
P ₁ -100	6.81	6.99
P ₂ -200	6.58	8.09
C.D. (P=0.05)	0.59	

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EXPLORATION OF TURMERIC (*Curcuma longa* L.) CULTIVATION : A REVIEW

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ABSTRACT : *Curcuma longa* L is an important sacred and spice crop of Asia, used in several culinary purposes and also for treatment of several diseases. It is cultivated for its rhizomes for extraction of curcumin forming the principal source of drugs and colouring principle. In India, Andhra Pradesh, Karnataka, Tamil Nadu are the major state producing turmeric. There is a need to standardize the production technology which may help to improve the yield, quality so as to extend the farmers' hand of reliability so that they can get high net returns per unit area. The present review is focusing on production practices of *Curcuma longa* L.

Key words : *Curcuma longa*, turmeric, herbal medicine, production.

Turmeric (*Curcuma longa* L.) is an important, sacred and ancient spice of India. It is a major rhizomatous spice produced and exported from India. Turmeric is a herbaceous perennial plant, native to tropical South-East Asia, belonging to the family Zingiberaceae, under the order Scitaminae. It is cultivated for its underground rhizomes which is used as spice and condiment, dye stuff and in cosmetic and drug industry, particularly in the preparation of anti-cancerous medicines. It forms an important adjuvant in Indian culinary as it imparts colour and aromatic flavour to various dishes. Turmeric is widely used as a condiment in the preparation of pickles and curries and as a colouring agent in textile, food and confectionary industries. It is also used as herbal medicine 'Amraharidra', which gives a cooling, aromatic effect and promotes digestion (Srivastava *et al.*, 25). Turmeric has long been used in India for the treatment of sprains and inflammatory conditions. The turmeric rhizomes contain 'curcumin' which is responsible for colouring.

India is the world's largest producer and exporter of turmeric and it produces nearly 50 per cent of global turmeric production. It is grown in an area of 1.92 lakh hectares with an average production of 8.93 lakh MT (Anon., 1) with an average production of 156.31q/ha (Deshmukh *et al.*, 6). It is cultivated extensively in tropical regions of the world, from India to Indo-China, the East Indies and parts of China. It is also cultivated in Iran, Sri Lanka, China, Pakistan, East Indies, Indonesia, Libya, Nigeria, Sudan, Persia, Taiwan, Jamaica, and Peru. In India, it is mainly grown in the states of Andhra Pradesh, Orissa, Tamil Nadu, Assam, Maharashtra, Karnataka, Kerala and North-Eastern region. In Karnataka, it is largely cultivated in Chamarajnagar, Belagavi, Mysore, Mandya, Bidar,

Kodagu, and Chikamagalore districts (Lokesh and Chandrakanth, 13).

In India, Andhra Pradesh, Karnataka, Tamil Nadu are the major state producing turmeric. There is a need to standardize the production technology which may help to improve the yield, quality so as to extend the farmers a hand of reliability so that they can get high net returns per unit area. The present review is focused on production practices of *Curcuma longa* L. so as to promote the production of the crop in non-traditional areas. In this regard the studies on different aspects of *Curcuma longa* L. are reviewed and presented under different headings.

Fig. 1: Plant and plant parts of turmeric.

Genotypic evaluation studies

Chaudhary *et al.* (5) evaluated five varieties of turmeric viz. Krishna, Suvarna, Rajendra Sonia, Suguna and Sudarshana and revealed that the variety Krishna recorded highest fresh (405.60 q/ha) and cured rhizome (65.80 q/ha) yield followed by Rajendra Sonia and Suvarna, while in curing percentage, Suvarna (20.68%) was found to be superior followed by Rajendra Sonia and Krishna. With regard to rhizome numbers and their size, Krishna produced more rhizomes (11.48), maximum length (10.20 cm) and girth (2.45 cm) followed by Rajendra Sonia. The varieties Suvarna, Rajendra Sonia, Suguna and Sudarshan were found to be early duration types (190 to 210 days) compared to Krishna, which matured relatively late (255 days). Krishna recorded significantly highest shoot dry weight (19.54 g) followed by Rajendra Sonia (17.96 g) at maturity.

Jilani *et al.* (8) conducted experiments at three different localities of Dera Ismail Khan region of Pakistan to evaluate the performance of turmeric cultivars including Duggirala, Zedory and Krishna. The results showed the supremacy of Krishna over the other two cultivars in all the three localities, as Krishna took significantly least number of days (44.67, 46.00 and 48.33) to sprouting, maximum plant height (78.54, 73.64 and 75.43 cm), leaves per plant (13.74, 12.97 and 13.73), leaf width (8.733, 7.30 and 7.80 cm), maximum finger per plant (31.43, 54.44 & 37.00) in all the three localities.

In an evaluation of seven turmeric (*Curcuma longa*) varieties under irrigated condition for two crop seasons Chaturvedi *et al.* (4) found that varieties differed in their production potential and growth characters (plant height, number of tiller per plant, leaves per tiller, leaf length and leaf breadth). Among varieties tested, Barua Sagar resulted in maximum production of fresh rhizome 33.50 t/ha (2006-07) and 30.25 t/ha (2007-08) and it was at par with the production of Azad Haldi-1 (32.60 t/ha and 29.85 t/ha) during 2006-07, 2007-08, respectively. These two varieties namely Barua Sagar and Azad Haldi-1 were significantly superior to the varieties during all the seasons and are suitable for general cultivation in the area of central Uttar Pradesh.

Rao *et al.* (18) studied the genetic divergence in fifty four turmeric (*Curcuma longa*) cultivars at Jagtial (Andhra Pradesh) by subjecting D_2 statistics to assess the genetic diversity available in the cultivars. The D^2 analysis showed wide diversity among the cultivars and they were grouped into six clusters. Inter-cluster

distance values also showed wide genetic divergence among the cultivars. Based on cluster-mean values, the cultivars PTS-38 and Duggirala in cluster I (high cured yield), PCT-5 and PCT-8 in cluster III (high curcumin, essential oil and oleoresin contents) and PCT-13, PCT-14 and PCT-10 in cluster IV (short duration, medium yield with good curcumin content).

In-vitro studies

Gomathy *et al.* (7) conducted an experiment for the standardization of *in vitro* culture technique for the mass propagation of *Curcuma longa* L., Scooped rhizomatous buds were used as explants and they were cultured on MS medium supplemented with different concentrations of BAP, Kn and IAA both in individual and in combined form for shoot inductions and the best results were obtained from MS medium supplemented with BAP+IAA at the concentration of 2.0mg/l and 0.5mg/l, respectively. Best root formation of *in vitro* developed shoots could be achieved on half strength MS medium supplemented with IBA at concentration 1.0mg/l. The *in vitro* developed plantlets were transferred to pot and they were grown in greenhouse for hardening and finally they were planted in the open field. Around 90% of plants were successfully established in natural field condition.

Archana *et al.* (2) conducted an experiment to develop an efficient protocol for the development of micro rhizome and mini rhizome technology in high yielding variety of turmeric, Alleppey Supreme, using two media combinations and four types of culture vessels. Cultures in all media showed prominent basal bulging within one month of growth as an indication of micro rhizome induction irrespective of vessels used. In solid medium shoot number ranged from 1.0 to 5.55 ± 0.71 and in liquid medium it ranged from 3.67 ± 1.15 to 5.5 ± 2.12 . In both the medium, cultures grown in planton vessel showed higher number of shoots. Length of shoot did not exhibit any prominent difference in any of the media and vessel except for cultures grown in 350 ml bottle (B1) in solid medium where maximum shoot length (11.6 ± 0.57) was observed. Yield was nearly three times higher in minirhizome seed material (526.67 ± 9.5) compared to the conventional seed rhizome (183.0 ± 8.30).

A high frequency *in vitro* plantlet regeneration method was developed for *Curcuma longa* L. (cv. Ranga) using fresh sprouting rhizome bud on semisolid culture media (Kambaska *et al.*, 10). The explants were cultured on Murashige and Skoog's (MS) medium supplemented with different concentration and combinations of BAP (6-Benzyl-amino-purine) and

NAA(α - Naphthalene acetic acid) for shoot and root induction. Explants cultured on MS basal medium supplemented with 2.0mg/l BAP+0.5gm/l NAA showed highest rate of shoot multiplication. *In vitro* shoots were rooted on to the half-strength MS basal media supplemented with 2.0 mg/l NAA and rooting was better. Rooted shoots were transplanted in the green house for hardening and their survival rate was 95% in the field condition.

Propagation studies

Singh *et al.* (24) used different planting materials of turmeric *i.e.*, mother rhizome, primary finger, secondary finger and tertiary fingers and observed data on plant growth, yield and yield contributing characters along with economics of turmeric cv. Erode. The highest number of fingers per plant (13.64), finger length (9.06 cm), finger weight (36.14g) and yield (389.47g/plant and 235.41 q/ha) were obtained by use of the mother rhizome.

In a study on the different rhizome sizes used for propagation of the turmeric, Meenakshi *et al.* (17) found that mother rhizomes recorded maximum numbers of tillers, number of leaves and plant height as compared to fingers used for propagation. Planting of mother rhizomes and fingers brought about significant variations with regard to number of tillers per plant at 150 DAP, number of leaves and plant height at 120 DAP. Leaf area was found to differ significantly both at 120 and 150 DAP, recording maximum at 150 DAP in all the cases and total dry matter production per plant differed significantly due to planting material. In all the cases mother rhizome was found to be superior than finger rhizomes. Like this, Kumar and Gill (12) also found that use of mother rhizome as planting material resulted in better emergence (86.6% and 83.1%), taller plants (49.6 and 50.0 cm) with more number of leaves and leaf area index (4.4 and 3.8), more tillers/ plant (2.7 and 3.1), higher number (17.09 and 23.89) and weight (136.96 and 227.66 g) of total rhizomes plant⁻¹ as compared to use of primary and secondary fingers as planting material. Planting of mother rhizomes produced highest fresh (207.7q/ha), dry (46.0q/ha) and processed (44.1 q/ha) turmeric yield and it decreased significantly with decrease in seed size.

Nutritional studies

Application of different levels of S and Mg did not have any significant effect on the vegetative growth of the turmeric plants. Though maximum number of mother rhizomes and primary fingers, as well as highest length of primary fingers, was noted at 44 kg/ha of S and 22 kg Mg/ha (Bose *et al.*, 3). There was a

significant increase in the weight of the mother rhizome at the above dose, which then declined with further increases in S and Mg levels. Significant variation in weight of primary fingers was observed due to S and Mg applications, also peaking with 44 kg S/ha in this study at application rates of more than 22 kg/ha of Mg, which reduced K uptake and caused losses in yield.

Kulpapangkorn and Mai-leang (11) studied the effect of plant nutrients on turmeric production with 5 treatments namely: 1) untreated check, 2) farm manure at 12 kg N/rai 3) farm manure at 12 kg N/rai plus chemical fertilizer at 5-5-5 (N-N-P₂O₅-K₂O) kg/rai, 4) farm manure at 12 kg N/rai plus chemical fertilizer at 10-5-5 (N-P₂O₅-K₂O) kg/rai and, 5) chemical fertilizer at 10-5-5 (N-P₂O₅-K₂O) kg/rai. The results showed that effect of plant nutrition to yield was significant. Untreated check (1,242 kg/rai) provided lowest yield, while as, fertilizer using provided higher yield (2260.22 kg/rai). The combination of farm manure and chemical fertilizer trended to have higher yield than the single treatment. The curcuminoids and volatile oil contained in turmeric were more than 5% curcuminoids and 6% volatile oil, which were met to standard level and no significantly different in amounts of active constituents on any treatment.

Sadanandan and Hamza (21) conducted experiment on the response of four varieties of turmeric viz. Suvarna, Suguna, Sudarshana and Alleppey with four levels of NPK fertilizers and two levels of micro nutrients, under rainfed conditions. The variety Alleppey followed by Sudarshana and Suguna were superior with regard to yield of rhizome, curcumin recovery and economics and these were significantly increased due to application of NPK and micronutrients. NPK @ 60, 50, 120 kg ha⁻¹ with micronutrient was optimum for the varieties Suvarna, Suguna and Alleppey, whereas 50, 40, 100 kg ha⁻¹ with micronutrients was optimum for Sudarshana.

Among different treatment combinations of organic manures and microbial inoculants tried, the most effective treatment was vermicompost + *Azospirillum sp.* + *Glomus sp.* (28.94 t ha⁻¹) followed by compost + *Azospirillum sp.* + *Glomus sp.* (26.93 t ha⁻¹) as compared to recommended inorganic NPK (Roy and Hore, 20). Maximum root colonisation (74%) with microbial inoculants at 180 days after planting was observed with vermicompost + *Azospirillum sp.* + *Glomus sp.* Maximum bacterial population (105.25 x 10⁵ CFU g⁻¹ soil) at harvest was noticed in compost + *Azospirillum sp.* + *Glomus sp.*, as compared to lowest population with recommended NPK (56.35 x 10⁵ CFU

g^{-1} soil). By integration of bio-fertilizers and inorganic fertilizers, Singh *et al.* (23) found that combined application of NPK (180:90:90 kg/ha) + *Azotobacter chroococcum* (2.5 kg/ha) + *Pseudomonas fluorescence* (2.5 kg/ha) significantly increased yield and yield attributes of turmeric.

Turmeric showed better response to the application of organic manures (Kamal and Yousuf, 9). Plants feeded with neem cake application had the taller plant (79.30 cm), maximum number of tillers per height ant (5.40), leaf number (5.40), leaf area (44.09) leaf area index (0.429), fresh weight of haulm (190.05g), fresh weight of root (49.13 g), fresh weight of rhizome per plant (256.21 g) and dry weight of haulm (15.21g), dry weight of root (7.32 g), dry weight of rhizome per plant (40.35 g), total dry matter yield ($6.85 t ha^{-1}$) than those received other types of manures. Moreover, yield attributes such as number of mother rhizomes plant⁻¹ (1.75), more number of primary rhizomes per plant⁻¹ (5.19), secondary rhizomes per plant (18.03) and tertiary rhizomes per plant (7.69) were also highly accelerated by neem cake application. Similarly, the same treatment expressed the best in terms of size of mother rhizome (7.69 cm), primary rhizome (21.86 cm) and secondary rhizomes (7.05 cm). All these parameters in cumulative contributed to produce the highest estimated fresh rhizomes yield & cured rhizomes yield ($29.48 t ha^{-1}$, $5.59 t ha^{-1}$ respectively). The highest curing percentage (20.28) was observed in treatment having mustard cake @ 2.0 t/ha.

Quality assessment

Lokhande *et al.* (14) carried out an investigation on the effect of curing and drying methods on the recovery, curcumin content and essential oil content in different turmeric cultivars. The Krishna cultivars were best among the three cultivars on the basis of physico-chemical analysis whereas, Salem and Tekurpeta had higher values for colour. The fingers cured with improved method loose moisture at faster rate than uncured and cured with traditional method. The fingers of Salem cultivar cured with improved method followed by shade-net drying had got higher recovery. The essential oil content of three cultivars was unaffected by the curing and drying methods.

Ratnambal (19) evaluated 184 accessions of *Curcuma* for curing (dry recovery), essential oil, oleoresin and curcumin contents. Curing percentage varied from 13.5 to 32.4. The cultivar Konni had the maximum percentage of oleoresin (19.2). The volatile oil content was more in *Curcuma aromatica* than in

Curcuma domestica. Curcumin content varied from 2.3 % in Hahim to 10.9 % in cultivar Edapalayam. However, curcumin content was comparatively low in six exotic types as well as in 14 related species.

Economic assessment

The economics of production of turmeric was investigated by Mane *et al.* (16) in which they studied the economics of 60 cultivators with equal distribution in small, medium and large groups. The techniques like mean, percentage, ratio and cost concept of Cost-A, Cost-B and Cost-C were used to analyze the data. The results revealed that use of hired human labour was more than family human labour in turmeric production. The use of hired human labour, bullock labour and machine labour, increased with an increase in farm size. Whereas, the use of seed, FYM, nitrogen, phosphorus, potash, family human labour decreased with an increase in farm size. Per hectare net profit was ₹352053.97 in small farm followed by ₹ 344388.94 and ₹ 333662.36 on medium and large farm, respectively. The output-input ratio was 2.23 on small farm followed by that of 2.21 and 2.18 on medium and large farm, respectively. Per quintal cost of production in turmeric was ₹ 1475.75 on small farm followed by ₹1485.46 and ₹1501.09 on medium and large farm, respectively.

Singh (22) studied impact of integrated nutrient management on the economic cultivation of turmeric (*Curcuma longa* L.) in an acid alfisol of Himachal Pradesh where the pooled results of two years showed that highest mean yield ($150.8q ha^{-1}$), highest income over control (₹ 50,382 ha^{-1}) and highest net returns (₹ 63,566 ha^{-1}) were recorded in the treatment, 100% NPKS + 20 t FYM ha^{-1} as soil mulch. Whereas, highest benefit cost ratio (1:2.99) was recorded in treatment 100% NPKS. All the planting materials grown under juvenile guava orchard were found desirable in terms of gross return, net return and benefit :cost ratio over sole crop (Singh *et al.*, 24). In front line demonstrations (FLDs) on turmeric cv. Megha Turmeric-1, Deshmukh *et al.* (6) concluded that an attractive gross return (₹ 2,34,460/-) and net return (₹ 1,41,604/-) with higher B : C ratio (2.52) were recorded by SHGs with adoption of scientific management practices.

Mahawar and Grover (15) estimated the economics of turmeric cultivation for different categories of producers in Hoshiarpur, Nawashahar (Shaheed Bhagat Singh Nagar) and Gurdaspur districts of Punjab. The results revealed that on an overall basis the total cost incurred on use of physical input, machine labour and human labour use was ₹ 74438, ₹ 5227 and ₹ 29556 per hectare, respectively.

The total variable cost was ₹ 121720, ₹ 108357 and ₹103569 per hectare for small, medium and large producers, respectively. On an overall basis returns over variable cost per hectare was ₹ 45380 which was highest for large producers (₹ 68604) followed by medium producers (₹ 48660) and small producers (₹ 30822). Similarly, B-C ratio was also highest for large producers (1.66) followed by medium producers (1.45) and small producers (1.25). The overall benefit : cost (B : C) ratio was 1.40 denoting turmeric cultivation a profitable enterprise. The results of the study on economics of turmeric cultivation showed that the net returns per hectare received were quite high for all the categories of the farmers which clearly indicate the financial worthiness of turmeric crop.

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STUDIES ON GENETIC VARIABILITY AND TRAIT INTER-RELATIONSHIP IN BOTTLE GOURD (*Lagenaria siceraria* (Mol.) Standl)

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ABSTRACT : A field investigation was carried out at Horticulture Farm of Institute of Agriculture, Sriniketan to evaluate the twenty seven genotypes of bottle gourd in randomized block design with three replications. Sowing was done in late *khari* season of 2013 at a spacing of 50 cm between hills. Observations were recorded for 8 quantitative characters viz., node number of first female flower, sex ratio, days to first harvest, number of fruits per plant, fruit weight, fruit length, fruit girth and fruit yield per plant. The analysis of variance showed highly significant differences for all the characters studied indicating considerable variability among the genotypes. The highest GCV (34.84%) and PCV (35.14%) were observed for sex ratio. The differences between GCV and PCV were high for fruit number per plant indicating environmental influences. High heritability associates with high estimates of genetic advance in per cent of mean were noted for node number of first female flower, sex ratio, fruit length, fruit girth, number of fruits per plant and fruit yield per plant. It indicated the presence of additive gene effect and selection for these traits would be effective. Fruit yield/plant was positively and significantly correlated (at genotypic and phenotypic level) with fruit length and fruits number/plant. Negative associations of fruit yield/plant were noted with node number of first female flower, sex ratio and days to first harvest. Path analysis revealed that days to first harvest (2.783) and fruit girth (1.356) had very high positive direct effect on fruit yield/plant.

Keywords : Bottle gourd, variability, heritability, genetic advance, correlation, path co-efficient.

Bottle gourd (*Lagenaria siceraria* L.) is an important vegetable grown for its tender fruits both on homestead gardens and Farms. Bottle gourd is gaining popularity as a health food because of its easy digestibility, diuretic and cardiatonic effects (Rahaman *et al.*, 13). Bottle gourd is a cross pollinated crop with large amount of variation for many economically important traits. India is one of the centres of diversity of bottle gourd endowed with a variety of diverse germplasm (De-Candole, 5). Evaluation of a collection of bottle gourd from different parts of India revealed genetic diversity for various qualitative (Mathew *et al.*, 11) and quantitative characters (Singh *et al.*, 15). Collection and evaluation of bottle gourd genotypes from different parts of India will be helpful for identifying superior genotypes) for a specific region. Until now no systematic work have been reported on bottle gourd under Red and Laterite zone of West Bengal. Again, the earliness and yield potentiality of this crop can be improved through an effective breeding program. Studies on variability along with heritability and genetic advance helps in predicting inheritance pattern of various characters. Correlation and path co-efficient studies between yield and its components and their relative contributions to yield will be of great value in

planning sound breeding program. Therefore, the present investigation was undertaken with a view to work out phenotypic and genotypic coefficients of variation, heritability, genetic gain, association of important genetic traits and path analysis between components of yield in the twenty seven genotypes of bottle gourd, so as to make effective selection for improvement of this crop.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The experiment was conducted at the Horticulture Farm of Institute of Agriculture, Sriniketan, Visva-Bharati. The 27 genotypes of bottle gourd were sown in randomized block design with three replications. The crop was grown in channel and bed system (0.5m x 2.5m). The plant to plant spacing was given 50cm. Sowing of pre-soaked seeds was done on 14th September, 2013. Standard package of practices was adopted to raise a good crop. Observations were recorded for 8 characters viz., node number of first female flower, sex ratio, days to fruit harvest, number of fruits per plant, fruit weight, fruit length, fruit girth and yield per plant. The data were analyzed to estimate genotypic and phenotypic co-efficient of variation (Burton *et al.*, 4), heritability in broad sense (Burton and Devane, 3) and genetic advance (Allard, 1), correlation

co-efficient (Johnson *et al.*, 8) and path coefficients (Dewey and Lu, 6). The data were analyzed using Statistical Package for Agricultural Research (SPAR-1) developed at Indian Agricultural Statistical Research institute, New Delhi.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The mean sums of squares due to genotypes were highly significant for all the characters subjected to analysis of variance (Table 1). This indicated the

GCV for fruits number per plant indicated considerable environmental influences in inheritance of this character. High heritability associated with high estimates of genetic advance in percent of mean (GAPM) was noticed for sex ratio, fruit length, fruit girth, number of fruits per plant and fruit yield per plant. It indicated the presence of additive gene effect and selection for these traits would be effective. The present findings are supported by Kumar *et al.* (9) and Yadav *et al.* (17).

Table 1: Estimates of genetic parameters of 8 characters in 27 bottle gourd genotypes.

Traits	NNFFF	SR	DFH	NFP	FW	FL	FG	FYP
MSG	13.10**	21.34**	201.50**	2.21*	29746.25**	153.47**	126.01**	1.00**
CV (%)	10.96	4.53	4.72	17.99	12.12	11.38	6.80	9.79
Mean	10.98	7.64	77.71	3.35	775.80	28.74	27.68	2.74
Range	7.80 - 14.87	4.73 - 14.87	61.33 - 96.27	2.10 - 5.30	547.33 - 980.00	15.93 - 40.77	22.20 - 39.77	2.00 - 4.00
SE(±)	0.98	0.28	2.99	0.49	76.80	2.57	1.60	0.22
GCV	17.95	34.84	10.19	23.44	10.76	24.99	22.21	20.41
PCV	21.03	35.14	11.23	29.55	16.21	27.46	23.22	22.64
h ² b	72.85	98.34	82.34	62.91	44.06	82.83	91.43	81.29
GAPM	31.55	71.18	19.04	38.29	14.71	46.85	43.74	37.91

Here, * & ** indicates 5% and 1% level of significance, MSG = Mean sum of squares due to genotypes, CV = Co-efficient of Variation, SE = Standard Error, GCV = Genotypic coefficient of variation, PCV = Phenotypic coefficient of variation, h²b = Heritability, GAPM = Genetic Advance in percent of mean; NNFFF- Node Number of First Female Flower, SR- Sex Ratio, DFH- Days to First Harvest, NFP- Number of Fruits per Plant, FW- Fruit Weight (g), FL- Fruit Length (cm), FG- Fruit Girth (cm), FYP- Fruit Yield per Plant (Kg).

presence of considerable amount of variation among the genotypes to carry out further genetic analysis. Similar results were also reported by Pandit *et al.* (12). The highest coefficient of variation (17.99%) was recorded for number of fruits/plant. Therefore, it is possibility of selection of genotype having more number of fruits plant from available germplasm. Among the genotypes, the range of variation was observed from 7.80 to 14.87 with mean value of 10.98±0.98 for node number of flowers per plant, 4.73 to 14.87 with mean value of 7.64±0.28 for sex ratio, 61.33 to 96.27 days with mean value of 77.71±2.99 for days to first harvest, 2.10 to 5.30 with mean value of 3.35±0.49 for number of fruits per plant, 547.33 g to 980.00 g with mean value of 775.80±76.80 for fruit weight, 15.93 cm to 40.77 cm with mean value of 28.74±2.57 for fruit length, 22.20 cm to 39.77 cm with mean value of 27.68±1.60 for fruit girth and 2.00 kg to 4.00 kg with mean value of 2.74±0.22 for fruit yield per plant. In order to obtain a clear understanding of the pattern of variations, the phenotypic variances have been partitioned into genotypic and environmental variance. Considerable genotypic variances were found in sex ratio followed by fruit length and fruit number per plant. Greater value of PCV than that of

High genotypic and phenotypic coefficients of variation (>20%) were recorded for sex ratio, fruit length, fruit girth, fruits number/plant and fruit yield/plant. High heritability (>60%) coupled with high genetic advance over mean (>20%) was observed for node number of first female flower, sex ratio, fruit length, fruit girth, fruits number/plant and fruit yield/plant. The individual bottle gourd genotypes which showed desirable mean values in characters like sex ratio, fruit length and number of fruits per plant should be selected, because these characters with high genotypic coefficients of variation, high heritability and high genetic gain are controlled by additive gene action and hence direct selection is effective. Days to first fruit harvest and fruit weight registered low genotypic coefficient of variation, moderate heritability and low genetic gain which indicated the preponderance of non additive gene action and influence of environment.

Correlation indicated the mutual relationship among various plant characters and determines the component characters on which selection can be based for genetic improvement of yield. In present study, the nature of genotypic correlations was similar to the phenotypic correlations. However, values of

genotypic correlation were higher than the phenotypic correlation that indicates a less influence of environmental factors. Correlation coefficients at genotypic and phenotypic levels were worked out among different characters keeping fruit yield/plant as dependable variable (Table 2). Fruit yield/plant was positively and significantly correlated (at genotypic and

characters (Table 3). Path analysis revealed that days to first harvest (2.783) and fruit girth (1.356) had very high positive direct effect on fruit yield/plant, followed by node number of first female flower (0.769) and fruits number/plant (0.396). However, fruit length (-1.728) and fruit girth (-1.645) had negative and very high direct effects on fruit yield/plant. The characters

Table 2 : Genotypic (G) and Phenotypic (P) correlation coefficients among different characters of bottle gourd.

Characters		SR	DFH	NFP	FW	FL	FG	FYP
NNFFF	G	0.524**	0.646**	-0.530**	0.678**	-0.608**	0.401**	-0.438**
	P	0.455**	0.545**	-0.373**	0.574**	-0.360**	0.115	-0.297**
SR	G		0.596**	-0.284*	0.475**	-0.630**	0.212	-0.528**
	P		0.540**	-0.253*	0.454**	-0.491**	0.161	-0.458**
DFH	G			-0.471**	0.507**	-0.578**	-0.059	-0.581**
	P			-0.378**	0.451**	-0.411**	-0.086	-0.476**
NFP	G				-0.901**	0.268*	0.107	0.305**
	P				-0.748**	0.186	0.038	0.270*
FW	G					-0.406**	0.306**	-0.281*
	P					-0.297**	0.158	-0.215
FL	G						-0.380**	0.815**
	P						-0.257*	0.765*
FG	G							0.197
	P							0.190

* & ** indicates 5% and 1% level of significance; NNFFF- Node Number of First Female Flower, SR- Sex Ratio, DFH- Days to First Harvest, NFP- Number of Fruits per Plant, FW- Fruit Weight (g), FL- Fruit Length (cm), FG- Fruit Girth (cm), FYP- Fruit Yield per Plant (Kg).

phenotypic level) with fruit length and fruits number/plant. Similar associations of the characters were observed by Badade *et al.* (2) and Gayen and Hossain (7). However, node number of first female flower, sex ratio and days to first harvest had negative association at genotypic and phenotypic level with fruit yield/plant. Fruit yield/plant was also negatively correlated with fruit girth but only at genotypic level. Sarvesh and Singh (14) reported negative correlation of yield per plant with the node number of first female flower and days to first harvest in bottle gourd. Association of component characters revealed positive and significant genotypic and phenotypic correlations of node number of first female flower with sex ratio, days to first harvest, fruit girth and fruit weight (only at genotypic level); sex ratio with days to first harvest and fruit weight; days to first harvest with fruit weight; fruit length with fruits number/plant at only genotypic level; fruit girth with fruit weight (only at genotypic level). Manna and Paul (10) gave high priority to fruit length, fruit weight and number of fruits per plant for improvement of tomato.

The genotypic correlations were portioned into direct and indirect effects through path coefficient analysis to know the relative importance of 8

showing high negative direct effects can be selected via other traits. The present findings were in agreement with Umamaheswarappa *et al.* (16) and Gayen and Hossain (7). Node number of first female flower had negative and significant association with fruit yield/plant but its direct effect was noted high positive (0.769). This character showed very high positive indirect effect via days to first harvest (1.799) and high positive effect via fruit length (0.916) and fruit weight (0.544). Sex ratio had negative and significant correlation with fruit yield/plant but its direct effect (-0.115) was low. It had very high to moderate positive indirect effect via days to first harvest (1.659), node number of first female flower (0.403), fruits number/plant (0.490) and fruit girth (0.288). Days to first harvest had negative and significant association with fruit yield/plant. However, it possessed very high positive direct effect (2.783) on fruit yield per plant. This character showed high positive indirect effect via node number of first female flower (0.497) and fruits number/plant (0.815). Fruits number/plant was positively and significantly correlated with fruit yield/plant but it possessed very high negative direct effect (-1.728). This character had very high positive indirect effect via fruit weight (1.482). Fruit weight had

Table 3 : Genotypic path coefficient of different characters with fruit yield/plant of bottle gourd.

Characters	NNFFF	SR	DFH	NFP	FW	FL	FG	Correlation with fruit yield/plant (Kg)
NNFFF	0.769	-0.060	1.799	0.916	-1.115	-0.241	0.544	-0.438** -0.297**
SR	0.403	-0.115	1.659	0.490	-0.782	-0.249	0.288	-0.528** -0.458**
DFH	0.497	-0.069	2.783	0.815	-0.834	-0.229	-0.080	-0.581** -0.476**
NFP	-0.408	0.033	-1.312	-1.728	1.482	0.106	0.146	0.305** 0.270*
FW	0.522	-0.055	1.412	1.557	-1.645	-0.161	0.415	-0.281* -0.215
FL	-0.467	0.073	-1.608	-0.463	0.668	0.396	-0.516	0.815** 0.765*
FG	0.308	-0.024	-0.164	-0.185	-0.504	-0.151	1.356	0.197 0.190

Residual effect =0.166; Diagonal values (Bold) indicate direct effect; * & ** indicates 5% and 1% level of significance; NNFFF- Node Number of First Female Flower, SR- Sex Ratio, DFH- Days to First Harvest, NFP- Number of Fruits per Plant, FW- Fruit Weight (g), FL- Fruit Length (cm), FG- Fruit Girth (cm).

very high negative direct effect (-1.645) on fruit yield/plant that was confirmed by negative correlation between this character and fruit yield/plant. Its positive indirect effects were recorded very high *via* days to first harvest (1.412) and fruits number/plant (1.557), and high *via* node number of first female flower (0.522) and fruit weight (0.415). Fruit length possessed high positive direct effect (0.396) on fruit yield/plant. It also contributed towards fruit yield/plant possessing high positive indirect effects *via* fruit weight (0.668). Positive and higher magnitude of direct and indirect association of this character with fruit yield/plant resulted into positive and significant correlation. Fruit girth had very high positive direct effect (1.356) and high indirect effect *via* node number of first female flower (0.308) towards fruit yield/plant. Lower magnitude of positive indirect effects and higher magnitude of negative indirect effects cancelled the positive effects leading to non-significant correlation. The residual effect (0.166) indicated that the eight characters included in this study explained higher percentage of variation in yield of this population.

CONCLUSION

In present study, bottle gourd genotypes that showed desirable mean values with high genotypic coefficients of variation, high heritability and high genetic gain in traits like sex ratio, fruit length and number of fruits per plant should be selected, where direct selection assumed to be effective. Fruit yield/plant was also positively and significantly correlated (at genotypic and phenotypic level) with fruit length and fruits number/plant. Traits like days to first harvest and fruit weight should be given due consideration for bottle gourd improvement work as revealed from path analysis study.

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EFFECT OF PLANTING TIME AND INDOLE BUTYRIC ACID LEVELS ON ROOTING OF WOODY CUTTINGS OF PHALSA (*Grewia asiatica* L.)

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ABSTRACT : The study on effect of planting time and IBA levels on rooting of phalsa (*Grewia asiatica* L.) woody cuttings under mist house condition was undertaken in Horticulture Research Centre, Chauras Campus, HNBGU, Srinagar, Garhwal during 2013. The experiment was laid out in Factorial RBD with three replications. Cuttings were collected during winter season (mid January, February, March) and rainy season (mid June, July and August). The 20 cm long cuttings were prepared from 4 to 5 year old plants and treated with 1000, 1500, 2000 ppm IBA solutions by quick dip method. The cuttings treated with IBA 2000 ppm performed best in all aspects, as rooting percentage, length of shoot, length of root, thickening of root and leaf sprouting in shoot. Overall, M₄C₃ (mid June planting with 2000 ppm IBA) treatment combination was found best for all parameters studied.

Keywords : Phalsa, planting time, IBA, rooting, survival.

Phalsa (*Grewia asiatica* L.), belonging to family Tiliaceae, is an important minor fruit crop of India. It is native to the Indian sub-continent and South-East Asia. The genus *Grewia* has 140 species, of which only *Grewia asiatica* is of commercial importance. Phalsa cultivation is the most suitable for marginal lands, particularly for the utilization of the wastelands in arid and semi-arid regions of the world. Phalsa plant is a small bush and hardy in nature and preferred as an ideal crop for growing in hot and arid regions. It can be grown successfully on the slope of hills. It is also preferred for dry land horticulture and silvi-horticulture.

Ripe fruits are sub acidic and good source of vitamin A and vitamin-C. Fruits contain 50-60% juice, 10 to 11% sugar and 2-2.5% acids (Aykroyd, 3). The fruits are used for making excellent juice and squash. It is also used as table fruit by children. The fruits possess high medicinal properties. Its ripe fruit exert cooling effects, cure inflammation, heart and blood diseases, fever and constipation (Salunkhe and Desai, 13). The bark is used as a soap substitute in Burma. The leaves are believed to have antibiotic properties hence, applied on skin eruptions and they are known to have antibiotic action.

Phalsa is usually propagated by seeds which germinate in 15-20 days. Ground-layers, treated with hormones, may have 50% and air-layers may have 85% success. Cuttings are difficult to root. Only 20% of semi-hardwood cuttings from spring flush, treated with 1,000 ppm NAA, and planted in July rooted and grew normally (Morton, 9). The phalsa plant is readily

propagated by hardwood cuttings as well as layering (Samson, 14). Rooting of phalsa cuttings depends upon various factors such as pretreatment of cutting, growing condition, environmental factors, etc. which influence the regeneration ability of cuttings (Jadhav, 7). Although phalsa can strike roots but rooting is not appreciable. So, growth regulators are to be used to improve its high rooting ability (Yadav and Rajput, 21). Type of cutting and planting date also influence the rooting of phalsa (Singh *et al.*, 16). The stimulation of adventitious root formation in stem cuttings treated with auxin is well known. Hence, use of growth regulators and suitable planting season and condition would help for rapid multiplication in propagating phalsa cuttings.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The experiment was conducted at Horticulture Research Centre, Chauras Campus, HNB Garhwal University, Srinagar (Garhwal) during 2013. The Srinagar valley shows a semi-arid and sub-tropical climate. Except during rainy season rest of months are usually dry with exception of occasional showers during winter or early spring. Hardwood stem cuttings of phalsa (*Grewia asiatica* L.) were collected from 4 to 5 year old plants and 20 cm long stem cuttings with basal portion were prepared. For rooting media, sandy soil and farm yard manure (FYM) in ratio of 2:1 by v/v were mixed thoroughly, cleaned for stones and grasses, then the mixture was filled in root trainers. The cuttings were collected from winter season (mid January, February, March) and rainy season (mid June, July and August). The basal end of the cuttings was

dipped in dilute solutions of 1000 ppm, 1500 ppm and 2000 ppm IBA by quick dip method for 10 seconds before planting in the rooting medium. Cuttings used for control (check) were dipped in tap water only. After the treatment, the cuttings was immediately planted in root trainers and inserted 7.5 cm deep in the rooting media. The experiment was replicated thrice with 10 cuttings in each treatment and a total of 120 cuttings were planted in mist chamber. The mist chamber has the arrangement for intermittent misting to 60 seconds at every 30 minutes interval between 8 am and 8 pm. The number of sprouted cuttings, number of sprouts, length of sprout, percentage of rooting, number of primary roots percentage of secondary rooting, length of root, diameter of root, and fresh weight and dry weight of roots were measured after three months. The data recorded were subjected to statistical analysis by using Factorial Randomized Block Design (FRBD) as described by Cochran and Cox (5).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

A perusal of Table 1 indicated that the rooting percentage was influenced significantly by time of planting and IBA treatment. The highest rooting percentage (54.16 %) was recorded when cuttings were planted on mid June (M_4) followed by mid March (M_3), while the lowest rooting percentage (39.16 %) was recorded when cuttings were planted on mid January. The maximum rooting percentage of 62.23 % was recorded in cuttings treated with 2000 ppm IBA (C_3) and the minimum rooting percentage (31.66 %) was recorded under control. Treatment combination of M_6C_3 (mid August planting with 2000 ppm IBA) was found to be the best by producing 73.34 % of rooting. The enhanced hydrolytic activity in presence of applied IBA coupled with appropriate planting time might be responsible for the increased percentage of rooted cuttings. High carbohydrate and low nitrogen have

been reported to favour root formation. The findings of Subbaraj *et al.* (20) in *Gymnema slyvestre* are in agreement to present results. Mid August planting time (M_6) resulted in significantly higher number of primary roots per cutting (17.83). Among various concentrations of IBA, 2000 ppm IBA resulted in the higher number of primary roots per cutting (16.08). The interaction of planting time and IBA concentration (mid August planting with 2000 ppm IBA) was found to be best by producing maximum number of primary roots/cutting (21.44). This may be due to enhanced hydrolysis of carbohydrates caused by auxin treatment (Rajarama, 12; Singh *et al.*, 16).

Significantly the longest average length of roots/cutting (8.56 cm) was found by mid June planting. The appropriate planting time, application of IBA as well as genetic makeup of genotype used might have played vital role in augmenting the growth of roots (Singh and Singh, 15). Amongst IBA levels, the maximum average length of roots/cutting (8.60 cm) was recorded under 2000 ppm which might be due to enhanced histological features like formation of callus and tissues and differentiation of vascular tissues due to auxin (Mitra and Bose, 8). The longest root/cutting (11.38 cm) was produced by interaction of M_4C_3 (mid June planting with 2000 ppm IBA). The findings with respect to average length of root are agreed with the reports of Singh *et al.* (17) in *Thuja compecta* and Singh *et al.* (18) in *Duranta*. Mid June planting time exhibited the maximum diameter of roots (1.90 mm). The maximum average diameter of root (1.82 mm) was recorded with 2000 ppm IBA. The highest diameter of roots/cutting (2.44 mm) was observed under M_4C_3 (mid June planting with 2000 ppm IBA). The invigorated growth of shoot with IBA 2000 ppm at June planting synchronized due to more diameter of roots in these treatments (Table 2) which might have produced

Table 1: Rooting percentage and number of primary roots of phalsa cuttings as influenced by time of planting and IBA concentrations.

IBA Concentrations	Rooting percentage							Number of primary roots/plant						
	M_1	M_2	M_3	M_4	M_5	M_6	Mean	M_1	M_2	M_3	M_4	M_5	M_6	Mean
C_1 (1000 ppm)	43.34	50.00	50.00	53.34	46.66	53.34	49.45	8.34	6.78	8.22	12.61	13.78	17.44	11.19
C_2 (1500 ppm)	46.67	46.67	56.66	56.67	63.33	53.34	53.89	8.11	8.34	8.89	14.34	15.78	17.99	12.24
C_3 (2000 ppm)	50.00	60.00	63.34	66.66	60.00	73.34	62.23	10.33	14.11	11.50	18.55	20.55	21.44	16.08
C_0 (Control)	16.66	40.00	43.34	40.00	36.67	13.34	31.66	1.66	5.67	4.84	9.00	5.50	14.44	6.85
Mean	39.16	49.16	53.34	54.16	51.67	48.34		7.11	8.72	8.36	13.62	13.90	17.83	
C D (P=0.05)														
Time of planting (M)	4.76							1.57						
IBA Conc. (C)	3.89							1.28						
M × C	9.56							3.14						

Table 2: Length of longest roots and diameter of thickest roots of phalsa cuttings as influenced by time of planting and IBA concentrations.

IBA Concentrations	Length of longest root (cm)							Diameter of thickest roots (cm)						
	M ₁	M ₂	M ₃	M ₄	M ₅	M ₆	Mean	M ₁	M ₂	M ₃	M ₄	M ₅	M ₆	Mean
C ₁ (1000 ppm)	5.51	5.92	6.04	8.59	6.82	7.07	6.66	1.00	1.00	1.34	1.83	1.11	1.55	1.30
C ₂ (1500 ppm)	5.62	6.27	7.19	9.50	6.36	6.27	6.87	1.11	1.34	1.11	2.00	1.11	1.55	1.37
C ₃ (2000 ppm)	6.47	7.65	9.16	11.38	8.61	8.34	8.60	1.22	1.44	1.61	2.44	2.11	2.11	1.82
C ₀ (Control)	1.21	3.84	4.03	4.83	4.35	5.00	3.87	0.33	1.00	1.00	1.34	1.00	1.67	0.97
Mean	4.70	5.92	6.61	8.56	6.53	6.67		0.91	1.19	1.26	1.90	1.33	1.59	
C D (P=0.05)														
Time of planting (M)	0.59							0.27						
IBA Conc. (C)	0.48							0.22						
M × C	1.19							0.54						

more assimilates and resulted in thickest root growth. These findings are also agree with the results of Awad *et al.* (2).

The maximum average fresh weight of roots per cutting (1.00 g) was recorded under mid June planting time (M₄). Imtiyaz and Sofi (6) also observed the significant variation for these parameters in the two rootstocks with significant increased per cent survival, callusing, bud sprouting and rhizogenesis in M-26 with the application of 2000 ppm IBA than M-9. Among IBA concentrations, C₃ (2000 ppm IBA) revealed the maximum average fresh weight of roots/cutting (1.04 g). The maximum average fresh weight of roots/cutting (1.21 g) was recorded due to interaction M₄C₂ (mid June planting with 1500 ppm IBA). These finding also agreed with the Bhusal *et al.* (4) as reported in *Citrus*. The greater average dry weight of roots/cutting (0.50 g) was recorded with M₅ (mid July planting time). Among IBA concentrations, 2000 ppm IBA produced the maximum average dry weight of roots/cutting (0.56 g).

Average length of sprout per cutting was recorded maximum (7.81 cm) under mid June planting (M₄). The maximum length of sprout per cutting (9.46 cm) was found under 2000 ppm IBA followed by 1500 ppm IBA, while the minimum length of sprout (4.35 cm) was observed under control (Table 4). Auxin concentration has a positive impact in stimulation of growth of pre-formed buds. Due to interaction of planting time and IBA concentration, the maximum length of sprout per cutting (10.46 cm) was produced under M₄C₃ (mid June planting with 2000 ppm IBA treatment). Mid June planting time (M₆) exhibited the maximum diameter of sprout/cutting (1.88 mm). The maximum average diameter of sprout (2.59 mm) was recorded under C₃ (2000 ppm IBA) and the minimum average diameter of sprout (1.39 mm) was under C₁ (1000 ppm IBA). Treatment combination of M₄C₃ resulted in the highest average diameter of sprout per cutting (2.67 mm). The

present findings are similar to the reports of Panwar *et al.* (11) in *Bougainvillea* var. Alok.

The maximum average number of leaves/cutting (8.56) was recorded by mid June planting, while the minimum number of leaves per cutting (3.62) was under M₃ (mid March planting). Suitable environmental and climatic conditions for growth of shoots (more light and high photoperiod) might be the cause for the increase in length of shoots and the number of leaves in cuttings of late June (Abdou *et al.*, 1). Significantly the maximum average number of leaves/cutting (Table 5) was obtained by 2000 ppm IBA treatment. The highest average number of leaves per cutting was produced by the interaction of M₄C₃ (mid June planting with 2000 ppm IBA). Srivastava *et al.* (19) had also observed the best results in terms of growth and survival of phalsa cuttings treated with 2000 ppm IBA as compared to 100 and 300 ppm IBA concentrations. Planting time and IBA concentrations affected the number of sprouts per cutting significantly. Among various planting times, M₃ (mid March planting) produced the maximum number of sprouts/cutting (2.50). The highest average number of sprouts/cutting (3.05) was observed with 2000 ppm IBA, while the lowest average number of sprouts per cutting (1.45) was recorded under control. The highest average number of sprouts/cutting (3.34) was recorded under the interaction of mid March planting with 2000 ppm IBA treatment. Environmental conditions in the greenhouse may also be effective for rooting of cuttings (Nair *et al.*, 10).

From the above discussion, it may be concluded that time of planting and various levels of IBA had a large impact on the success, survival and rooting in cuttings of phalsa (*Grewia asiatica* L.) cv. Dwarf type. Time of planting in mid June (M₄) and IBA @ 2000 ppm were found to be the best treatments may be

Table 3: Fresh and dry weight of roots/ cutting (g) of phalsa cuttings as influenced by time of planting and IBA concentrations.

IBA Concentrations	Fresh weight of roots per cutting (g)							Dry weight of roots per cutting (g)						
	M ₁	M ₂	M ₃	M ₄	M ₅	M ₆	Mean	M ₁	M ₂	M ₃	M ₄	M ₅	M ₆	Mean
C ₁ (1000 ppm)	0.92	0.82	0.87	1.06	0.93	0.91	0.92	0.43	0.34	0.44	0.51	0.57	0.45	0.45
C ₂ (1500 ppm)	0.92	0.85	0.86	1.21	0.97	0.94	0.96	0.43	0.37	0.41	0.46	0.52	0.47	0.44
C ₃ (2000 ppm)	1.04	0.86	1.05	1.13	1.16	1.02	1.04	0.57	0.37	0.63	0.59	0.62	0.56	0.56
C ₀ (Control)	0.22	0.57	0.57	0.60	0.59	0.74	0.55	0.09	0.22	0.25	0.24	0.28	0.33	0.23
Mean	0.77	0.77	0.84	1.00	0.91	0.90		0.38	0.32	0.43	0.45	0.50	0.45	
C D (P=0.05)														
Time of planting (M)	0.06							0.04						
IBA Conc. (C)	0.05							0.03						
M × C	0.13							0.08						

Table 4: Length of longest sprout and diameter of thickest sprout of phalsa cuttings as influenced by time of planting and IBA concentrations

IBA Concentrations	Length of longest sprouts (cm)							Diameter of thickest sprout (mm)						
	M ₁	M ₂	M ₃	M ₄	M ₅	M ₆	Mean	M ₁	M ₂	M ₃	M ₄	M ₅	M ₆	Mean
C ₁ (1000 ppm)	5.51	6.37	6.74	7.46	7.93	6.82	6.80	1.11	1.34	1.34	1.50	1.44	1.67	1.39
C ₂ (1500 ppm)	6.39	6.50	7.74	8.08	7.59	7.17	7.24	1.22	1.67	1.84	1.67	1.89	2.00	1.71
C ₃ (2000 ppm)	8.11	8.52	9.59	10.46	9.91	10.19	9.46	3.11	2.33	2.34	2.67	2.55	2.55	2.59
C ₀ (Control)	1.50	4.27	4.50	5.26	5.35	5.25	4.35	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.34	1.34	2.12
Mean	5.37	6.41	7.14	7.81	7.69	7.36		1.61	1.58	1.62	1.70	1.80	1.88	
C D (P=0.05)														
Time of planting (M)	0.53							0.19						
IBA Conc. (C)	0.43							0.15						
M × C	1.06							0.38						

Table 5: Number of leaves and sprouts per cutting of phalsa as influenced by time of planting and IBA concentrations.

IBA Concentrations	Number of new leaves							Number of sprout per cutting						
	M ₁	M ₂	M ₃	M ₄	M ₅	M ₆	Mean	M ₁	M ₂	M ₃	M ₄	M ₅	M ₆	Mean
C ₁ (1000 ppm)	4.11	4.78	3.34	4.67	4.67	4.00	4.26	1.89	2.11	2.34	1.34	2.00	1.77	1.90
C ₂ (1500 ppm)	4.88	4.77	3.61	4.16	4.44	5.34	4.53	2.34	2.44	2.67	1.16	2.11	2.11	2.13
C ₃ (2000 ppm)	6.09	5.77	4.89	5.44	5.22	5.11	5.42	3.00	3.11	3.34	2.77	3.00	3.11	3.05
C ₀ (Control)	1.93	2.34	2.67	3.34	2.67	2.67	2.60	1.00	1.00	1.67	2.00	1.34	1.67	1.45
Mean	4.25	4.41	3.62	4.40	4.25	4.27		2.05	2.16	2.50	1.81	2.11	2.16	
C D (P=0.05)														
Time of planting (M)	0.48							0.31						
IBA Conc. (C)	0.39							0.26						
M × C	0.96							0.63						

M₁= Mid January, M₂= Mid February, M₃= Mid March, M₄= Mid June, M₅ = Mid July, M₆= Mid August , C₁= 1000 ppm IBA , C₂= 1500 ppm IBA, C₃ = 2000 ppm IBA and C₀ = Control.

recommended for the propagation of phalsa by stem cuttings.

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STANDARDIZATION OF LOW TEMPERATURE STORAGE TECHNOLOGY WITH NOVEL PACKAGING TECHNIQUES IN ROSE CUT FLOWER CV. PASSION

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ABSTRACT : Rose cut flowers of cv. Passion were subjected to storage techniques viz., seal packaging with polypropylene (PP 24 μ), butter paper (52 μ), holding in 200 mgL⁻¹ Al₂(SO₄)₃ vase solution, holding in vase (distilled water) and without any packaging and without holding in vase water at low temperature (2°C) for 10 days. The ten days cold stored flowers were compared with fresh cut flowers for vase life and quality. The polypropylene packaged low temperature stored cut roses showed optimistic results with best postharvest flower quality at the end of 10 days storage period as compared to other treatments. The PP packaged low temperature stored rose cut flowers showed maximum water uptake, retention of fresh weight, retained higher anthocyanin pigment content in the petals and maximum bud length and diameter when held in vase (distilled water) after 10 days of low temperature storage and were at par with fresh flowers (not stored). Cut flowers held in vase solution during low temperature storage failed to retain bud stage but showed advance bud opening at the end of the storage period. PP packaged low temperature stored cut roses showed higher membrane stability index (MSI) of petal tissue. The same treatment recorded maximum score for quality test. Thus PP packed cold stored rose flowers retained best flower quality as well as showed higher vase life as compared to the rose flowers stored with other treatments.

Keywords : Rose, polypropylene, low temperature storage, anthocyanin, vase life.

Rose (*Rosa indica* L.), belongs to family Rosaceae, is one of the oldest flowers under cultivation and most popular among all commercial flowers throughout the world. It is one of the nature's beautiful creations and is universally known as the "Queen of Flowers". Rose flowers are beautiful in shape, size, fragrance and colour and have good demand in domestic and export market. The demand of cut roses often reaches its peak followed by high prices during festival times while at times faces the problem of price crash during market gluts. Effective storage technique and long distance transportation can facilitate better market strategy for roses. However, long distance transportation of roses *via* sea shipment is further restricted due its limited vase life, deterioration in flower quality (Mor *et al.*, 8; van Doorn and D' Hont, 14) and chilling injury (Pompodakis *et al.*, 10) at low temperature storage. Further, low temperature storage has also been known to promote ethylene production that further triggers early senescence in rose (Faragher *et al.*, 2; Devechi *et al.*, 1). Seal packaging of cut flowers with polyfilms at low temperature is known to create modified atmospheric conditions (Farber *et al.*, 3). Considering the immense importance of rose in domestic as well as overseas market, it seemed the right

way to plan the experiment to evaluate proper low temperature storage technique along novel packing material for rose cut flower cv. Passion.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Fresh rose cut flowers cv. Passion were obtained from greenhouse complex, Navsari Agricultural University, Navsari and were brought to the Floriculture Laboratory, College of Horticulture and Forestry, NAU Navsari at an ambient temperature (18-21°C). The experiment was conducted in completely randomized block design. There were five treatments and each treatment was repeated four times. Cut roses at uniform bud size, fresh weight (10 \pm 2 g) and stem length (50 \pm 5 cm) were selected and divided into five groups each having one hundred twenty flowers (30 in each repetition) and subjected to different treatments. Treatment combinations included seal packaging with polypropylene (PP) 24 microns (T₁), seal packaging with butter paper 52 microns (T₂), holding in 200 mgL⁻¹ Al₂(SO₄)₃ solution (T₃), holding in distilled water (T₄) and without any packaging and holding solution in CFB box (T₅). All bunches were stored at 2°C temperature in cold storage for 10 days. After 10 days of cold storage, the flowers were taken out from cold storage,

unpacked and removed from respective packaging treatments and were held in distilled vase water at ambient conditions in the laboratory for recording of different observations. Fresh flowers of cv. Passion as control (T_0) bought from the same greenhouse complex were also held in distilled water in order to compare with treated and stored flowers. Observations regarding vase life and different postharvest parameters were recorded at different intervals during vase life. Total water uptake, fresh weight, bud length and bud diameter and bud opening were recorded on 2nd, 4th and 6th day of vase life. Membrane stability index was recorded on 2nd, 4th and 6th day of vase life. MSI was calculated on the basis of electrolyte leakage (ion leakage) of petals. Anthocyanin pigment content was analysed from the rose petals on 4th day of vase life. Quality of the flowers in terms of colour and freshness was recorded on 2nd, 4th and 6th day of vase life and given score from 1 to 5 on visual basis.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Data depicted in Table 1 revealed that the maximum water uptake (60.1 ml) was observed in the cut rose flowers packed in polypropylene (T_1) which

that were packaged in polypropylene (T_1), (10.58, 3.89 and -4.68 %) at 2nd, 4th and 6th day of vase life respectively. Minimum fresh weight loss in tuberose spikes packed with vented PP bags have also been reported by Mazumdar *et al.* (7) Maximum anthocyanin pigment content (8.43 mg/g fresh weight) was observed in fresh flowers (T_0), which was at par with cold stored rose cut flowers that were packaged with polypropylene T_1 (8.12 mg/g fresh weight). Seal packaging of fresh produce in poly films is known to create modified internal gaseous components passively (Farber *et al.*, 3), that helps in minimizing metabolic activities during storage and retains fresh produce in normal condition (Zeltzer *et al.*, 15). Thus, PP packaging contributed in maintaining higher water uptake as well as fresh weight retention in stored cut flowers. Packaging with poly films have been earlier known to enhance water uptake after cold storage as well as retain fresh weight in gladiolus cut spikes (Singh *et al.*, 11 and Grover *et al.*, 4), gerbera (Patel and Singh, 9) and solidago (Zeltzer *et al.*, 15). In addition to this, storage conditions including low oxygen and high relative humidity have been found to influence anthocyanin retention in different plant

Table 1: Effect of different storage techniques (wet and dry) on quantitative parameters and pigment content of rose cv. Passion.

.Storage Technology	Day After Storage						
	Water uptake (ml)			Fresh weight (%)			Anthocyanin content (mg/g fresh weight)
	2 nd	4 th	6 th	2 nd	4 th	6 th	4 th
T_0 -Control, Fresh Flowers, no storage	55.3	51.98	41.47	11.97	4.26	-3.23	8.43
T_1 -Polypropylene	60.1	50.62	40.53	10.58	3.89	-4.68	8.12
T_2 -Butter paper	12.2	7.40	2.13	-29.25	-31.64	-38.49	5.94
T_3 -200mg/l $Al_2(SO_4)_3$	46.9	42.94	25.07	8.64	-7.10	-12.87	7.61
T_4 -Water	35.6	31.44	19.21	6.73	-9.02	-12.81	6.17
T_5 -Without any packaging	8.4	5.13	1.83	-40.27	-40.78	-46.78	3.99
C.D. (P=0.05)	1.53	0.71	0.58	0.63	0.59	0.9	0.38

was at par with fresh flowers (Control, 55.3 ml) at 2nd day of vase life. Fresh flowers (T_0 -control) recorded maximum water up take (51.98 ml and 41.47 ml) which was at par with cut flowers that were PP packaged and cold stored (50.62 ml and 40.53 ml) at the 4th and 6th day of vase life. Rose flowers that were stored with other treatments showed very low water uptake. Further, maximum fresh weight retention (11.97, 4.26 and -3.23%) was observed in fresh rose flowers (T_0 control), which was at par with the cold stored flowers

products (Markakis, 6). Modified atmospheric conditions with PP polyfilm packaging retained anthocyanin pigments in the low temperature stored rose petals as earlier observed in gladiolus (Singh *et al.*, 12).

Data presented in the Table 2 stated that the maximum bud length (3.73 cm) was observed in fresh flowers (T_0 -control), which was at par with cut flowers packaged in polypropylene T_1 (3.67 cm), cut flowers dipped in $Al_2(SO_4)_3$ - T_3 (3.63 cm), and water- T_4 (3.43

cm) at 2nd DAS. On 4th and 6th DAS the maximum bud length was observed in rose cut flowers packaged in polypropylene (3.77 and 3.57 cm) respectively which was at par with fresh flowers (T₀) kept (3.93).

roses that were PP packaged might have increased the cell-turgidity and cell enlargement leading to petal expansion as also observed earlier in gerbera (Patel and Singh, 9).

Table 2: Effect of different storage techniques (wet and dry) on qualitative parameters and vase life of rose cv. Passion

Storage Technology	Day After Storage									
	Bud length (cm)			Bud diameter (cm)			MSI (%)			Vase life (days)
	2 nd	4 th	6 th	2 nd	4 th	6 th	2 nd	4 th	6 th	
T ₀ .Control, Fresh Flowers, no storage	3.73	3.93	3.83	4.53	5.33	5.33	90.03	63.43	38.63	5.23
T ₁ .Polypropylene	3.67	3.77	3.57	4.33	5.03	5.13	89.53	62.27	37.57	5.07
T ₂ .Butter paper	3.07	2.67	2.17	3.03	3.17	3.20	36.27	26.37	23.53	1.30
T ₃ .200 mg/l Al ₂ (SO ₄) ₃	3.63	3.40	2.83	4.87	4.73	4.86	75.87	51.63	26.67	3.23
T ₄ .Water	3.43	3.13	2.77	4.50	4.57	4.62	68.03	42.13	23.77	2.33
T ₅ .Without any packaging	2.77	2.47	1.93	3.07	3.13	3.20	32.63	26.07	21.63	1.03
C.D. (P=0.05)	0.18	0.17	0.19	0.16	0.18	0.19	1.05	1.18	0.83	0.14

Table 3: Effect of different storage techniques (wet and dry) on qualitative parameters of rose cv. Passion

Storage Technology	Day After Storage					
	Quality			Bud opening (%)		
	2 nd	4 th	6 th	2 nd	4 th	6 th
T ₀ .Control, Fresh Flowers, no storage	5	5	4	86.43	100.00	100.00
T ₁ .Polypropylene	5	5	4	80.23	100.00	100.00
T ₂ .Butter paper	1	1	1	36.34	39.46	41.00
T ₃ .200mg/l Al ₂ (SO ₄) ₃	3	2	1	95.63	92.34	95.26
T ₄ .Water	3	2	1	85.00	86.39	88.67
T ₅ .Without any packaging	1	1	1	36.04	38.27	41.00
C.D.(P=0.05)	-	-	-	1.9	1.69	1.60

Quality rating score: 1-Dull/Flaccid, 2-Poor, 3-Fair, 4-Very good and 5-Excellent

and 3.83 cm). The trend in the data showed increase in bud diameter in fresh flowers (4.53, 5.33 and 5.33 cm) and in stored flowers that were PP packaged (4.33, 5.03 and 5.13 cm) over all other storage techniques. Further, maximum Membrane Stability Index(MSI) of the petal tissue was observed in the fresh flowers, (T₀) (90.03%, 63.43% and 38.63%) which was at par with cut flowers packaged in polypropylene (PP), T₁ (89.53%, 62.27% and 37.57%) at 2nd, 4th and 6th DAS. Increase in bud size can be attributed to the retention of higher fresh weight and petal tissue integrity as evidenced from retained MSI level. The enhanced water uptake by fresh rose flowers and in cut

Maximum vase life was recorded in fresh flowers (control) (5.23 days) which were at par with cut flowers packaged in polypropylene-T₁ (5.07 days). Further, flower quality of fresh flowers (not stored) and of PP packed cold stored flowers was found to have higher quality score on visual basis in terms of colour and freshness compared to flowers cold stored with other treatments (Table 3). In terms of bud opening percentage, initially on 2nd day, it was maximum (95.63%) in cold stored flowers that were held in Al₂(SO₄)₃. Gradually PP packed cold stored flowers as well as fresh flowers showed 100% opening on 4th and 6th day of vase life while the untreated cold stored

and butter paper packed cold stored roses showed restricted opening. Enhanced bud opening along with improved flower quality of cut roses packed with PP during low temperature (2°C) and in fresh flowers was due to availability of water through improved water uptake when held in vase water after storage. Water balance (Halevy and Mayak, 5) along with intact cell membrane of petal tissue (Torre *et al.*, 13) was suggested to improve bud opening in cut flowers. In addition to this, the retention of fresh weight, better water balance with high water uptake along alleviated MSI delayed the petal senescence and improved vase life of PP packaged low temperature stored cut roses.

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RESIDUAL EFFECT OF PRE-HARVEST SPRAY OF MH AND STORAGE CONDITIONS OF BULBS FOR SUCCEEDING CROP OF SPIDER LILY (*Hymenocallis littoralis* L.) CV. LOCAL

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ABSTRACT : The experiment to find out residual effect of pre-harvest spray of MH and storage conditions of bulbs for succeeding crop of spider lily (*Hymenocallis littoralis* L.) cv. Local was carried out at Department of Horticulture, College of Agriculture, Junagadh Agricultural University, Junagadh during 2012-2013. The experiment consisted of six levels of pre-harvest MH spray with four levels of storage conditions and it was laid out in Factorial Randomized Block Design (FCRD) with three replications. Minimum days taken to sprouting, maximum number of leaves at 1st flowering stage and leaf area were found in control (no maleic hydrazide spray, and bulbs stored in plastic carets at an ambient temperature). But, minimum days to first flower emergence were found in control (no maleic hydrazide spray) and net bags at an ambient temperature. Maximum plant height at 1st flowering stage was found in the MH 500 ppm with net bags at an ambient temperature. Maximum length of flower stalk was found in the MH 500 ppm with plastic carets at an ambient temperature. Maximum chlorophyll content in leaves, number of flower stalks/plant, number of flowers harvested per net plot and yield of flowers were found in MH 3000 ppm with plastic carets at an ambient temperature.

Key words : Spider lily bulbs, field planting, pre-harvest MH spray, storage conditions,

Spider lily (*Hymenocallis littoralis* L.) is native to South America and belongs to the family Amaryllidaceae. It is bulbous ornamental plant which grows upto 45-60 cm tall. It has long, broad and strap shaped light green leaves. It is cultivated for its white, fragrant spidery shaped flowers for varied used as loose flower for making decoration, bridal car decoration, bouquets preparation etc. An umbel produced 9-10 flowers on its head. 2-3 flower umbels are produced at a time on a single well developed plant. It is suitable for growing in the field as well as in pots. Also as cut flower it is attractive but the flowers do not last long. These are most suitable as plants for border plantings in the greenhouse, alongside the boundary walls and water channels, in herbaceous border, alongside the lawn and also in beds in the gardens but these prefer sunny situations. As they are propagated through bulbs, during storage pre-planting sprouting and decay of bulbs are the serious problems. MH is a growth-regulatory substance that disrupts cell division. It spreads upwards and downwards in stored bulbs and it suppresses sprouting and root growth. MH penetrates extensively into the plant and is transported in the phloem to actively growing tissues including the bulbs and tubers. Residues persist in these parts

sufficiently to induce dormancy and hamper sprouting for fairly.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The experiment was carried out at Department of Horticulture, College of Agriculture, Junagadh Agricultural University, Junagadh during 2012-2013. Three years old standing crop of spider lily was selected for pre harvest treatments. During the pre harvest spray the standing crop was under rest (leg phase of flowering). Spray of maleic hydrazide (MH) at different concentration was done as per treatments, one month before uplifting of bulbs. The bulbs were carefully dug out and uplifted and cleaned and separated from upper plant portion. Bavistin as fungicide treatment was given to these bulbs before storage for five months period. The experiment consisted of six levels of pre-harvest MH spray *i.e.*, P₀- Control (No MH treatment), P₁- 500 ppm, P₂- 1000 ppm, P₃- 2000 ppm, P₄- 3000 ppm and P₅- 4000 ppm MH with four levels of storage conditions S₁- Plastic carets at 12°C, S₂- Net bags at 12°C, S₃- Plastic carets at an ambient temperature and S₄- Net bags at an ambient temperature. Five months stored bulbs were planted in the field according to the treatment combinations to see the residual effect of MH and

storage conditions on vegetative growth, flowering behaviour flower quality and flower yield.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Effect of Pre-Harvest Spray of MH

Vegetative parameters

Days taken to bulbs sprouting were maximum (35.58 days) in 4000 MH which was found at par with 1000 to 3000 ppm MH. The earliest sprouting (27.42 days) was noticed in control (P_0). This may be due to fact that the MH spray had suppressed the activity of GA_3 , which is growth promoter and might be resulted in delayed in sprouting (Weaver, 7). The height of plant was decreased linearly with every increase in concentration of MH. The maximum plant height of 30.25 cm was recorded with spray of 500 ppm MH (Table 1). Minimum plant height at 1st flowering stage (17.08 cm) was found in the MH 4000 ppm (P_5) which was at par with MH 3000 and 2000 ppm. The suppression in plant height might be due to residual effect of MH which inhibited to sprouting and shoot growth of modified plant organs on storage (Wittwer *et al.*, 8). Delay in flowering and reduced plant height due to exogenous application of growth retardants like ethrel as reported by Kumar and Singh (2) also

confirms the present findings. Similarly, number of leaves at 1st flowering stage as well as leaf area were also decreased linearly with every increase in MH concentration. The maximum number of leaves (6.61) and maximum leaf area (330.75 cm²) were found in control (P_0) which was at par with P_1 and P_2 . This might be due to good plant growth at low level of growth inhibitors like MH as pre-harvest spray which might had increased sink levels and subsequently resulted in maximum number of leaves (Raja and Palanisamy, 4; Weaver, 7). The maximum chlorophyll content (55.37 µg/g) was found with MH 3000 ppm (P_4) being at par with P_5 confirming to the reports of Dhua *et al.* (1).

Flowering parameters

A perusal of data (Table 2) revealed that days to first flower emergence was significantly lowest (40.86 days) in control. This might be due to good plant growth in absence of MH, a growth retardant, might had increased sink level and subsequently in early flower emergence which are in line of Raja and Palanisamy (4) in tuberose. Maximum number of flower stalks/plant (9.27) was found in MH 3000 ppm (P_4). The results showing effectiveness of MH treatment which might have kept stored bulbs healthy and sufficient food reserve and acceleration of flowering

Table 1: Effect of pre harvest spray of MH and storage conditions of bulbs on growth parameters during succeeding crop of spider lily.

Treatment	Storage condition				
	Days taken to sprouting (days)	Plant height at first flowering (cm)	Number of leaves at 1 st flowering	Leaf Area (cm ²)	Chlorophyll content (µg/g)
Pre-harvest spray treatments					
P_0 - 0 (control)	27.42	28.58	6.61	330.75	43.59
P_1 - 500 ppm MH	30.67	30.25	6.00	318.75	49.31
P_2 - 1000 ppm MH	34.17	25.42	5.91	300.40	49.23
P_3 - 2000 ppm MH	34.25	19.02	5.82	278.69	52.11
P_4 - 3000 ppm MH	34.50	18.42	5.74	292.31	55.37
P_5 - 4000 ppm MH	35.58	17.08	5.24	277.69	54.08
C. D. (P=0.05)	2.26	5.13	0.75	34.47	5.28
Storage conditions					
S_1 - Plastic carets at 12°C	37.50	20.17	5.29	284.99	48.16
S_2 - Net bags at 12°C	37.78	21.06	5.49	292.21	48.68
S_3 - Plastic carets at ambient temp.	24.72	22.72	6.51	325.26	55.79
S_4 - Net bags at an ambient temp.	28.17	28.56	6.31	296.21	49.76
C. D. (P=0.05)	1.85	4.19	0.61	28.14	4.31
Interactions: P × S					
C. D. (P=0.05)	NS	NS	NS	NS	NS
C.V.%	8.40	10.66	15.54	13.98	12.70

Table 2 : Effect of pre harvest spray of MH and storage conditions on flowering parameter of during succeeding crop of spider lily.

Treatment	Storage condition					
	Days to first flower emergence	Number of flower stalks / plant	Length of flower stalk (cm)	Number of flowers / plant	Number of flowers harvested/ net plot (1.80 × 0.9 cm ²)	Yield of flowers harvested (bundles/ha)
Pre-harvest spray treatments						
P ₀ - 0 (control)	40.86	7.96	53.39	89.32	535.92	62518
P ₁ - 500 ppm MH	42.25	8.01	57.28	92.32	552.72	64481
P ₂ - 1000 ppm MH	41.93	7.88	54.28	91.96	551.76	64372
P ₃ - 2000 ppm MH	41.46	8.03	49.05	93.71	562.26	65597
P ₄ - 3000 ppm MH	48.83	9.27	48.91	106.98	641.88	74886
P ₅ - 4000 ppm MH	47.50	8.23	49.05	102.01	612.06	69305
C. D. (P=0.05)	5.66	0.91	5.57	9.54	38.12	8850
Storage conditions :						
S ₁ - Plastic carets at 12°C	48.72	7.72	49.38	89.24	589.44	62470
S ₂ - Net bags at 12°C	47.67	7.33	51.47	86.27	517.62	60392
S ₃ - Plastic carets at ambient temp.	41.23	8.88	54.37	109.76	658.56	76830
S ₄ - Net bags at an ambient temp.	37.60	7.80	52.85	99.02	594.12	67123
C. D. (P=0.05)	4.62	1.04	NS	11.51	72.02	2636
Interactions: P x S						
C. D. (P=0.05)	NS	NS	NS	NS	NS	NS
C.V.%	15.70	13.79	12.79	10.13	11.25	15.60

might be due to increased amount of endogenous MH like substances and also better development of flower primordials. This might be due to its effect on causing growth of several bud primordial (Singh *et al.*, 5). Reduction in flower stalk length and increase in number of flower stalks due to application of ethrel (Umrao *et al.*, 6) confirms present results. Length of flower stalk was maximum (57.28cm) with MH 500 ppm (P₁) and the length of flower stalk was decreased by increasing levels of MH. The results are in consonance with Maurya and Nagda (3). Whereas, number of flowers/ plant (106.98) and number of flowers harvested per net plot (641.88) were highest in MH 3000 ppm (P₄) but it was found at par with 4000 ppm (P₅). Here, MH might had been absorbed and stopped cell division but not cell expansion. Effective means of controlling sprouting and moisture loss during long term cold storage of bulbs and these healthy and vigorous bulbs might be expressed maximum number of flowers due to stimulation of endogenous substances in the treated plants. Similarly, highest yield of flowers harvested (74886 bundles/ha) was obtained with MH 3000 ppm (P₄) being at par with P₅. This might be due to its effect on causing growth of several buds primordial; hence, number of flowers per

plant and number of flower stalks per plant are converted in to maximum yield per hectare.

Effect of Storage Conditions

Vegetative parameters

The pre harvest MH treated bulbs when stored in plastic carets at an ambient temperature (S₃) resulted in positive outstanding in most of the vegetative parameters (Table 1) when these bulbs are planted in field. Days taken to sprouting (24.72 days) were significantly minimum in plastic carets at an ambient temperature (S₃). Plant height at 1st flowering stage (28.56 cm) was significantly highest in net bags at an ambient temperature (S₄). Significantly maximum number of leaves at 1st flowering stage (6.51) and leaf area (325.26 cm²) were found the highest in bulbs stored in plastic carets at an ambient temperature (S₃). This storage condition kept bulbs more healthy and viable for next generation. Bulbs storage in net bags at ambient conditions (S₄) might had decreased growth inhibitors, ultimately resulted in maximum leaf area. Chlorophyll content was found maximum (55.79 µg/g) in plants grown from bulbs stored in plastic carets at an ambient temperature (S₃). This might be due to decrease in food material in bulbs during summer and

stored for four to six months in ambient condition of high temperature and high humidity due to monsoon rains. During this period, the bulbs sprout very easily and development of chlorophyll content in leaves might get congenial condition in field grown lily plants.

Flowering parameters

Packing of bulbs in different type of bags had also exhibited significant effects on flowering parameters (Table 2). Significantly the earliest flower emergence (37.60 days) was observed in bulbs stored in net bags at an ambient temperature (S₄). Packing of bulbs in plastic carets (S₁) delayed first flower emergence by about 10 days over S₃. Maximum number of flower stalks/plant (8.88) and maximum length of flower stalk (54.37 cm) as well as number of flowers/ plant (109.76) were found in bulbs packed in plastic carets and stored at an ambient temperature (S₃). This might be due to good plant growth had increased sink level and subsequently resulted in early floret emergence (Dhua *et al.*, 1). Maximum number of flowers harvested per net plot (658.56) was highest in bulbs packed in plastic carets and stored under ambient temperature (S₃), but it was at par with (S₄). Similarly, highest yield of flowers harvested (76830 bundles/ha) was found in bulbs stored in plastic carets at an ambient temperature (S₃).

From foregoing discussion, it can be inferred that for better growth, flowering and flower yield of spider lily under field condition, the pre-harvest spray of MH 3000 ppm was found best when bulbs were stored in plastic carets at an ambient temperature having good circulation of air in the store room during five months of storage.

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ANALYSIS OF FRUIT QUALITY OF KINNOW MANDARIN HYBRID IN ARID IRRIGATED AREAS OF RAJASTHAN

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ABSTRACT: The present study on physico-chemical characteristics of Kinnow fruit in Bikaner district at the farmer's field during 2010 revealed that peel percentage, juice recovery percentage and ascorbic acid content, total soluble solids were acceptable, whereas other quality attributes needed to be improved by regulating orchard management practices such as recommended doses of manures and fertilizers as well as foliar application of micronutrients etc. The bearing Kinnow trees of 10 years age are required to be fertilized by application of Single Super Phosphate (1.5 kg/tree), Muriate of Potash (350 g/tree) and Zinc sulphate (500 g/tree) in the month of January to the soil and by application of 50-60 kg well rotten FYM per tree.

Keywords : Kinnow Mandarin, fruit length, peel thickness. TSS/Acidity ratio

Kinnow (*Citrus nobilis* × *Citrus deliciosa*) is a highly preferred mandarin hybrid in North India. It is very juicy and highly prized for its nutritional value. Kinnow cultivation is becoming very popular among farmers of Bikaner district in Indira Gandhi canal command area of Khajuwala, Chattargarh and many orchards have come up in those areas giving an average yield of 256 q/ha. Bikaner district has approximately 2.81 lac hectare canal irrigated area which has great potential for expanding area under Kinnow cultivation. It is also being grown in the areas irrigated by tube wells of good quality water. Survey was undertaken at the orchards of private fruit growers in Bikaner district during 2010 for assessing fruit quality of Kinnow.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Studies were conducted on 10 year old healthy and vigorously growing uniform trees of Kinnow mandarin budded on Jatti Khatti (*C. jambheri*) rootstock during the year 2010 at orchards of private fruit growers in Bikaner district of Rajasthan state. The fruit samples were collected during ripening time in the month of December. Four orchards were selected for the study and details of locations of the orchards along with name of owners are given in Table 1.

The soil fertility status of Kinnow orchards surveyed are given in Table 2.

At locations Khajuwala 1 and Khajuwala 2, the Kinnow trees received recommended doses of farmyard manure and half of the recommended doses of inorganic fertilizers whereas at Nokha 1 and Chattargarh 1, the Kinnow trees received half of the recommended doses of farmyard manure and 1/4th of

Table 1 : Location of orchards selected.

S. No.	Name of fruit growers	Village/Chak	Location
1.	Rajasthan Go Sewa Sangh	Chattargarh	Chattargarh 1
2.	Sh. Narendra Kiradoo	22KYD, Khajuwala	Khajuwala 1
3.	Sh. Shiv Pratap Verma	14 BD, Khajuwala	Khajuwala 2
4.	Sh. Hanuman Panchariya	Nokha	Nokha 1

the recommended doses of inorganic fertilizers. At none of the locations, foliar applications of micronutrients were made. Plant protection measures were appropriately adopted at all the locations. The source of irrigation was canal water at locations Chattargarh1, Khajuwala 1 and Khajuwala 2 which had pH 8.1, EC 1.06 dSm⁻¹, Na⁺ 7.40 Meq/litre, Ca⁺⁺ + Mg⁺⁺ 5.0 Meq/litre and Cl⁻ 17.50 Meq/litre whereas at Nokha Kinnow orchard received irrigation through tube well which had pH 8.19, EC 0.86 dS m⁻¹, Na⁺ 6.04 Meq/litre, Ca⁺⁺ + Mg⁺⁺ 2.50 Meq/litre and Cl⁻ Meq/litre (Bhatnagar, 4).

For recording observations, 4 fresh fruits were randomly plucked from each experimental tree from all four directions and at each orchard; five trees were randomly selected for assessing the physico-chemical characteristics of fruits. Observations were recorded for fruit weight, fruit length, breadth, circumference, weight of juice vesicles, peel thickness, total number of seeds, segment number, segment size, seed percentage, peel percentage, rag percentage, total soluble solids, total titratable acidity of juice, ascorbic

acid, total sugars and reducing sugars. The per cent was determined by titrating the juice against N/10 NaOH using phenolphthalein as an indicator and has been expressed in terms of citric acid. The total titratable acidity was determined by titration method

different orchards due to variations in soil fertility status as mentioned in Table 1. Fruit weight varied from minimum (146.88g) at the orchard of Khajuwala 1 to maximum (171.47g) at the orchard of Nokha 1. Average weight of kinnow fruits was recorded between

Table 1 : Soil fertility status of Kinnow orchards.

Locations/Soil Properties	Khajuwala 1	Khajuwala2	Nokha 1	Chattargarh 1
Soil pH(1:2)	8.20	8.24	8.56	8.59
EC (1:2) dSm ⁻¹	0.17	0.13	0.38	0.24
O.C.(%)	0.36	0.33	0.31	0.17
Available N (mg kg ⁻¹)	74.40	49.77	46.84	39.29
Available P (mg kg ⁻¹)	24.71	21.13	27.60	8.56
Available K (mg kg ⁻¹)	120.32	115.20	109.59	90.20
Available S (mg kg ⁻¹)	28.65	35.36	14.63	32.14

(A.O.A.C. 1). Total sugar content was determined by using Anthrone reagent method (Dubois *et al.*, 6) and reducing sugar content was measured by Nelsons Modification of 'Somogyis Method' (Somogyi, 17).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The data on physicochemical characteristics of Kinnow fruit are presented in Table 3. The fruit weight of kinnow varied significantly from each other in

112.82g to 170.80 g at Faisalabad, Pakistan by Ahmad *et al.* (2) which is almost similar to the results of present investigations. The size of the kinnow fruits varied significantly in different orchards. The fruit length ranged from 5.38 cm (at the orchards of Khajuwala 2) to 7.36 cm (at the orchard of Nokha 1). Fruit length of kinnow was reported from 6.43 cm to 7.90 cm by Ahmad *et al.* (2) which is almost similar to the present findings. A diameter of 65.68 mm in kinnow fruits has

Table 3: Physico-chemical characteristics of Kinnow fruit.

Locations/Characters	Chattargarh 1	Khajuwala 2	Khajuwala 1	Nokha1	Pooled S.E.(±)	Pooled (%)	C.V
Fruit weight (g)	163.87	147.08	146.88	171.47	5.18	17.66	
Length (cm)	5.80	5.38	5.45	7.36	0.14	13.37	
Breadth (cm)	6.44	6.58	6.72	6.74	0.12	9.84	
Circumference (cm)	20.85	24.29	22.65	24.31	1.55	42.43	
Juice vesicles wt./fruit	116.73	111.88	116.06	131.09	3.80	17.19	
Juice (ml)	67.50	72.87	75.25	81.00	2.02	14.61	
Peel thickness (cm)	0.37	0.33	0.32	0.43	0.09	13.78	
Total seeds (Nos)	40.75	35.50	25.25	43.13	1.53	23.11	
Segment (Nos)	12.62	11.12	10.50	11.95	0.23	10.67	
Seed (%)	2.22	1.85	1.56	2.27	0.07	21.45	
Pee l(%)	23.38	19.28	17.16	24.26	0.69	17.96	
Rags (%)	1.40	1.56	1.19	1.71	0.07	26.43	
Segment (%)	71.52	76.22	79.32	76.47	1.01	7.11	
Juice recovery (%)	41.11	49.60	51.39	47.97	0.94	10.50	
TSS (°Brix)	10.11	10.07	9.56	10.17	0.15	8.32	
Total acidity (%)	1.20	1.44	1.39	0.62	0.06	25.64	
TSS/Acidity ratio	8.42	6.99	6.87	16.40	0.74	44.65	
Ascorbic Acid (mg/100 ml juice)	29.10	27.95	27.88	27.00	0.45	8.55	
Total sugars (%)	8.18	8.12	8.15	8.50	0.05	3.30	
Reducing sugars (%)	4.78	3.97	4.02	5.40	10.13	16.29	

also been reported by Sayyad *et al.* (16). The fruit breadth varied from 6.44 cm (at the orchard of Chattargarh1) to 6.74 cm (at the orchard of Nokha 1) which are in agreement with reports of Monga *et al.* (11) and Sandhu and Randhawa (15). Fruit circumference of the Kinnow fruit varied from minimum (20.85 cm) at the orchard of Chattargarh 1 to maximum (24.31 cm) at the orchard of Nokha 1. the highest juice vesicles weight per fruit (131.09g) was recorded in the fruits of Nokha 1, whereas lowest weight of juice vesicles per fruit (111.88g) was recorded in the fruits of Khajuwala 2.

Peel thickness varied from 0.32 cm (at the orchard of Khajuwala 1) to 0.43 cm (at the orchard of Nokha1). Seed percentage in Kinnow fruits varied from 1.56 per cent (at the orchard of Khajuwala 1) to 2.27 per cent (at the orchard of Nokha 1).

Peel percentage varied from 17.16 per cent (at the orchard of Khajuwala 1) to 24.26 per cent (at the orchard of Nokha 1). Peel percentage of Kinnow fruits was also reported between 27.10 to 31.24 per cent by Sandhu and Randhawa (15) and 26.6 to 29.7 per cent by Josan *et al.* (9) at Punjab. Less peel percentage obtained under present investigation suggests better fruit quality on the basis of it as reported by Davies and Albrigo (5).

The juice recovery percentage of Kinnow fruits ranged from 41.11 per cent (at the orchard of Chattargarh 1) to 51.39 per cent (at the orchard of Khajuwala 1) which are in close confirmity with Ahmad *et al.* (3) who reported 46.3% juice recovery in Kinnow fruits. Total number of seeds varied from 25.25 (at the orchard of Khajuwala 1) to 43.12 (at the orchard of Nokha 1). Likewise, Ahmad *et al.* (3) also reported that total number of seeds in Kinnow fruits varied from 26.12 to 29.12 which are in conformity to the results of present findings.

The total soluble solids content in Kinnow fruits varied from 9.56° brix (at the orchard of Khajuwala 1) to 10.17° brix (at the orchard of Nokha 1). Average total soluble solids content in Kinnow (11.86° brix) was also reported by Khan *et al.* (10) under semi arid plains. The lower amount of total soluble solids in arid irrigated plains of Rajasthan might be due to higher temperature at the time of fruit ripening thus facilitating early maturity of fruits.

The total titratable acidity percentage varied from 0.62 per cent (at the orchard of Nokha 1) to 1.44 per cent (at the orchard of Khajuwala 2). It has been reported from 0.8 to 1.7 per cent by Sandhu and Randhawa (15); 0.83 to 1.21 per cent by Josan *et al.*

(9) and 0.91 to 1.27 per cent by Dhillon *et al.* (7) in Punjab which are in close agreement to the results of present findings.

The TSS/Acidity ratio varied from 6.87:1 (at the orchard of Khajuwala 1) to 16.40:1 (at the orchard of Nokha1). , TSS/Acidity ratio of 12:1 to 14:1 Jawanda *et al.* (8) is considered to be optimum for Kinnow fruits at the time of full maturity under semi arid conditions, whereas varied TSS/Acidity ratio of 11:1 Mehta and Bajaj (11); 11.01:1 (Monga *et al.*, (12); 8.41:1 to 10.61:1 (Sandhu and Randhawa, (15); and 8.7:1 to 14.5:1 by Josan *et al.* (9) are also in close accordance with the findings of present investigations.

Ascorbic acid content ranged from 27.00 mg/100 ml juice (at the orchard of Nokha1) to 29.10 mg/100 ml juice (at the orchard of Chhatargarh 1). Differences in ascorbic acid content in Kinnow fruits as 24.5 mg/100 ml (Mehta and Bajaj, 11); 22.90 to 27.60 mg/100 ml. Sandhu and Randhawa (15); 23.6 to 30.4 mg/100 ml. (Dhillon *et al.*, 7) had also been reported.

The total sugar percentage varied from 8.12 per cent (at the orchard of Khajuwala 2) to 8.50 per cent (at the orchard of Nokha 1). Average total sugar percentage of Kinnow fruits from 4.8 to 5.6 per cent reported by Khan *et al.* (10) are in support of present findings. The reducing sugar percentage varied from 3.97 per cent (at Khajuwala 2) to 5.4 per cent (at Nokha1). Similarly, 3.20% and 4.90% reducing sugars in kinnow fruits had also been reported by Sandhu *et al.* (14) and Premi *et al.* (13), respectively which are in line of present results.

Conclusion

The present study harnesses the underestimated potential of Kinnow mandarin under arid irrigated tracts of Bikaner district and fruits of excellent quality can be produced with good quality canal water incorporated with sufficient quantities of organic matter coupled with inorganic fertilizers as well as foliar feeding of micronutrients to which the sandy soils response very quickly.

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FLOWER AND BULB PRODUCTION OF TUBEROSE (*Polianthes tuberosa* L.) AS INFLUENCED BY DIFFERENT SOURCES OF NUTRIENTS

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ABSTRACT : The present investigation on flower and bulb production of tuberose (*Polianthes tuberosa* L.) cv. Vaibhav as influenced by different sources of nutrients was carried out at Horticultural Research Centre (HRC) of SVPUAT, Meerut during the year 2013-14. The experiment consisted of ten treatments, viz. T₁: control (without NPK), T₂ : 100% RDF (160:80:80), T₃: 75% RDF + 25% Neem Cake, T₄: 75% RDF + 25% Neem Cake+ 2.0 g/plant *Azospirillum* + 2.0g/plant PSB, T₅: 75% RDF + 25% VC, T₆: 75% RDF + 25% VC + 2.0 g/plant *Azospirillum* + 2g/plant PSB, T₇: 50% RDF + 50% Neem Cake, T₈: 50% RDF +50% Neem Cake + 2.0 g/plant *Azospirillum* + 2g/plant PSB, T₉: 50% RDF + 50% VC T₁₀: 50% RDF + 50% VC + 2.0 g/plant *Azospirillum* + 2g/plant PSB. Results revealed that the 50% reduced doses of inorganic fertilizers which was supplemented by organic and bio fertilizers using in treatment T₁₀ (50% RDF+ 50% VC + 2.0 g/plant *Azospirillum* + 2.0 g/plant PSB), produced maximum diameter of flower, number of florets per spike, diameter of spike and number of spikes per corm, while treatment T₆ resulted maximum length of spike, rachis length and number of corms per plant. The treatment receiving 50% RDF+ 50% VC + 2.0 g/plant *Azospirillum* + 2.0 g/plant PSB significantly resulted in maximum values for number of bulblets, diameter of bulb, weight of bulb and yield of bulbs and bulblets per plant.

Keywords : Tuberose, nutrients, flowering, bulb production.

Flowers are good carrier for emotions of mankind. Human uses flowers at the time of any joyful function and also in sorrowful situation to express their feelings. Among the ornamental bulbous plants, tuberose is one of the most important commercial flower crop in India. It belongs to the family Amaryllidaceae. The spikes of tuberose are mainly used for garden, interior decoration, garland, essential oil and for making bouquets. It has great market value during the festivals like Diwali, Holi, New Year, Charismas and also on marriage ceremony. Tuberose flowers are also used to decorate house, office etc, to complete ceremony to purpose friendship, and marriage as well as for making perfumes, medicines, essential oil and cosmetics etc. It has been observed that flowers create an incentive, pleasing, colourful and fragrant atmosphere to mankind.

In tuberose, farmers generally apply inorganic fertilizers for increasing flower and bulb production. Often, they do not apply micronutrients which can be easily available through application of organic manures. Some educated farmers use both organic manures and inorganic fertilizers but unfortunately they are applying these fertilizers in inadequate combinations. Therefore, the soils remain deficient in micronutrients. Plants require both organic manures and inorganic fertilizers in an adequate combination to produce better output. Tuberose also requires macro

and micro nutrients in an adequate combination. Tuberose cultivar "Vaibhav" is one of the promising cultivars of India. The cultivar produces very attractive spikes and the flowering spike of the cultivar is in great demand in Indian flower markets. Therefore, the present study was carried out to find out the optimum doses of integrated sources of nutrients for flower and bulb production in tuberose.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The experiment was conducted at Horticultural Research Centre (HRC) of Sardar Vallabhbhai Patel University of Agriculture and Technology, Meerut (U.P.) during Rabi season, 2013-14. The University is situated 8.0 km away from Meerut city in the Western Uttar Pradesh. Geographically, Meerut is located at 29.01° north latitude, 77.75° east longitude and at an altitude of 297 m above the mean sea level. The soil of the field had (155.40 kg/ha alkaline permanganate oxidizable nitrogen (Subbaiah and Asija, 10), 14.76 kg/ha available phosphorus (Olsen *et al.*, 6), 139.86 kg/ha⁻¹ N ammonium acetate exchangeable potassium (Hanway and Heidal, 2) and 0.45% organic carbon (Walkley and Black, 12). The pH of the soil (7.6) was measured by Beckman's glass electrode pH meter method (Jackson, 3). The experiment was laid out in a simple randomized block design with 10 treatments and three replications. Well decomposed farmyard manure, vermin compost, *Azospirillum* and PSB were

applied treatment-wise before planting. Recommended fertilizer doses of 180:80:80 kg/ha NPK were also given treatment-wise as 100, 75 and 50%. These fertilizers were applied in the form of urea, single superphosphate and muriate of potash. Uniform size of tuberose bulbs (3.0 to 4.0 cm) of cv. Vaibhav were planted on 15th March, 2013. The row to row distance of 30 cm and plant to plant distance of 20 cm in a plot size of 3.0 × 2.0 m was maintained. The treatments imposed were : T₁: control (without NPK), T₂ : 100% RDF (160:80:80), T₃: 75% RDF + 25% Neem Cake, T₄: 75% RDF + 25% Neem Cake+ 2.0 g/plant *Azospirillum* + 2.0g/plant + 2g/plant PSB, T₅ : 75% RDF + 25% VC, T₆ : 75% RDF + 25% VC + 2.0 g/plant *Azospirillum* + 2g/plant PSB, T₇ : 50% RDF + 50% Neem Cake, T₈ : 50% RDF +50% Neem Cake + 2.0 g/plant *Azospirillum* + 2g/plant PSB, T₉ : 50% RDF + 50% VC, and T₁₀: 50% RDF + 50% VC + 2.0 g/plant *Azospirillum* + 2g/plant PSB. The observations on various growth and flowering aspects were recorded and analyzed statistically.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

It is clear from the Table 1 that all the characters under present investigation were significantly influenced by different treatment combinations. Treatment combination of T₁₀, (50% RDF + 50% VC + 2g/plant *Azospirillum* + 2.0 g/ plant PSB) significantly showed maximum diameter of flower (93.10 cm) followed by T₆ (3.05 cm) and minimum diameter of flower (2.17 cm) was observed in control. Significantly maximum number of florets per spike (52.33) was observed in treatment T₁₀ when plants received 50% RDF + 50% VC + 2.0 g/plant *Azospirillum* + 2g/plant PSB, and minimum number of florets (36.98 florets/spike) was recorded in control. The similar results were obtained by Moghadam and Shoor (4) who mentioned that the treatment receiving *Azospirillum* sp. + Phosphate solubilizing bacterium + Vermicompost + NPK (25% of recommended dose) improved the flower quality and increased the flower yield of *Petunia hybrida*. Further, significant influence of different combinations of reduced doses of inorganic fertilizers along with organic fertilizers on flower characters of tuberose was observed. The quantity of different sources of nutrients among the treatments also showed significant variations in number of spikes per bulb. Treatment T₁₀ (50% RDF + 50% VC + 2g/plant *Azospirillum* + 2.0 g/ plant PSB) significantly produced maximum number of spikes/plant (1.69) over control (0.92 spikes) and RDF (1.31 spikes). The similar results were also reported by Wange and Patil (13) in tuberose. This might be due to combined effect

of bio fertilizers and vermin compost, on nutrient availability and absorption, besides release of growth promoting substances like IAA and GA, which promotes the crop growth by enhanced cell division and enlargement, leading to proper shoot and root growth that ultimately favours of maximum number of spikes and increased size of spikes. Results are in consonance with the findings of Pathak (7) and Singh *et al.* (8). The plants receiving 25% reduced doses of inorganic fertilizers in treatment T₆ significantly exhibited maximum length of spike (102.49 cm) which was at par with T₁₀ and T₂, while it was minimum in control. Length of rachis was also influenced by different sources of nutrients which was maximum (56.42 cm) in treatment T₆ over control (41.94 cm) and RDF (52.48cm), respectively. The increase in spike and rachis length might be due to the abundant availability of nutrition and elevated levels of macronutrients which have positive effect on floral characteristics. Swaminathan *et al.* (11) had also observed higher spike length by combined application of inorganics, PSB and *Azospirillum*. The conjunctive effect of vermin compost and bio-fertilizers with 25 per cent reduced doses of chemical fertilizers in terms of increasing the diameter of spike was also found to be significant though it varied among treatments in the present investigation.

A perusal of data (Tables 1) revealed that all the bulb's characteristics of tuberose were significantly affected by different sources of nutrients. The plants receiving 25% reduced doses of inorganic fertilizers (T₆) significantly produced maximum number of bulbs per plant (9.77) being at par with the treatment T₁₀ and it was minimum (4.33 bulbs) in control. Present findings are in consonance with Singh (8). Bulblets were also shown significant variations among the treatments and it varied from 27.27- 45.41. Plants receiving 50% reduced doses of inorganic fertilizers (T₁₀) produced maximum number of bulblets per plant (45.41) which was statistically at par with T₆ over control and RDF, respectively. The diameter of bulb found was maximum (6.40 cm) when plants were treated with 50% RDF + 50% VC + 2.0 g/plant *Azospirillum* + 2.0/plant PSB (T₁₀) and minimum diameter of bulb (2.80 cm) was observed under control. Again, treatment T₁₀ significantly produced maximum weight of bulb (44.08 g) being at par with the bulb produced under plants received 25% reduced doses of inorganic fertilizer (T₆) and it was minimum when plants were grown without any fertilizer (control). The total yield of bulbs and bulblets ranged from 188.72-422.15g/plant and it was maximum (422.15g/plant)

Table 1: Flower and bulb production of tuberose (*Polianthes tuberosa* L.) cv. Vaibhav as influenced by different sources of nutrients.

Treatments	Diameter of flower (cm)	No. of florets / spike	Diameter of spike (cm)	No. of spike /bulb	Length of spike (cm)	Length of rachis (cm)	No. of bulbs/plant	No. of bulblets /plant	Diameter of bulb (cm)	Weight of bulb (g)	Yield of bulbs & bulblets (g)
T ₁ -Control (without NPK)	2.17	36.98	1.75	0.92	82.23	41.94	4.33	27.27	2.80	26.07	188.72
T ₂ -100% RDF(160:80:80)	2.86	50.43	2.03	1.31	101.87	52.48	9.30	42.65	5.97	41.30	385.25
T ₃ -75% RDF + 25% Neem Cake	2.51	44.93	1.94	1.17	92.91	44.00	5.80	29.53	3.30	32.15	205.74
T ₄ -75% RDF + 25% Neem Cake+ 2.0 g/plant <i>Azospirillum</i> + 2.0g/plant + 2g/plant PSB	2.43	44.15	1.87	1.19	93.91	44.28	6.18	34.30	3.60	33.51	207.73
T ₅ -75% RDF + 25% VC	2.53	43.73	1.87	1.18	94.92	45.43	7.20	34.99	3.92	35.67	257.04
T ₆ -75% RDF + 25% VC + 2.0 g/plant <i>Azospirillum</i> + 2g/plant PSB	3.05	51.87	1.94	1.55	102.49	56.42	9.77	43.53	6.12	42.55	415.22
T ₇ -50% RDF + 50% Neem Cake	2.19	46.13	2.22	1.29	94.17	47.99	5.90	30.08	3.88	33.20	196.01
T ₈ -50% RDF +50% Neem Cake + 2.0 g/plant <i>Azospirillum</i> + 2g/plant PSB	2.22	47.49	1.91	1.19	95.98	48.93	6.37	33.57	4.33	34.91	223.42
T ₉ -50% RDF + 50% VC	2.47	48.62	1.99	1.33	97.33	51.16	7.48	36.95	4.83	36.46	272.72
T ₁₀ -50% RDF+ 50% VC+ 2.0g/plant <i>Azospirillum</i> +2.0g/plant PSB	3.10	52.33	2.27	1.69	101.40	52.43	9.58	45.41	6.4	44.08	422.15

under the treatment T₁₀ being at par with T₆, while it was observed minimum under control. A marked increase in both number of bulbs and bulblets per plant and weight may be attributed to better availability of phosphorous, which is required in particularly for corm growth. Higher bulblets production might be due to bulbs inoculated with bio fertilizers had stored more carbohydrates through effective photosynthesis. The increase in bulbs weight might be due to storage of carbohydrates and nitrogen compounds in the bulbs. The carbohydrates and soluble nitrogen compounds translocates from leaves to bulbs. Bulbs act as sink source for storage of food as reported by Nazki and Arora (5). These results are also in close conformity with the findings of Ali *et al.* (1).

Conclusion

Based on the results obtained from the present study, it may be concluded that combined applications of organic and inorganic fertilizers was found to be most effective in the improving the flowering and bulb yield of tuberose cv. 'Vaibhav' under the agro climatic conditions of Western Uttar Pradesh.

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PERFORMANCE OF POPLAR CUTTINGS WITH DIFFERENT GROWTH REGULATORS AND POTTING MEDIA

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ABSTRACT : The study was conducted on performance of poplar cuttings with different growth regulators and potting media in the Forest Nursery and Research Centre of SHIATS, Allahabad. The experiment was laid out in RBD with four replications. There were six treatments of growth regulators, viz. T₁-Control (distilled water), T₂- IBA(100 ppm), T₃- IAA (100 ppm), T₄- NAA (100 ppm), T₅-GA₃ (100 ppm), T₆-2,4-D (100 ppm), and seven treatments of potting media, viz. M₁-Soil only, M₂-Soil + Sand + FYM (1:1:1), M₃- Soil + FYM + Neem cake (1:1:1), M₄- Soil + FYM + VC (1:1:1), M₅- Neem cake + sand + VC (1:1:1), M₆- Neem Cake + Soil + VC (1:1:1) and M₇- Neem cake + FYM + VC (1:1:1). Ten cuttings per replication were used for each treatment. Among different growth regulators used, IAA @100 ppm showed maximum survival percentage (80.00%), shoot and root length ((35.30cm and 32.55cm, respectively), fresh shoot weight (20.00g), and fresh and dry weight of roots (13.00g and 6.47g, respectively), as well as total biomass (12.82g) compared to control and other treatments. Number of sprouts and no. of roots/cutting (2.25 and 27.00, respectively) and dry weight of shoot (6.70g) were found maximum with 100ppm IBA, while maximum root: shoot ratio of 1.15 was produced by 100 GA₃. Among potting media combinations, most effective treatment was M₂ (Soil + Sand+ FYM, 1:1:1) which resulted in maximum number of sprouts/cutting (2.55), survival percentage (63.33%), shoot length (24.45 cm), dry weight of shoot (5.17g) and fresh weight of root (10.17g) over other treatments. Length of root (22.0cm), dry weight of roots (6.22g), root: shoot ratio (1.71) and total biomass (11.02g) were maximum in M₇ (Neem cake + FYM + VC, 1:1:1).

Keywords : Vermicompost, potting media, growth regulators, clone, poplar.

Poplar (*Populus deltoides*), belongs to the family Salicaceae, is a very important group of tree species in plantation forestry because it is a deciduous fast growing multipurpose tree species and can be harvested at a short rotation of 7-8 years (Chaturvedi, 4). The tree is deciduous which remains leafless from 3 - 4 months during winter and produces straight and clean bole in very short duration (Singh, 12) The best time of planting poplar cuttings is January to February (Lal, 6), February to March (Mishra and Gupta, 9) and middle of February to middle of March (Chandra, 3).

Populus deltoides is the most widely planted species of poplar in India. It is planted in the plains of North West India i.e., Western Uttar Pradesh, Punjab and Haryana and to some extent in outer plains/valleys of Uttarakhand, Himachal Pradesh and J & K. It has been successfully cultivated as a forest crop and/or agro-forestry crop in Punjab plains and in Tarai region of U.P. Poplars have been raised at slightly lower latitudes also, but it is only above 29°N that they had fair success in experimental plantations and on farms timber is used principally for lumber, veneer, pulpwood, excelsior and fuel (Laver, 7). Widely used for shelter

belt, windbreak and amenity plantings. Recently, it has been championed as one of the leading potential species for silviculture biomass production. Salicylic acid, derivable from this species, is used as a coupling agent in dye intermediates (Behan, 2).

Vegetative propagation of trees is a tool and its domestication has a long history. The rate of multiplication through cuttings is higher than for any other vegetative propagation technique, with the exception of micro-propagation. Propagation of poplars by stem cuttings is the easiest way for selection of new clones (Singh, 12). The nursery plants raised from cuttings are taken from one year old nursery growth. The ability of cuttings to root and their subsequent growth in nursery is determined by number of factors viz; time at which cuttings are taken, age of the donor tree, position within the crown from where cuttings are taken, treatment and status of rooting/growth hormones and conditions under which cuttings are rooted (Puri, 10). The time of the year in which cuttings are taken can have a dramatic influence on rooting of cuttings and may provide the key to highly successful rooting (Hartmann and Kester, 5).

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The study was conducted in the Forest Nursery of Allahabad Agricultural Institute (SHIATS) situated at 25.28°N latitude and 81.55°E longitude. The area is situated at an altitude of 98 m above average mean sea level and enjoys sub-tropical type of climate.

(A) Method of solution and treatments

The size of cuttings was 5 to 6 inches long, having 2 to 3 buds with the slanting basal cut. Cuttings of *Populus deltoides* were soaked in growth regulators for 24 hours before planting. The prepared cuttings were treated by dipping their basal 3.5 cm portions in solutions of IBA, IAA, NAA, GA₃ and 2,4-D@100ppm each and distilled water (control) for 24 hours at room temperature (20±1°C). Treated cuttings were planted in beds made by mixing soil and sand. The experiment was laid out in Randomized Block Design with 6 treatments each replicated 4 times. In each replication, 10 cuttings were raised accordingly.

(b) Preparation of propagating media

The cuttings were planted in plastic bags having propagation media viz., M₁-Soil only, M₂-Soil + Sand + FYM (1 : 1 : 1), M₃- Soil + FYM + Neem cake (1 : 1 : 1), M₄- Soil + FYM + VC (1 : 1 : 1), M₅- Neem cake+ sand+ VC (1 : 1 : 1), M₆- Neem Cake+Soil+VC (1:1:1) and M₇- Neem cake+FYM+VC (1:1:1). After planting in plastic bags, full irrigation was given with a sprinkler to protect them from desiccation. The experiment was laid out in Randomized Block Design with 7 treatments

each replicated 4 times. In each replication, 10 cuttings were raised accordingly.

Data on growth, sprouting and survival of poplar cuttings were recorded periodically (Table 1 and 2) and analyzed statistically.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Effect of different growth regulators

A perusal of Table 1 revealed that cuttings treated with 100ppm IBA (T₂) performed best for maximum number of sprouts/cutting (2.25), number of roots (27.00) and dry weight of shoot (6.70 g) followed by 100ppm IAA as compared to other treatments. Survival per cent (80%), shoot and root length (35.30 and 32.55 cm, respectively) fresh weight of shoot and roots (20g and 13 g, respectively), dry weight of roots (6.47g) and total biomass (12.82g) were found maximum in cuttings treated with 100ppm IAA as compared to other treatments. The root: shoot ratio was maximum (1.15) in 100ppm GA₃ treated ones followed by 100 ppm NAA (1.11).

Efficacy of different potting media

The maximum sprouts/cutting (2.55), survival per cent (63.33%), dry weight of shoot (5.17g) as well as fresh weight of roots (10.17g) were significantly maximum in cuttings planted in mixture of soil + sand + FYM in ratio of 1 : 1 : 1 (M₂). Number of roots/cutting was observed maximum (15.57) in cuttings planted in M₆ (Soil + Vermicompost + Neem cake, 1 : 1 : 1) followed by M₂ (13.67 roots). It might be due to that

Table 1: Effect of different growth regulator on poplar cuttings.

Treatments Parameters	T ₁ (Control)	T ₂ (100ppmIBA)	T ₃ (100ppmIAA)	T ₄ (100ppmNAA)	T ₅ (100ppmGA ₃)	T ₆ (100ppm 2,4-D)
Survival %	30.00	67.50	80.00	55.00	77.50	65.00
No. of sprouts/cutting	1.81	2.25	2.06	2.00	1.93	2.00
Shoot length (cm)	20.10	32.82	35.30	31.52	30.92	26.33
No. of roots/cutting	8.81	27.00	21.39	19.56	19.35	17.96
Root length (cm)	15.78	29.45	32.55	22.60	23.69	21.18
Fresh wt. of shoot (g)	8.25	16.50	20.00	13.50	9.31	12.42
Dry wt. of shoot (g)	3.39	6.70	6.60	5.05	3.76	4.72
Fresh wt. of root (g)	5.31	12.58	13.00	9.69	7.75	7.25
Dry wt. of root (g)	3.44	5.88	6.47	3.75	4.23	3.80
Root : shoot ratio	0.84	0.87	0.96	1.11	1.15	0.98
Total biomass (g)	7.14	12.63	12.82	9.28	7.21	8.51

Table 2: Evaluation of efficacy of different potting media on poplar cuttings.

Treatments	M ₁	M ₂	M ₃	M ₄	M ₅	M ₆	M ₇
Survival %	13.33	63.33	16.67	33.33	20.00	53.33	23.33
No. of sprouts/cutting	1.77	2.55	2.22	2.33	1.89	1.89	2.44
Shoot length (cm)	18.33	24.45	22.35	23.20	17.53	21.85	19.80
No. of roots/cutting	6.85	13.67	12.73	9.14	10.23	15.57	7.83
Root length (cm)	16.72	17.15	18.52	21.44	19.90	17.17	22.00
Fresh wt. of shoot (g)	8.53	13.08	14.12	10.83	10.50	11.55	10.83
Dry wt. of shoot (g)	4.32	5.17	4.40	4.40	4.98	4.34	4.63
Fresh wt. of root (g)	7.58	10.17	10.08	8.94	9.55	9.07	8.42
Dry wt. of root (g)	4.17	4.57	5.33	4.57	4.66	5.18	6.22
Root : shoot ratio	0.94	1.47	0.96	1.05	0.99	1.56	1.71
Total biomass (g)	8.80	9.73	9.50	8.97	9.64	9.50	11.02

*M₁–Soil only, M₂–Soil + Sand + FYM, M₃–Soil + FYM + Neemcake, M₄–Soil + FYM + vermicompost, M₅–Neem cake + Sand + VC, M₆–Neem cake + Soil + VC, M₇–Neem cake + FYM + VC.

decomposed organic material improves soil fertility by increasing soil aeration, water holding capacity and water infiltration at lower surface (Mathad and Nalwadi, 8). Similarly, the poorest performance of rooted cuttings in control may be due to nutritionally poor medium, lacking in organic material that resulted in minimum survival, thereby reducing the plant survival and growth.

After 120 days of planting, the maximum root length of 22.0 cm, dry weight of roots (6.22g) and maximum root: shoot ratio (1.71) and biomass (11.02g) were observed in cuttings planted in Vermicompost + FYM + Neem cake (M₇). Ahmad and Qasim (1) and Rahman and Ishtiaq (11) had also found that potting media containing FYM, poultry manure as main source of organic matter with sand, silt and saw dust were better than sole factor of soil itself, as these combinations presented more growth and vigour of the plants improving total available nitrogen and phosphorus.

In the view of above findings, the most effective growth regulator was IAA @100ppm) which gave better results with survival percentage, number of roots, shoot and root length, shoot and root fresh weight, root dry weight and total biomass compared to control and other treatments.

Among all potting media combinations, the most effective medium was Soil + Sand + FYM (1 : 1 : 1)

which showed better results in number of sprouts/cutting, survival percentage, shoot length, shoot dry weight and root fresh weight as compared to control or other treatments.

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POST HARVEST FLOWERING BEHAVIOUR OF SOME GLADIOLUS VARIETIES GROWN UNDER FAIZABAD CLIMATIC CONDITION

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ABSTRACT : The study was conducted to find out post harvest flowering behavior of some gladiolus varieties grown under Faizabad conditions. Results revealed that the per cent increase in spike length in vase was maximum in Red Sparkle at 4th and 8th day, and it was minimum in White Prosperity. Per cent opening of florets was maximum in Day Dreams at 4th and 8th day. Day Dreams also exhibited no floret dropping at 4th day. The longest vase life was found in Aldebaran, while Day Dreams exhibited shortest vase life.

Keywords : *Gladiolus, cut flower, post harvest behaviour, floret dropping, vase life.*

Commercial floriculture is one of the most profitable agro industries in the world (Ezhimathi *et al.*, 1). Decrease in cut flowers' quality from harvesting to market is a great problem for growers. Perishability of flowers make their physiological functions very actively even after harvest. Preference of varieties depends upon the post harvest flowering behaviour of flowers (Faraji *et al.*, 2). Gladiolus is a widely grown flower crop and mostly used in all purposes. In case of gladiolus flower increase in spike length, opening of florets, dropping of florets after senescence, volume of water uptake, and total sugar content affect the vase life of spikes. It vary from variety to variety. Idea about evaluation of varieties on the basis of their postharvest characteristics will give a brief idea about preference of variety by consumers which will be profitable for gladiolus growers under the conditions of Faizabad districts of Uttar Pradesh.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Total 11 varieties of gladiolus viz. V₁-Wine and Roses, V₂-Interpit Bicolor, V₃-Red Sparkle, V₃-Puppy Dear, V₅-White Prosperity, V₆-Pacific White, V₇-Seventh Wonder, V₈-Norallow Bicolor, V₉-Aldebaran, V₁₀- Day Dreams and V₁₁-Red Beauty were chosen for experiment. All the readings on per cent increase in spike length, opening and dropping of florets, and vase life as well as volume of water uptake and total carbohydrate content were taken on 4th day, 8th day and 12th day. 500 ml 4% sucrose solution was taken as vase solution which is standard for gladiolus cut flower. Volume of water uptake was measured by: Final weight – initial weight of flask with solution with spike. For estimation of total carbohydrate content, 0.25g chopped perianth tissue fixed in ethanol macerated and centrifuged (3500X 10 min)

supernatant used for carbohydrate estimation by Paquan and Lechacer (4).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Data illustrated in Fig. 1, 2 and 3 revealed that per cent increase in spike length was maximum on 4th and 8th day in Red Sparkle and minimum in White Prosperity. There was no increase in spike length on 12th day. Per cent increase in opening of florets was found maximum on 4th and 8th day in Day Dreams, on 12th day: Aldebaran and minimum on 4th day in Wine and Roses, 12th day in Norallow Bicolor and on 12th day in White Prosperity. Drooping of florets was nil on 4th day, maximum on 8th and 12th day in Day Dreams and minimum on 8th day in Red Sparkle, Aldebaran, Red Beauty, Puppy Dear, on 12th day in Aldebaran and Pacific White. Vase life was longest in Aldebaran followed by Pacific White, which might be due to highest total carbohydrate content in case of Aldebaran followed by Pacific White. While Day Dreams exhibited the shortest vase life which might be due to lowest amount of total carbohydrate content and highest uptake of sucrose solution (Yadav, 5). Volume of water consumed was maximum on 4th and 8th day in Day Dreams, on 12th day in Wine and Roses, while it was minimum on 4th day, 8th day and 12th day in Seventh Wonder. Total carbohydrate content was maximum on 4th, 8th and 12th day in Aldebaran while minimum on 4th, 8th and 12th day in Day Dreams. Reduction in carbohydrate content after first day can be due to the increase in the respiration rate (Macnish *et al.*, 3). Per cent increase in opening of florets in earlier days (4th and 8th day) was maximum Aldebaran. Dropping of florets also was lowest on 4th day in Aldebaran.

Fig. 3 : Per cent increase in spike length and opening of florets of gladiolus cut flowers in vase.

Fig. 2 : Per cent increase in water consumed and dropping of florets of gladiolus cut flower in vase.

Fig. 3 : Per cent increase in vase life and total carbohydrate content in gladiolus cut flower in vase.

Conclusion

Longest vase life is exhibited by Aldebaran followed by Pacific White. Average performances of Aldebaran variety with respect to per cent opening of florets, dropping of florets at a specific time which are important in preference of gladiolus variety for postharvest life lead to the recommendation of this variety to grow under arid climate of Faizabad district of Uttar Pradesh.

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EFFECT OF SOWING TIME AND SPACING ON THE PERFORMANCE OF CAPE GOOSEBERRY (*Physalis peruviana* L.) IN CENTRAL UTTAR PRADESH

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ABSTRACT : Study on the effect of sowing time and spacing on the performance of Cape gooseberry (*Physalis peruviana* L.) in central Uttar Pradesh was conducted at Horticulture Research Farm, BBA University, Lucknow, India during 2011-12. The experiment was laid out in split plot design with three dates of sowing [D₁ (3 Nov., 2011), D₂ (8 Nov., 2011) and D₃ (13 Nov., 2011)] and four spacing [S₁ (35x90cm), S₂ (40 x 90cm), S₃ (45x90 cm) and S₄ (50x90 cm)] and was replicated thrice. Results revealed that maximum plant height (54.25 cm.), number of leaves/plant (60.50), number of internodes (11.50), diameter of stem (5.65 cm), number of branches/plant (7.88), number of flowers/plant (4.66) and number of fruits (5.55) were obtained at first date of sowing i.e., D₁ (3 Nov., 2011). The spacing of 40 × 90 gave significantly maximum plant height, number of internodes, diameter of stem, number of branches, number of flowers and number of fruits. The treatment D₁S₂ (3 Nov. sowing with 45 x 90 cm spacing) was found to be the best for proper growth and development of the plant and fruiting performance of cape gooseberry.

Keywords : Cape gooseberry, spacing, sowing time.

Cape gooseberry (*Physalis peruviana* L.), a member of family Solanaceae, is an Andean herbaceous crop growing erect up to one meter in height (which may occasionally attain 1.8 m height) grown for its edible fruits. It is an underexploited crop usually cultivated as an annual, but in the absence of frost it can be a perennial (Legge, 1). Fruits are yellow-orange berries (1 to 3.5cm diameter), very juicy, aromatic, with a characteristic bitter-sweet flavour. They are enclosed by the ascent epicalyxes, which give them the shape of a bladder (Morton, 3). Successful cultivation of any crop depends upon several factors viz. date of sowing, plant spacing and other cultivation practices. Optimum plant spacing ensures proper growth and development of plant resulting in maximum yield and economic use of land. However, there are no reports regarding optimum sowing date and spacing for the successful cultivation of Cape gooseberry, especially under the agro climatic condition of Central Uttar Pradesh. The present investigation was thus designed to find out the most suitable sowing 'time' and spacing to achieve higher yield and quality fruits in Cape gooseberry.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The present investigation was carried out during 2011-12 at the Horticulture Research Farm of the Department of Applied Plant Science (Horticulture), Babasaheb Bhimrao Ambedkar University, Lucknow. The experiment was laid out in split plot design with

three dates of sowing viz., D₁ (3 Nov., 2011), D₂ (8 Nov., 2011) and D₃ (13 Nov., 2011) in combination with four spacings viz., S₁- (35 × 90cm), S₂- (40 × 90cm), S₃- (45 × 90 cm) and S₄- (50 × 90 cm). Each combination replicated thrice. Seeds were procured from local reliable sources and 200 seeds were sown in seedling trays (sand: soil, 1: 2, respectively) at different dates (D) as per details given above. Transplanting of seedlings having different vigour and height (according to date of sowing) were carried out in well prepared plots. Transplanting was done in the evening hours and irrigation was done immediately after transplanting. Intercultural operation, irrigation and plant protection measures were adopted as per standard practices. The observations were recorded manually on number of leaves per plant, number of branches per plant, number of internodes per plant, plant height (cm) using a meter scale, stem diameter (cm) using digital vernier calipers (Mitutoyo, Japan) and number of flowers and number of fruits per plant. Average data was analyzed statistically by following procedure of Panse and Sukhatme (4).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Under the present study it was observed that the first date of sowing was found to be significantly better for the vegetative growth (Table 1) as well as flowering and fruiting (Table 2) as compared to other dates of sowing. However, spacing did not have any significant effect on the same. It was observed that treatment

Table 1 : Effect of date of sowing and plant spacing on performance of Cape gooseberry.

Treatments	Plant height (cm) 60 DAT	No. of leaves /plant 60 DAT	No. of internodes / plant 60 DAT	No. of branches/ plant 60 DAT	Stem diameter (cm) 60 DAT	Flowering 60 DAT	No. of fruits/ plant 60 DAT
D ₁ S ₁	51.5	52.05	11.5	7.77	5.43	4.21	3
D ₁ S ₂	54.25	60.5	10.75	7.88	5.5	3.99	5.55
D ₁ S ₃	49.5	59.52	10.77	7.55	5.65	4.66	4
D ₁ S ₄	53.55	59.08	10.45	6.55	5.35	3.33	3.55
D ₂ S ₁	42.5	52.15	9.95	6.33	4.95	2.22	0.77
D ₂ S ₂	40.15	51.65	9.75	6.77	5.1	3.11	0.11
D ₂ S ₃	38	50.29	9.67	7.55	5.05	2.99	0.11
D ₂ S ₄	36.18	50.05	9.25	5.77	4.85	2.88	0
D ₃ S ₁	29.15	42.25	7.73	6.22	4.8	2.33	0
D ₃ S ₂	28.5	40.67	8.1	6.22	4.5	2.66	0
D ₃ S ₃	32.8	46.25	8.15	5.88	4.55	2.44	0.22
D ₃ S ₄	33.15	54.5	9.3	5.77	4.75	2.44	0
CD (P=0.05)							
D	1.07	0.66	0.48	0.11	0.07	0.15	0.67
S	2.04	1.46	1.28	0.26	0.13	0.26	0.57
D × S	3.54	2.52	2.22	0.49	0.23	0.46	0.99

*Sowing dates: 3rd November (D₁), 8th Nov. (D₂) and 13th Nov. (D₃).

*Plant Spacing: 35 × 90 cm (S₁), 40 × 90 cm (S₂), 45 × 90 cm (S₃) and 50 × 90 cm (S₄).

combination D₁S₂ (3 Nov., 2011 sowing with 40x90 cm spacing) performed best as compared to other treatments. The plant height was recorded to be significantly better under treatment D₁S₂ (54.25 cm). However, the maximum number of internodes/plant (7.88) was recorded in treatment D₁S₃. Number of leaves/plant was recorded to be significantly maximum (60.50) under first date of sowing, i.e., 3rd Nov., 2011. The maximum number of branches/plant (7.88) were observed in D₁S₂ followed by D₁S₁ (7.77) and D₁S₃ and D₂S₃ (7.55 each) at 60 DAS. Thus, it is clear that first date of sowing was superior over second and third date of sowing with closer spacing. There was maximum flowering under the treatment D₁S₃ (4.66 flowers/plant) followed by D₁S₁ (4.21) and D₁S₂ (3.99) as compared to other treatments at 60 DAT. In a study on tomato and capsicum, Moldoveanu *et al.* (2) and Satpute *et al.* (5) also concluded that increased plant density enhanced earliness in flowering. This could be due to high temperature and proper utilization of nutrients because of which a greater vegetative growth was shown in treatment with early sowing and close spacing. The first date of sowing was statistically superior, over the second D₂ (8 Nov., 2011) and third

D₃ (13 Nov., 2011) dates of sowing which did not perform well (Table 1). This could be due to low temperatures existing towards mid-late November which delayed the seed germination. Due to the relatively higher temperature (20-22°C) in the beginning of November i.e., D₁ (3rd Nov., 2011) the seed germination was better and in December to January the seedlings were able to attain four leaf stage and were transferred to polybags before their growth became static. However, towards February to March upon return of congenial environmental conditions the seedling growth was revived and a significant improvement in the performance of the seedlings was observed. However, on the later dates of sowing (D₂ & D₃) the temperature being low in late November delayed seed germination and also the vegetative growth of seedling was poor until the return of congenial conditions when the growth was revived. Number of fruits per plant maximum (5.55 fruits/plant) in plants sown on 3rd Nov., 2011 and transplanted at 40 × 90cm followed by D₁S₃ (4.0 fruits) and D₁S₄ (3.55 fruits/plant).

There was a significant effect of sowing time on the performance of Cape gooseberry. The first date of sowing was found good for vegetative growth and development and flowering and fruiting, while second and third dates of sowing performed well in vegetative growth and development but not in flowering. On the other hand, there was no fruiting in second and third date of sowing until 60 DAT. The present investigation has further revealed that spacing did not had any significant effect on plant growth and development of Cape gooseberry. But this needs to be researched further for conclusive results.

Thus, it may be concluded that sowing of seeds on 3rd Nov., and transplanting at 45 X 90 cm spacing (D₁S₂) is best for the proper growth and development and fruiting performance of Cape gooseberry.

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INFLUENCE OF SPACING AND NITROGEN ON FLOWER QUALITY AND VASE LIFE OF ASIATIC LILY CV. GIRONDE

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ABSTRACT : The study on influence of spacing and nitrogen on flower quality and vase life of Asiatic lily cv. Gironde was carried out in UHS, Bagalkot during 2012-2013 and nitrogen levels viz., on flower quality and vase life of flowers. All twelve possible combinations of the spacing S₁ to S₃ (30x15 cm, 30x30 cm and 40x15 cm) and nitrogen levels N₁ to N₄ (0, 100, 150 and 200kg/ha) were laid in combination as per treatments in Factorial Randomized Block Design (FRBD) with three replications. The quality parameters and vase life of Asiatic lily were significantly influenced by spacing and nitrogen. Spacing of 30x15 cm and nitrogen level of 200 kg per ha were found excellent when compared to others. The interaction between spacing and nitrogen exhibited significant enhancement in bud diameter.

Keywords : Asiatic lily, flower quality, vase life, spacing, nitrogen.

Globally growing floriculture industry has achieved significance during the past few decades. At present, cut flower production focus has moved from traditional growers, such as the Netherlands, Germany and France, to countries like African countries and some of the Asian countries where the climates are better and production costs are low. In India, there has been a dynamic shift from sustenance production to commercial production of commercial flowers.

Asiatic lily, a member of the family Liliaceae, has its elegant flower spikes which have rich variation of colours and long vase life, is commercially grown for its fascinating flowers which are used as the most preferred line flowers in floral arrangements worldwide. To achieve production of quality spikes improved crop management techniques need to be standardized for every new location where the crop is grown. Besides the climatic condition, the plant spacing and nitrogen plays important role in quality of flowers. The basic crop management practices like plant spacing and nitrogen doses are not yet standardized for cultivating this crop in a commercial scale at Karnataka condition. Hence, the present investigation was undertaken to study the effect of spacing and nitrogen levels on quality and vase life of Asiatic lily cv. Gironde.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The field experiment was conducted during 2012-2013 in University of Horticultural Sciences, Bagalkot. There were a total of twelve treatments replicated three times in a Factorial Randomized Block Design (FRBD). Three different plant spacing viz., S₁- 30 x 15 cm, S₂-30 x 30, S₃- 40 x 15 cm, and four

different nitrogen doses viz., N₁ to N₄ (0, 100, 150 and 200 kg/ha) in twelve possible combinations were adopted as treatments. The quality parameters and vase life of flowers were recorded and the data were analyzed using the analysis of variance.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Effect of Spacing and Nitrogen

All the quality parameters viz., length and diameter of flower stalk, flower bud and vase life of Asiatic lily were significantly influenced by spacing and nitrogen levels individually (Table 1).

Maximum length of flower stalk (44.23 cm) was recorded at S₁ spacing which was on par at S₃ spacing (43.73 cm) and S₂ spacing (39.93 cm). This might be due to the fact that optimum use of all resources under closer spacing. This resulted in elongation of main stalk confirming to observations made by Mane *et al.* (4) in tuberose. Maximum length of flower stalk (34.70 cm) was recorded at N₄ level of nitrogen followed by N₃ level (33.27 cm), while minimum mean length of flower stalk (28.88 cm) was recorded at N₁ level. Nitrogen was absorbed by the plants and thereby stimulated plant growth and induced the production of auxiliary buds resulting in increased flower stalk height. Results are in consonance with Rathore and Singh (6) and Singh (7).

Increasing nitrogen levels up to 200 kg per ha significantly increased flower stalk diameter from 0.27 cm to 0.44 cm. The increase in growth characters and yield components from increased nitrogen level might be due to the role of nitrogen in stimulating vegetative growth. The hypothesis is that nitrogen is a constituent

of protein, nucleic acids and nucleotides that are essential to the metabolic function of plants (Khalaj and Edrisi, 3).

Data (Table 1) also confirmed that the maximum flower stalk diameter (0.51 cm) was produced at the closer spacing (30 x 15 cm) compared to the minimum (0.43 cm) flower stalk diameter at the wider spacing of 30 x 30 cm. The results are in support of Mane *et al.* (5).

Maximum diameter of bud (1.63 cm) was recorded at 30x15 cm spacing compared to the least diameter (1.28 cm) at wider spacing of 30 x 30 cm. Maximum diameter of bud (1.31 cm) was recorded at 200 kg per ha level of nitrogen followed by 150 kg per ha (1.09 cm) and 100 kg per ha (1.00 cm), while

minimum mean diameter of bud (0.93 cm) was recorded at N₁ level (Table 1). This might be due to the fact that optimum utilization of resources.

Maximum length of bud (5.43 m) was recorded at closer spacing (30 x 15 cm) which was on par with S₃ spacing (5.14 cm) and least length of bud (4.60 cm) was recorded under 30 x 30 cm spacing. Maximum length of bud (4.47 cm) was recorded at N₄ level of nitrogen which was on par at N₃ level (4.05 cm), while minimum mean length of bud (3.10 cm) was recorded at N₁ level. This might be due to the fact that optimum utilization of resources. This resulted in elongation of bud length, increase in bud length may be due to elongation of cells and number of cells due to cell division. Similar observations had also been made by

Table 1: Effect of spacing and nitrogen levels on quality parameters and vase life of Asiatic lily.

Treatment	Length of flower stalk (cm)	Diameter of flower stalk (cm)	Bud diameter (cm)	Bud length (cm)	Vase life (days)
Spacing (cm)					
S ₁ = 30 x15	44.23	0.51	1.63	5.43	6.75
S ₂ = 30 x 30	39.93	0.43	1.28	4.60	5.93
S ₃ = 40 x15	43.73	0.47	1.41	5.14	6.59
C.D. (P=0.05)	3.12	0.04	0.12	0.45	0.42
Nitrogen levels (kg/ha)					
N ₁ =0	28.88	0.27	0.93	3.10	4.23
N ₂ =100	31.04	0.31	1.00	3.54	4.58
N ₃ =150	33.27	0.40	1.09	4.05	5.06
N ₄ =200	34.70	0.44	1.31	4.47	5.40
C.D. (P=0.05)	3.60	0.04	0.14	0.52	0.49
Interaction (S x N)					
S ₁ N ₁	38.90	0.39	1.27	4.37	6.13
S ₁ N ₂	42.43	0.45	1.48	5.00	6.23
S ₁ N ₃	46.23	0.58	1.74	5.81	6.89
S ₁ N ₄	49.33	0.63	2.01	6.53	7.74
S ₂ N ₁	36.73	0.31	1.21	3.97	5.13
S ₂ N ₂	39.80	0.39	1.25	4.40	5.99
S ₂ N ₃	40.73	0.49	1.28	4.77	6.25
S ₂ N ₄	42.47	0.53	1.39	5.27	6.35
S ₃ N ₁	39.87	0.36	1.23	4.07	5.64
S ₃ N ₂	41.93	0.40	1.27	4.77	6.10
S ₃ N ₃	46.10	0.52	1.32	5.63	7.10
S ₃ N ₄	47.00	0.59	1.83	6.10	7.53
C.D. (P=0.05)	NS	NS	0.25	NS	NS

Karavadia and Dhaduk (1) in chrysanthemum, Karthikeyan and Jawaharlal (6) in carnation and Mane et al. (4) in tuberose.

Maximum vase life of flowers (6.75 days) was recorded at S₁ spacing which was on par at S₃ spacing (6.59 days) and least vase life under S₂ spacing (5.93 days). The vase life increased with a decrease of plant spacing (Mane et al., 5).

With respect to nitrogen levels, maximum vase life of flower (5.40 days) was recorded at 200 kg/ha (N₄) level of nitrogen which was on par with 150 kg/ha level (5.06 days), while minimum vase life of flower (4.23 days) was recorded at control (0 kgN/ha). It could be due to the fact that more number of flower buds and flowers per spike, maximum weight of flowers and also bigger sized flowers in the spike (Khalaj and Edrisi, 3). Increase in vase life of tuberose flowers due to higher nitrogen level had also been reported by Rathore and Singh (6).

Interaction Effect of Spacing and Nitrogen

The interaction effect of nitrogen levels and spacing showed significant differences with respect to bud diameter. The biggest sized (2.01 cm) buds were obtained from treatment combination of 200 kgN/ha (N₄) and S₁ (30 x 15cm) spacing which was on par with S₃N₄ combination (1.83 cm), while the lowest bud diameter (1.21 cm) was recorded in combination of N₁ and S₂ (Table 1).

The interaction effect of nitrogen levels and spacing showed non-significant differences with respect to length and diameter of flower stalk, length of flower bud and vase life of flowers.

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EFFECT OF CHEMICAL FLORAL PRESERVATIVES ON VASE LIFE OF CUT FLOWERS OF GERBERA CV. PRESIDENT

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ABSTRACT : Gerbera cv. President was subjected to twelve different treatment combinations against control to study the vase life. Treatment with 100ppm silver nitrate + 6% sucrose + 400 ppm 8-HQS + 100ppm silver thiosulphate showed significant beneficial effect in extending the vase life of the cultivar to 9.63 days, as against 7.57 days of vase life in control. The findings provide an alternative for extending the vase life of cut gerbera flowers. Treated flower stems also showed minimum contamination of micro organisms.

Keywords : Gerbera, cut flower, STS, HQS, silver nitrate, vase life.

Gerbera is an elegant garden flower of immense value. They are a real attraction in the garden with their star like flowers of varying colour shades. Flowers borne terminally on slender long stems, they form effective, colourful flower borders or beds (Thangaraj *et al.*, 5). The first scientific description of a Gerbera was made by J.D. Hooker in Curtis's Botanical Magazine in 1889, when he described Gerbera jamesonii, a South African species also known as Barberton Daisy. Vase life of cut flowers may be extended by adding chemical preservative in holding solution (Yoo and Kim, 9). The objective of this study was to determine the effects of different chemicals in extending vase life of gerbera flowers.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The present investigation was carried out at Division of Horticulture, UAS Bengaluru during 2009-10. Flowers selected for the experiment were harvested when their outer ray florets were completely elongated or when outer two rows of disc florets are perpendicular to the flower stalk. Flowers were carefully brought to the laboratory without causing any damage and they were kept in clean water. Then they were imposed with treatments.

Flowers were sorted out for uniform head size so as to maintain uniformity within the replication. About an inch (2.5cm) of basal portion of stem was cut to evaluate for the presence of bacteria. Then stems were cut to a uniform length of 50cm. Then each flower stalk were placed in 500ml bottle containing 250 ml of aqueous solutions of different chemical preservatives used individually or in combination as detailed

separately in each experiment (Table 1) or 250 ml of distilled water. Distilled water was used to increase experimental variability.

Observations on water uptake, water loss, water balance, fresh weight and vase life of flowers were recorded and analyzed statistically.

Plate count technique was adopted to estimate the bacterial counts. Stem pieces of 2.5cm were taken in 100ml sterile water and placed in a shaker for 10 minutes. Afterwards serial dilution was made up to 10⁻⁷. The dilutions of 10⁻⁵, 10⁻⁶ and 10⁻⁷ were placed on nutrient agar for presence or absence of bacteria. Bengal agar was used to find out the presence of different bacteria. Under each dilution, three plates were used by making with plus symbol and presence of microorganisms was recorded with plus. More plus indicates higher density of microorganisms.

The experiment was laid out in a single factorial design with three replications. The mean data on various parameters recorded during the period of study were subjected to statistical analysis as per the procedure given by Sundarraj *et al.* (4).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The cut flowers of gerbera cv. President treated with chemicals at different concentration significantly increased the cumulative water uptake compared to control. Maximum cumulative water uptake of 49.33 g/fl was recorded in 100ppm Silver nitrate + 6% sucrose + 400 ppm 8-HQS followed by treatment with 200ppm Sodium benzoate +4% sucrose + 200 ppm 8-HQS which recorded 46.67 g/fl compared to other concentrations and control (26.33 g/fl). A significant

influence was noticed on water uptake of gerbera by silver nitrate with sucrose and 8-HQS as compared to control. This might be due to germicidal activity of silver nitrate and 8-HQS, hence improving water uptake by reducing bacterial blockage (Halvey and Mayak, 2; Vaidya and Collis, 6) and minimizing loss in fresh weight.

The cut flowers of Gerbera cv. President treated with chemicals at different concentration significantly increased the cumulative water loss compared to control. Maximum cumulative water loss of 59.33 g/fl was recorded in 100 ppm silver nitrate + 6% sucrose + 400 ppm 8-HQS followed by treatment with 200ppm Sodium benzoate +4% sucrose + 200 ppm 8-HQS which recorded 55.67 g/fl compared to other concentrations and control (32.33 g/fl). Results are in agreement with Dasgupta (1) and Vaidya and Collis (7). Flowers treated with silver nitrate in combination with 8-HQS showed water loss but still recorded a long vase life compared to control. This is in accordance with results obtained by Yogitha (8).

All the treatments including control showed minimum water uptake to water loss ratio. However, among the different treatments, T₄, T₇ and T₈ recorded maximum water uptake to water loss (0.88) and it can be observed from the Table 1 that the cut flowers

recorded a negative water balance in all the treatments including control.

Cut flowers treated with chemicals at different concentration significantly increased the fresh weight compared to control. Maximum fresh weight of 39.67 g/fl was recorded in 100 ppm silver nitrate + 6% sucrose + 400 ppm 8-HQS followed by treatment 200ppm Sodium benzoate +4% sucrose + 200 ppm 8-HQS which recorded 37.33 g/fl compared to other concentrations and control (34.00 g/fl).

The significant increase in fresh weight was due to silver compounds and this is attributed to the inhibition of ethylene production during vase life and minimizing loss in fresh weight. These results are in close agreement to observation made by Han and Lee (3).

Maximum vase life of 9.63 days was recorded in 100 ppm silver nitrate + 6% sucrose + 400 ppm 8-HQS followed by treatment with 200ppm sodium benzoate +4% sucrose + 200 ppm 8-HQS which recorded 9.10 days compared to other concentrations and control (7.57 days).

Presence of bacteria in the basal stem portion of cut gerbera

Data with respect to the presence of bacterial presence in the basal stem segment of cut gerbera is

Table 1 : Effect of chemical floral preservatives on vase life of cut flowers of gerbera cv. President.

Treatment	Water uptake (ml)	Water Loss (ml)	Water uptake :loss ratio	Water balance	Fresh weight (g)	Vase life (days)
T ₁ : 200ppm Aluminum sulphate +4% sucrose + 200 ppm 8-HQS	39.00	45.00	0.87	-6.0	31.33	8.13
T ₂ : 400ppm Aluminum sulphate +6% sucrose + 400 ppm 8-HQS	37.00	43.00	0.86	-6.0	32.33	8.20
T ₃ :T ₁ + 100ppm Silver thiosulphate	36.67	45.67	0.80	-9.0	33.33	8.40
T ₄ :T ₂ + 150ppm Silver thiosulphate	44.67	50.67	0.88	-6.0	36.33	8.63
T ₅ :200ppm Sodium benzoate +4% sucrose + 200 ppm 8-HQS	46.67	55.67	0.84	-9.0	37.33	9.10
T ₆ :300ppm Sodium benzoate + 6% sucrose + 400 ppm 8-HQS	45.33	53.33	0.85	-8.0	34.33	8.70
T ₇ :T ₅ + 100ppm Silver thiosulphate	43.67	49.67	0.88	-6.0	33.33	8.83
T ₈ :T ₆ + 150ppm Silver thiosulphate	42.67	48.67	0.88	-6.0	32.67	9.03
T ₉ :50ppm Silver nitrate + 4% sucrose + 200 ppm 8-HQS	41.33	47.33	0.87	-6.0	34.33	8.50
T ₁₀ :100ppm Silver nitrate + 6% sucrose + 400 ppm 8-HQS	49.33	59.33	0.83	-10.0	39.67	9.63
T ₁₁ : T ₉ + 100ppm Silver thiosulphate	38.67	44.67	0.87	-6.0	36.33	8.20
T ₁₂ :T ₁₀ +150ppm Silver thiosulphate	38.33	44.33	0.86	-6.0	34.00	7.90
T ₁₃ : Control (Distilled water)	26.33	32.33	0.81	-6.0	34.00	7.57
CD (P=0.05)	1.01	1.01	0.06	0.003	1.14	0.066

presented in Table 2. The basal cut stems of size 2.5 cm were taken and subjected to microbial examination. From the table, it is evident that the basal stem portion recorded the presence of Pseudomonas and Bacillus. They were found more in control as compared to the treatment 100ppm Silver nitrate + 6% sucrose + 400 ppm 8-HQS which are in line of Dasgupta (1).

Table 2: Bacterial presence in the basal stem segment of cut flowers of gerbera cv. President.

Treatment	<i>Bacillus spp.</i>	<i>Pseudomonas spp.</i>
100 ppm Silver nitrate + 6% sucrose + 400 ppm 8-HQS	++	++
Control	++++	+++

Conclusion

The best flower longevity was recorded in the treatment of 100ppm Silver nitrate + 6% sucrose + 400 ppm 8-HQS preservative solution and the lowest vase life was recorded from cut flowers treated with water. Generally, it can be concluded that use of 100ppm Silver nitrate + 6% sucrose + 400 ppm 8-HQS preservative solution for flower longevity and maintaining post-harvest characteristics of Gerbera cv. President cut flowers.

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EFFECT OF INTERCROPPING IN GLADIOLUS WITH CORIANDER, FENUGREEK AND SOYA

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ABSTRACT: The present experiment on “intercropping in gladiolus with coriander, fenugreek and soya under Allahabad condition was conducted during *Rabi* season at research farm of Department of Horticulture, SHIATS, Allahabad. The results revealed that growth parameters of coriander, fenugreek and soya, such as seed germination (%), plant height, number of leaves and branches/plant were found to be higher under the treatment T₂ (coriander sole), T₃ (fenugreek sole) and T₄ (soya alone) followed by their individual intercropping with gladiolus, viz. T₅ (gladiolus + coriander), T₆ (gladiolus + fenugreek) and T₇ (gladiolus + soya). The performance of gladiolus in all respect (growth to yield) was found better under the combination of T₆ (gladiolus + fenugreek).

Keywords : *Gladiolus, fenugreek, coriander, soya, growth, herbage yield, corm yield.*

Gladiolus cultivation under northern Indian plains, coastal areas of Tamil Nadu and Pondicherry has a potential to change the economic scenario of farmers of these areas. Gladiolus is a flower of glamour and perfection which is known as the queen of bulbous flowers due to its elegant spikes with florets of massive form, brilliant colours, attractive shapes, varying size and excellent shelf life. Gladiolus is grown as flower bed in gardens and used in floral arrangements for interior decoration as well as making high quality bouquet (Lepcha *et al.*, 1). Intercropping with flowering herbaceous plants increases parasitoid survivorship, fecundity and retention, and pest suppression in agro ecosystems. (Patt *et al.*, 3)

MATERIALS AND METHODS

This experiment was conducted in Floriculture Unit, Department of Horticulture, Allahabad School of Agriculture, SHIATS, Allahabad. Soil of the experimental plot was sandy loam, uniform in texture and well drained. The experiment was laid out in Randomized Block Design (RBD) with three replications. A total eight intercropping treatments viz. T₁-Gladiolus alone, T₂-Coriander alone, T₃- Fenugreek alone, T₄- Soya alone, T₅- Gladiolus + Coriander, T₆- Gladiolus + Fenugreek, T₇- Gladiolus+ Soya, and T₈-Gladiolus + Coriander + Fenugreek + Soya were adopted. All the recorded observations were subjected to the statistical analysis. The data on growth and herbage yield components of intercropped crops were subjected to Fisher's method of analysis of variance as outlined by Panse and Sukhatme (2).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Effect of intercropping on herbs with gladiolus

Data depicted in Table 1 revealed that a significant variation was observed in crops (coriander, fenugreek and soya) intercropped with gladiolus. Significantly maximum seed germination in coriander (96.67%), fenugreek (93.33%) and soya (91.67%) was observed under their sole cropping, while the minimum germination of 85%, 83.33% and 81.67%, respectively was recorded under in T₈ treatment (gladiolus + coriander + fenugreek + soya). The same trend was also observed for plant canopies in all three herbs grown individually and/or as intercrop. The tallest plants (33.93 cm, 27.13cm and 27.20 cm) and maximum number of leaves (58.40, 60.07 and 50.33) and branches/plant (15.40, 17.93 and 11.60) were recorded in coriander, fenugreek and soya, respectively when they were grown as sole crop. When they all were intercropped with gladiolus (T₈), plant canopy of these herbs (coriander/fenugreek/soya) reduced to minimum as 24.33cm, 23.13cm and 18.0cm (plant height), 52.13, 46.67 and 44.47 leaves/plant, and 10.53, 14.53 and 7.0 branches/plant, respectively (Table 1). The same trend was also observed for maximum total herbage yield of 7.87 t, 8.80 t and 7.47 t per hectare for coriander, fenugreek and soya, respectively when they were grown as sole crop. Intercropping of all these three herbs with gladiolus (T₈) resulted in the lowest herbage yield.

Table 1: Effect of intercropping in gladiolus with coriander, fenugreek and soya.

Treatment	Seed germination (%)			Plant height (cm)			No. of leaves/plant			No. of branches/plant			Herbage yield/plot (g)			Herbage yield (t/ha)			
	C	F	S	C	F	S	C	F	S	C	F	S	C	F	S	C	F	S	
T ₁ Gladiolus sole	96.67																		
T ₂ Coriander sole	33.93	93.33		58.40	60.07		15.40	17.93		787.33	880.00		7.87	8.80					
T ₃ Fenugreek sole	27.13																		
T ₄ Soya sole	29.20	91.67		56.00	50.33		13.67	11.60		507.00	746.67		5.47	7.47					
T ₅ Gladiolus + Coriander	25.20																		
T ₆ Gladiolus + Fenugreek	22.73	85.00		53.67	46.80		16.00	9.93		666.67	481.00		6.67	4.81					
T ₇ Gladiolus + Soya	23.13	83.33	81.67	46.67	44.47		10.53	7.00		377.00	357.33		3.44	4.21					
T ₈ Gladiolus + Coriander + Fenugreek + Soya	18.00	85.00	81.67	52.13	46.67		10.53	7.00		377.00	357.33		3.44	4.21					
C. D. (P = 0.05)	4.68	4.05	3.51	2.41	6.38	1.79	2.02	1.45	1.50	120.51	201.60	114.13	0.87	2.02					

Table 2 : Effect of intercropping on gladiolus with coriander, fenugreek and soya.

Treatment	Plant height (cm)	No. of leaves/plant	No. of shoots /corm	Days to spike initiation	Days to opening of the first floret	First floret durability (Days)	Spike length	Rachis length	No. of floret per spike	No. of opened florets /spike	No. of partially opened florets /spike	Floret size (cm)	Durability of spike (days)	No. of spikes /ha (lakh)	No. of corms /plant ed corm	No. of corms /ha (lakh)	No. of corm plants	No. of corms (lakh)
T ₁	26.87	4.40	1.53	68.53	80.67	9.27	75.93	47.93	15.33	13.27	2.07	8.53	9.73	1.38	2.07	1.86	20.40	18.36
T ₂	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
T ₃	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
T ₄	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
T ₅	28.97	5.13	1.80	66.67	78.33	9.60	76.80	49.33	16.00	13.87	2.13	8.73	10.47	1.08	2.13	1.28	21.73	13.04
T ₆	34.87	6.93	2.13	63.60	74.40	10.67	80.67	52.80	18.67	16.20	2.47	9.67	12.20	1.28	2.40	1.44	23.93	14.36
T ₇	30.73	6.20	1.93	65.33	76.53	10.07	78.47	51.13	17.07	14.80	2.27	9.13	11.27	1.16	2.20	1.32	22.73	13.64
T ₈	24.73	3.73	1.47	69.80	82.20	8.87	74.87	46.87	14.20	12.27	1.93	8.27	8.87	0.44	2.00	0.60	19.93	5.98
(C.P.=0.05)	1.90	0.73	0.16	1.32	1.76	0.40	1.05	1.39	1.06	0.91	0.25	0.25	0.79	0.09	0.10	0.07	0.91	0.57

Effect of intercropping on gladiolus with herbs

It is evident from the data (Table 2) that plant height (34.87cm), number of leaves/plant (6.93) and number of shoots/mother corm (2.13) were significantly maximum when gladiolus was inter cropped with fenugreek (T₆). The minimum plant height (24.73 cm), number of leaves/plant (3.73) and number of shoots/mother corm (1.93) in gladiolus were noted under T₈ treatment (gladiolus + coriander + fenugreek + soya).

Significantly the earliest spike emergence (63.60 days after planting) as well as earliest opening of first floret (74.40 DAP) were observed when gladiolus was intercropped with fenugreek (T₆) followed by T₇ (gladiolus + soya), T₅ (gladiolus + coriander) and T₈ (gladiolus + coriander + fenugreek + soya). Maximum durability of first floret (10.67 days), longest spike (80.67cm) and maximum length of rachis (52.80 cm) were in gladiolus intercropped with fenugreek (T₆) followed by gladiolus + soya (10.07 days, 78.47 cm and 51.13 cm, respectively) and gladiolus + coriander (T₅).

Gladiolus intercropped with coriander + fenugreek + soya (T₈) exhibited the lowest values for spike (74.87cm) and rachis (46.87cm) length, and first floret durability (8.87 days). Significantly the highest number of florets/spike (18.67), number of opened florets/spike (16.20) and maximum floret size (9.67cm) were found in gladiolus intercropped with fenugreek (T₆), and values for these parameters were observed minimum

(14.20, 12.27 and 8.27 cm) with T₈ (gladiolus + coriander + fenugreek + soya). Longevity of spike (12.20 days) as well as number of partially opened florets/spike (2.47) was also maximum in combination of gladiolus + fenugreek. Yield of spikes (1.28 lakh/ha), corms (2.40/mother corm, and 1.44 lakh/ha) and cormels (23.93/plant) were noted maximum in gladiolus intercropped with fenugreek (T₆).

From the above going discussion, it may be concluded that individual growing of coriander, fenugreek and soya (as sole crop) performed best for their growth and yield traits. While, intercropping of gladiolus with fenugreek (T₆) resulted best performance regarding growth, flowering and yield of gladiolus. Thus, intercropping of gladiolus with fenugreek may be recommended for higher benefit.

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EFFECT OF CHEMICAL FLORAL PRESERVATIVES ON VASE LIFE OF CUT FLOWERS OF GERBERA CV. SUNCITY

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ABSTRACT : Gerbera cv. Suncity was subjected to twelve different treatment combinations against control to evaluate vase life and quality. Treatment with 200ppm Aluminium sulphate + 4% sucrose + 200 ppm 8-HQS + 100ppm Silver thiosulphate showed significant beneficial effect in extending the vase life of the cut flower to 10 (9.5) days, as against 7 (7.47) days of vase life in control. Presence of microbes (*Bacillus spp.* and *Pseudomonas spp.*) was also recorded less on treated cut flower stems over control.

Keywords : Gerbera, cut flower, STS, HQS, aluminium sulphate, AgNO₃.

Gerbera is an elegant garden flower of immense value. They are a real attraction in the garden with their star like flowers of varying colour shades. Flowers borne terminally on slender long stems, and form effective, colourful flower borders or beds. The first scientific description of a Gerbera was made by J.D. Hooker in Curtis's Botanical Magazine in 1889, when he described *Gerbera jamesonii*, a South African species also known as Barberton Daisy. Addition of chemical floral preservatives to the holding solution has been recommended (Vaidya and Collis, 6) to prolong the vase life of cut flowers. Keeping the view in mind, present study was conducted to determine the effects of different chemicals in extending vase life of gerbera flowers.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The present investigation was carried out at Division of Horticulture, UAS Bengaluru during 2009-10. Flowers selected for the experiment were harvested when their outer ray florets were completely elongated or when outer two rows of disc florets were perpendicular to the flower stalk. Flowers were carefully brought to the laboratory without causing any damage and they were kept in clean water. Then they were imposed with treatments.

Flowers were sorted out for uniform head size so as to maintain uniformity within the replication. About an inch (2.5 cm) of basal portion of stem was cut to evaluate for the presence of bacteria. Then stems were cut to a uniform length of 50cm and each flower stalk was placed in 500ml bottle containing 250 ml of aqueous solutions of different chemical preservatives used individually or in combination as detailed (Table 1)

in each experiment or 250 ml of distilled water. Distilled water was used to increase experimental variability. Observations on water uptake, water lost due to transpiration, water balance, fresh weight of the flower and vase life were recorded.

Plate count technique was adopted to estimate the presence of bacteria. Stem pieces of 2.5 cm were taken in 100 ml sterile water and placed in a shaker for 10 minutes. Afterwards serial dilution was made up to 10⁻⁷. The dilutions of 10⁻⁵, 10⁻⁶ and 10⁻⁷ were plated on nutrient agar for presence or absence of bacteria. Bengal agar was used to find out the presence of different bacteria. Under each dilution, three plates were used by making with plus symbol and presence of microorganisms was recorded with plus. More plus indicates higher density of microorganisms.

The experiment was laid out in a single factorial design with three replications. The mean data on various parameters recorded during the period of study were subjected to statistical analysis as per the procedure of Sundarraj *et al.* (5).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Gerbera cv. Suncity cutflowers recorded maximum cumulative water uptake of 46.33 g/fl with treatment combination of 200 ppm sodium benzoate + 4% sucrose + 200 ppm 8- HQS followed by 44.0 g/fl with treatment combination of 100ppm silver nitrate + 6% sucrose + 400 ppm 8-HQS against other treatments and control (22.33g/fl). A significant influence was noticed on water uptake of gerbera by sodium benzoate treatments in combination with sucrose and germicide as compared to control (Table

1). This might be due to inhibiting bacterial blockage by improving water uptake (Vaidya and Collis, 7) minimizing loss in fresh weight.

confirming to the reports of Chand *et al.* (1) in rose and Shigeru *et al.* (4) in carnation.

Table 1 : Effect of chemical floral preservatives on vase life of cut flowers of gerbera cv. Suncity.

Treatment	Water uptake	Water Loss	uptake :loss ratio	Water balance	Fresh weight	Vase life
T ₁ : 200ppm Aluminum sulphate +4% sucrose + 200 ppm 8-HQS	37.00	44.00	0.84	-7.0	21.67	8.03
T ₂ : 400ppm Aluminum sulphate +6% sucrose + 400 ppm 8-HQS	36.33	41.33	0.88	-5.0	23.33	8.20
T ₃ :T ₁ + 100ppm Silver thiosulphate	34.67	39.67	0.87	-5.0	26.00	8.30
T ₄ :T ₂ + 150ppm Silver thiosulphate	30.33	36.00	0.84	-5.7	23.67	8.40
T ₅ :200ppm Sodium benzoate +4% sucrose + 200 ppm 8-HQS	46.33	54.33	0.85	-8.0	38.33	9.50
T ₆ :300ppm Sodium benzoate + 6% sucrose + 400 ppm 8-HQS	40.67	46.67	0.87	-6.0	27.67	8.63
T ₇ :T ₅ + 100ppm Silver thiosulphate	39.33	45.33	0.87	-6.0	30.33	9.10
T ₈ :T ₆ + 150ppm Silver thiosulphate	38.00	44.00	0.86	-6.0	33.00	8.30
T ₉ :50ppm Silver nitrate + 4% sucrose + 200 ppm 8-HQS	36.67	42.67	0.86	-6.0	36.00	8.40
T ₁₀ :100ppm Silver nitrate + 6% sucrose + 400 ppm 8-HQS	44.00	52.00	0.85	-8.0	36.33	9.03
T ₁₁ : T ₉ + 100ppm Silver thiosulphate	37.67	43.67	0.86	-6.0	37.00	9.20
T ₁₂ :T ₁₀ +150ppm Silver thiosulphate	34.33	40.33	0.85	-6.0	36.33	8.70
T ₁₃ : Control (Distill water)	22.33	28.33	0.79	-6.0	21.33	7.47
CD (P=0.05)	1.34	1.23	0.09	0.3	1.08	0.054

The maximum cumulative water loss of 54.33 g/fl was recorded in flowers treated with 200 ppm sodium benzoate + 4% sucrose + 200 ppm 8- HQS followed by 52.00 g/fl with treatment combination of 100ppm silver nitrate + 6% sucrose + 400 ppm 8-HQS against other treatments and control (32.00 g/fl). Flowers treated with sodium benzoate in combination with 8-HQS showed water loss but still recorded a long vase life compared to control. Dasgupta (2) and Yoo and Kim (8) had also documented similar findings which confirms present results.

All the treatments including control showed minimum water uptake to water loss ratio. However, among the treatments 400ppm Aluminum sulphate + 6% sucrose + 400 ppm 8-HQS recorded maximum water uptake to water loss (0.88) and it can be observed from the table that the cut flowers recorded a negative water balance in all the treatments including control. Results are in line of Chand *et al.* (1) and Yoo and Kim (8).

Maximum fresh weight of 38.33 g/fl was recorded in flowers treated with 200 ppm sodium benzoate + 4% sucrose + 200 ppm 8- HQS followed by 37.00 g/fl in 100ppm silver nitrate + 6% sucrose + 400 ppm 8-HQS and control recorded least fresh weight of 21.33g/fl

The significant increase in fresh weight was due to STS in vase solution containing aluminum sulphate. This is attributed to the inhibition of ethylene production during vase life and minimizing loss in fresh weight. Similar findings were also reported by Nair *et al.* (3) and Vaidya and Collis (6) in gerbera and Dendrobium, respectively.

Maximum vase life of 9.50 days was recorded in flowers treated with 200 ppm sodium benzoate + 4% sucrose + 200 ppm 8- HQS and vase life of 9.20 days was observed in treatment 100ppm silver nitrate + 6% sucrose + 400 ppm 8-HQS and control recorded lowest vase life of 7.47 days.

Presence of bacteria in the basal stem portion of cut gerbera

Data with respect to the presence of bacterial presence in the basal stem segment of cut gerbera cultivars is presented in Table 2. The basal cut stems of size 2.5 cm were taken and subjected to microbial examination in all the cultivars. From the table, it is evident that the basal stem portion recorded the presence of *Pseudomonas* and *Bacillus*. They were found more in control as compared to the other treatments.

Table 2 : Bacterial presence in the basal stem segment of cut flowers of gerbera cv. Suncity.

Treatment	<i>Bacillus spp.</i>	<i>Pseudomonas spp.</i>
200 ppm Sodium benzoate + 4% sucrose + 200 ppm 8-HQS	++	++
Control	++++	++++

Conclusion

The best flower longevity was recorded in the treatment 200 ppm sodium benzoate + 4% sucrose + 200 ppm 8- HQS preservative solution and the lowest vase life was recorded from cut flowers treated with water. Generally, it can be concluded that use of Sodium benzoate+ sucrose + 8-HQS preservative solution for flower longevity and maintaining post-harvest characteristics of Gerbera cv. Suncity cut flowers.

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Research Note :**MULBERRY: THE FRUIT OF HEAVEN'S CHOICE****V. Asha Krishna*, P. Sujathamma, G. Savithri and T. Vijaya***Department of Sericulture, S.P. Mahila Vishvavidyalayam (Women's University), Tirupati-517502, Andhra Pradesh, India***E-mail: ashakrishnanine@gmail.com*

ABSTRACT : Mulberry, belongs to the genus *Morus* of family Moraceae, consists more than 20 species and several subspecies or varieties. Mulberry is cultivated in many countries for a long time with the sole purpose of feeding the monophagous silkworm *Bombyx mori* L. In addition to the major utilization of mulberry leaves as silkworm feed, it is being used for many other purposes, for which it is called as *Kalpavriksha*. The modern interest on the cultivation and use of mulberry for animal feed and medicinal uses has been initiated due to search for alternative uses of mulberry, once the sericulture activities reduced due to competition from foreign countries in case of Japan and Italy. In addition to the major utilization of leaves as silkworm feed, they have many excellent and beneficial functions to do. This has opened a new vista to think about other uses of mulberry apart from silkworm feed. In this context multiple uses of mulberry fruits are being discussed in the paper.

Key words : *Mulberry fruit, juice, herbal medicine.*

Mulberry, belongs to the genus *Morus* of the family Moraceae, is believed to be a native of either India or China. It grows throughout the year in tropical climate and remains dormant during winter in temperate climate. India has rich flora and good number of plants containing substances having medicinal properties. Mulberry is one among them. There are many species of the genus *Morus*, of which around 10-15 are generally accepted. Of these the most cultivated are: the white mulberry (*Morus alba*); black mulberry (*Morus nigra*) and the American mulberry or red mulberry (*Morus rubra*). Mulberry silk comes from the silkworm *Bombyx mori* L. which solely feeds on the leaves of mulberry plan (Subhuti, 7). One of the primary uses of the plant is for raising silkworms, which utilize the leaves as their main food source. Mulberry starts producing fruits in May-June. Mulberry has an aggregate fruit that is composed of lots of berries stuck together and measures 2-5cm. The full bodied flavour of this fruit is a good balance of sweetness and tartness with nutritional elements of vital importance for human metabolism.

Botanically the fruit is not a berry but a collective fruit called as *sorosis*, because it is formed by the consolidation of many flowers and in appearance like a swollen long berry. When the flowers are pollinated, they and their fleshy bases begin to swell. Ultimately they completely altered in texture and colour-becoming succulent, fat and full of juice.

It is juicy and has a sweet taste with some sourness that is more prominent in the less mature fruits. The colour of the mulberry fruit does not identify the mulberry species. For example, white mulberries can produce white, lavender or black fruit and red mulberry fruits are usually a very deep red-almost black. Black mulberry which has a lovely balance of sweetness and tartness makes the best pressed juices.

Mulberries are the latest in a fairly long line of fruit berries to be given "Super food" status. Levels of antioxidants in mulberry fruits are 70% higher than blueberries and 24% more than those found in cranberries. Not only those but mulberries are packed

with full of vitamins and fibre and contain high levels of resveratrol- the antioxidant super hero which is the focus of so much scientific interest across a wide range of disciplines. Fruits are eaten fresh and used for pickle

preparation too. It contains (malic acid, citric acid, pectin, mucilage and a coloring matter (Shivkumar *et al.*, 5; Singhal *et al.*, 6).

Medicinal values

Fresh mulberry fruits are rich in amino acids, vitamins and mineral, such as Zn, Mn, Fe, Ca that are indispensable for the human body. In addition mulberry fruits are also rich in pectin and fibrin. Ascorbic acid content is as high as 20mg/100g in fresh fruit (Chu *et al.*, 2).

High level of antioxidants in mulberries is an excellent weapon to fight against infection. Shivkumar *et al.* (5) concluded that that resveratrol decreased the reproduction of the influenza virus. In other studies links are also being made between high levels of antioxidants in the diet and protection from some of the most distressing diseases of our age –chronic diseases like Alzheimers, many forms of cancer and Parkinson's.

Mulberry fruits are an excellent source of the antioxidants resveratrol, zeaxanthin, lutein and to a lesser extent the alpha and beta carotene. Mulberry fruits derive their colour from anthocyanins. This fruit pigment is noted for its powerful antioxidant property. One ounce of ripe mulberry fruit contains nearly 60mg of anthocyanins. This phytonutrient protects our body from the harmful oxidation of free radicals. Specifically, mulberry contains cyaniding 3-glucoside, which epidemiological studies confirm lowers the risk of many degenerative diseases such as chronic arthritis and atherosclerosis. Cyaniding 3-glucoside protects the body against cardiovascular disease and diabetes. Mulberry along with improving blood circulation can help people who suffer from heart palpitations.

In Chinese medicine, mulberries are considered as an important food remedy as blood tonic. They cleanse the blood; improve its circulation and helps in strengthening the entire system. So, eating of these berries are traditional folk remedies that have developed in countries for hundreds of years. Consuming mulberries during the hot season benefits in blood disorders and has a cooling effect on the body. It enriches the blood in the process while soothing and calming the nerves. It also helps in promoting the metabolism of alcohol. Eating even a small bowl of mulberries before sleeping can cure sleeping disorders. It can also help someone suffering from anaemia and can aid suffering from vertigo. A few pieces of the mulberry fruit can relieve constipation, lower blood pressure and improve the digestive system. Mulberries contain compounds that support

balanced sugar and control blood sugar in diabetic patients. Flavonoids present in mulberry fruit prevents the rise and fall of sugar level in patients. So it is highly effective to prevent complication in diabetic patients due to sugar level spike. Eating mulberry on regular basis will keep the cholesterol level within limits (Ye and Ye, 12).

Diabetics have a tendency to feel thirsty all the time, so they are more prone to liver-kidney yin deficiency. People who sweat easily in the day or night, youngsters who spot grey hair and women with irregular periods are likely to be suffering from this area of deficiency.

Nutritional values

Fruit juice/drink

Mulberry fruits are edible and well known for its delicious taste. The fruits of the mulberry are sweet and soft. Because of their sweetness, they are of little value for culinary uses. The ripe fruits are harvested by gently shaking the trees (Singhal *et al.*, 6). They can be consumed directly or can be used in the preparation of Wine, Jam or Soft drinks. "Da 10" is the most popular fruit mulberry variety, which is planted in Zhejiang, Guangdong and Jiangsu provinces of China (Ye, 11). Mulberry fruit research has become more active in the Sericulture Research Institute of Yunna province, China utilizing many species in cross breeding for fruit production, the result of which is DL-number 1 (Chu *et al.*, 2). Mulberry fruits have many excellent characters like nice taste, large size, attractive colour and high nutritive and medicinal values.

Mulberry fruit juice has been commercially produced as a health beverage, and it has become very popular in China, Japan and Korea (Machii, 4). As a result of working with the fresh fruits to yield a juice product, the constituents have been analyzed by (Subhuti, 7). The main content of fresh, ripe mulberry fruit is: Water 85 -88%, Carbohydrate-7.8-9.2%, Protein-0.4-1.5%, Fat-0.4-0.5%, Free acids- 1.1-1.9%, Fiber-0.9-1.4%, Minerals-0.7-0.9%, (Source : www.itmonline.org, 10)

Mulberries are literal powerhouse of nutrition. They are very rich in Vitamins B, C, K and the element iron. Good levels of fibre, riboflavin, phosphorus, copper, magnesium, potassium and calcium are also found in mulberries. A new UK fruit Juice Company has launched a super fruit drink prepared from pure fresh pressed mulberry fruits which is full of antioxidants (Fairjuice, 3) without adding preservatives, the original mulberry fruit juice remains fresh under

cold storage for 3 months, while the bottled beverage remains fresh at room temperature for 12 months.

Mulberry juice is extremely beneficial for post-operative patients. It accelerates healing, improves blood circulation, decrease swelling, aid recovery after child birth and prevents the onset of infection. It can balance internal secretion, enhance the immunity and promotes body fluid production. It also helps people who suffer from dehydration. It also promotes the melanin production in hair and helps to maintain the natural colour of the hair. People with grey hair can also benefit with regular intake of mulberry. Mulberry juice applied directly on the hair can revive the hair roots and stimulate healthy hair growth again.

Drinking a glass of mulberry juice also improves vision. It has a high content of vitamin A which strengthens our eye sight and relieves eye strain, which is ideal for people who spend hours on computer. It also protects eyes from free radicals which is the cause of eye sight loss and retina degeneration. If someone had consumed too much alcohol, a small bottle of mulberry juice can help you overcome the effects of it and prevent from getting a hang over the next day. Regular consumption of mulberry juice will also help for healthy skin, anti obesity and acts as brain tonic. Tanakij and Pilairuk (9) suggested through their experiment that mulberry fruit extract mixed with honey is not only nutritious but also it acts against both pathogenic and food poisoning bacteria.

Fruit tea

It is natural, pleasantly savor all year-round, hot or cold. It does not contain caffeine and/or theine and therefore can be safely drunk at any time of the day. In Chinese markets, mulberry is often provided in the form of a paste called "Sangshengao"-mixed in hot water to make tea. In Iran, dried mulberries are used as a sweetener in black tea. After a sip of tea, dried mulberry fruits are eaten to sweeten the mouth (Singhal *et al.*, 6; Tanakij and Pilairuk, 9).

Fruit wine

Over ripened and sour fruits have high source of vitamin-C which is commonly used for the preparation of special wine and beer in most of the cold countries.

A glass of mulberry wine a day helps to get rid of impurities in the body which can help and make the body slim. It is believed that small dose of the drink protects against stomach and heart diseases (Alakbarov and Aliyev, 1) and very popular as a ladies drink in Europe.

Fruit syrup

It is a kind of molasses obtained from mulberries. It is very beneficial to be consumed as food by anemic patients. It is good especially for stomach illness and ulcer. It is used to increase body resistance against cold, for asthma and bronchitis patients and also a source of energy for sports persons. It helps intelligence development and physical development of babies and children. During gargling, it is efficient for mouth and throat illness. It is suggested for the diet of pregnant and breast feeding women, tuberculosis patients and those in healing period (Sujathamma *et al.*, 8).

Fruit powder

Raw mulberry fruit powder is a true nutritional treasure, being used in both alternative and traditional medicines for years. It contains a vast amount of nutrients essential to one's health with an overwhelming amount of anti-inflammatory, antiseptic cleansing qualities and healing properties to refresh and restore the body. It promotes healthy liver and kidney function, and improves digestion and assimilation.

Commercial values

Food colour

Fruits can be used as colouring and flavouring agent (ShivKumar *et al.*, 5). As there is increasing demand for natural food colorants, mulberry fruit extract being water-soluble and easily extractable, acts as a good colouring and flavouring agent. Fruit as feed supplements to ruminant live stock can be exploited as an income-generating micro enterprise (Ye and Ye, 12).

Cosmetic

Fruit extract can be used in cosmetics globally. It is a common ingredient in many skin care creams, shower gels etc., due to its antioxidant powers.

In view of the excellent characters of mulberry fruit, much more research studies may be initiated for thorough exploitation.

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Research Note :

DEVELOPMENT AND NUTRITIONAL ANALYSIS OF PRODUCTS FORTIFIED WITH MORINGA (*Moringa oleifera*)

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ABSTRACT : The study was carried out by recipe standardization and assessment of their physico-chemical properties. The sensory quality analysis of Biscuit was 7.28 than other developed products which were reported by panel members. It was found that percentage of moisture, fat, protein, carbohydrate and fibre were increased but the quantity of ash decreased (but increase as quality wise). The other developed products acceptability on basis of organoleptically and nutritional were decreased as well as in quantity and quality wise. This type research is remarkable step in the context of development of products for health benefits of people in one and other hand.

Keywords : *Moringa leaves, products, chemical composition.*

Moringa oleifera Lam or Drumstick leaves, belongs to a monogenetic family Moringaceae, is considered to have its origin in Agra and Ouch, in the northwest region of India, south of the Himalayan Mountains. Although the name “*Shigon*” for *M. oleifera* is mentioned in the “*Shushruta Sanhita*” which was written in the beginning of the first century A.D. There is evidence that the cultivation of this tree in India dates back many thousands of years. The Indians knew that the seeds contain edible oil and they used them for medicinal purposes (Fahey, 3; Rao, 5). The common people also knew of its value as a fodder or vegetable. This tree can be found growing naturally at elevations of up to 1,000 m above sea level. It can grow well on hillsides but is more frequently found growing on pasture land or in river basins. It is a fast growing tree and has been found to grow to 6 – 7 m in one year in areas receiving less than 400 mm mean annual rainfall. As a non-cultivated plant it is known for its resistance to drought and diseases. Because this tree has so many potential uses. We have been conducting an extensive research program on it over the last 10 years with the financial assistance of the Austrian Government and University of Hohenheim, Stuttgart.

The plant possesses many valuable properties (Table 1) which make it of great scientific interest. These include the high protein content of the leaves, twigs and stem, the high protein and oil contents of the seeds, the large number of unique polypeptides in seeds that can bind to many moieties, the presence of growth factors in the leaves, and the high sugar and starch content of the entire plant (Anwar *et al.*, 1;

Bamishaiye *et al.*, 2; Ramchandran, 4). Moringa leaves enormously contain seven times vitamin-C over oranges, four times vitamin- A and calcium over carrots and milk, respectively, three times potassium of bananas and two times protein of yoghurt. Equally important is the fact that few parts of the tree contain some toxins that might decrease its potential as a source of food for animals or humans. All parts of the Moringa tree are edible and have long been consumed by humans.

Table 1: Nutritional value of fresh *Moringa oleifera* (Drumstick leaves).

Nutrients	Content (g/100g)
Moisture	75.0 g
Ash	7.6 g
Protein	6.7 g
Fat	0.9 g
Fibre	1.0 g
Carbohydrate	9.8 g
Vitamin A	6.78 mg
Vitamin B1	0.06 mg
Calcium	440 mg
Iron	0.85 mg
Zinc	0.16 mg

- 1. Procurement of raw material** - Selection of the drumstick fresh leaves from Moring plants grown in C.S.A.U.A. &T., campus in Kanpur.
- 2. Preparation of sample** - 1-Selection of sample/fresh leaves, 2-Sorting, 3-Washing,

4-Sundrying or Oven drying (65o C for 1 hour),
5-Grinding (2 times), 6-Sieving (2 times),
7-Storage.

3. **Development of products** - Soup, Biscuit, Corn cutlet, Ricemurku.

4. **Nutritional analysis of sample –**

✓ **Moisture** : The moisture content in the sample was determined by Oven drying method.

✓ **Ash** : Ash content represent the total mineral present in a biological material.Total ash content was determined by incineration of sample in a muffle furnace, at 550°C.

✓ **Protein** : Crude protein was determined by multiplying total N content in sample by the factor 6.25. Total N content in sample was determined by micro - Kjeldahl method as described by Sadasivam and Manickam (6).

✓ **Fat** : The sample of dried feed stuff was placed in a continuous extractor (Soxhlet) and subjected to extraction with ether.

✓ **Carbohydrate** : The total CHO content was calculated by difference method.

✓ **Total CHO (%)** = 100 - (Moisture + Crude Protein + Total Ash + Fat + Crude Fibre).

✓ **Fibre** : The dry fat free material was boiled successively with dilute acid and dilutes alkali for a specified time period and filtered.

5. Statistical analysis : Mean score of organoleptic sensory evaluation and chemical composition of developed products were analyzed statistically (Table 2). The mean score of chemical analysis of (moisture, protein, fat, carbohydrate, fibre and ash) of developed products are depicted in Figure1.

The results depicted in Table 2 revealed that mean score of moisture was maximum in corn cutlet (47.46g) and minimum score was found in rice muruku (15.77g). The corn cutlet was developed by corn flour; moringa

Figure 1: Mean score of chemical composition in developed products.

leaves powder, coriander leaves and ginger. The highest mean score of protein was found in biscuit (17.38g) and minimum was in corn cutlet (6.49g). In analysis of fat in biscuit was maximum (5.16g), whereas the minimum score was in corn cutlet (1.48g). The mean score of the carbohydrate in biscuit was maximum (70.09g). This was due to presence of milk cream and butter. The minimum mean score of fibre was found in corn cutlet (1.37g) and maximum in biscuit (4.29g). Ash content was highest in soup (4.18g) and lowest in biscuit (2.22g).

The nutritive value of developed product was highest in biscuit due to the presence of barley flour, fresh milk cream, baking powder, stevia leaves powder, moringa leaves powder and butter which might had increased nutritive value of biscuit.

During the previous work it was found that moringa leaves were helpful in reducing joint pain. The highest nutritive value product (biscuit and soup) were introduced to the respondents, due to the product with good nutritional and medicinal value. The respondents were consuming this product regularly (till 1 month) then, they reported about relief at their joint pain after consuming the product

Conclusion

This study indicates that the developed products (biscuit, corn cutlet, soup and rice muruku) with

Table 2 : Nutritive value of developed products (per 100g basis).

Product	Moisture (g)	Protein (g)	Fat (g)	Carbohydrate (g)	Fibre (g)	Ash (g)
Biscuit	29.32	17.38	5.16	42.55	4.29	2.22
Rice Muruku	15.77	8.49	1.96	70.09	1.44	2.26
Corn cutlet	47.46	6.49	1.48	42.06	1.37	2.59
Soup	36.49	7.72	3.79	44.59	4.28	4.18

moringa can be easily prepared under optimized condition. The various parameters such as moisture, crude protein, fat, carbohydrate, total ash and crude fibre were analyzed.

Since in country like India approximately 60% women are suffered from joint pain, hence the moringa leaves products can be introduced to the women.

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Research Note :

CONFIRMATION OF FLAVONES AND RHAMNOPYRANOSIDE IN *Strychnos potatorum* L. FLOWERS

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ABSTRACT : The glycoside on oxidation with sodium meta periodate consumed 3.04 moles of periodate with the liberation of 1.02 moles of formic acid for one mole of the glycoside. It consumed 3.12 moles of periodate and liberated 1.36 moles of formic acid per equivalent for each anhydrohexose sugar unit of the polymer after 60 h. Presence of (1→4)-0- α - type and (1→6)- β - type linkage obtained after methylation was also confirmed by the periodate oxidation results. A flavones glycoside 6,7,3',7' tetramethoxy flavones 5-0- β -D- glucopyranosyl -(1→4)-0- α -L-Rhamnopyranoside has been isolated from the methanolic extract soluble fraction of the rectified spirit soluble extract of the flowers of *Strychnos potatorum* L. and has been identified by its chemical and spectral analysis.

Keywords : *Strychnos potatorum*, periodate oxidation and consumption, formic acid, flavones,

Strychnos potatorum L., belonging to family Loganiaceae, commonly referred as 'clearing nut tree' or Nirmali, is a medium sized glabrous tree having height of 6-18 meters (Peter, 8). It has been reported in *Ayurveda*, *Siddha*, and *Unani* systems of medicine. Some of the chief constituents found in the plant are Strychine, Diaboline, Isomotioli and Stigmasterol (Chopra et al., 2). Many volatile fragrant compounds have also been analyzed from *Strychnos flowers* (Barar, 1). The seeds of tree are commonly used in traditional medicine as well as purifying water in India. Flowers are white, small, borne on compound inflorescences in the axils of the upper leaves.

Periodate oxidation reaction in the carbohydrate chemistry was first determined by Malaparade (6) and Fluery and Lange (3) had given the periodic acid for the oxidation of glycol group, while Perlin (7) given Lead tetra acetate and periodic acid showed that the glycol group undergo cyclic ester formation with oxidation and reaction is to be a dialdehyde type (Singh,9). Periodate oxidation studies of the seeds polysaccharides of *Nyctanthes arbor-tristis* L., *Pongamia pinnata* L., *Abrus precatorius* L. and *Withania somnifera* Dunal. have already been studied by various scientists for the confirmation of

polysaccharide structure which was obtained after methylation studies of polysaccharide (Gringauz, 4; Perlin, 7; Singh, 9).

The methanolic soluble fraction of the concentrated rectified spirit extract of the flowers of *Strychnos potatorum* L. on column chromatography showed the presence of single spot. On crystallization from methanol, light golden yellow coloured needle shaped structure crystals obtained. It gave the tests for glycoside and respond to all the colour reactions of flavones. For periodate consumption, the reaction mixture (5 ml) was taken in a conical flask then added sodium bicarbonate solution (2ml), sodium arsenate solution (0.01 N, 25 ml) and potassium iodide solution (20%, 2ml). Reaction mixture was shaken for 1 hr and added iodine solution (0.01 N, 5ml), using starch solution as an indicator. The excess iodine was titrated against sodium thiosulphate solution (0.01N). A blank titration was also carried out in a similar way. The difference between blank and experiment gives the periodate consumption of 3.12 moles of periodate after 60 hrs (Table 1.)

Formic acid liberation was determined by taking the aliquot (5ml) in a conical flask then added ethylene

Table 1: Periodate oxidation of *Strychnos potatorum* flowers' polysaccharide.

Sugar present	Time (hrs)						
	10	20	30	40	50	55	60
Periodate consumption of anhydrohexose sugar unit (moles/ mole)	1.16	1.74	2.12	2.56	2.84	3.12	3.12
Formic acid liberation of anhydrohexose sugar unit(moles/mole)	0.32	0.92	1.08	1.12	1.24	1.32	1.32

glycol (10ml) to destroy the excess of periodate ions present in the reaction mixture for 30 min. the formic acid liberation was estimated by titration against sodium hydroxide solution (0.12 N), using methyl red dye as an indicator. A blank titration was also carried out in a similar way for the estimation of formic acid. It liberated 1.32 moles of formic acid per mole of anhydrohexose sugar units after 60 hrs. Results of periodate consumption and formic liberation of *Strychnos potatorum* L. are given in Table 1.

Study of the glycosides TS-1: The glycoside on elemental analysis gave its molecular formula $C_{18}H_{36}O_{16}$. It gave positive Shinoda and Molish test. It also gave the colour reactions of flavones glycoside. The glycoside showed strong absorption bands at 282 and 335nm. The glycoside on hydrolysis with ethanolic sulphuric acid gave yellow crystalline aglycone TS 1 and D- glucose and L- Rhamnose as a sugar moieties.

Study of aglycone TS-1 : The aglycone on elemental analysis suggested its molecular formula to be $C_{10}H_{18}O_7$, M.P189-190°C. it gave all the characteristics colour tests of flavones, which confirmed the nature of aglycone to be flavanoid.

Position of methoxy group in aglycone TS-1 : Estimation of methoxy group (OCH_3) by Ziesel's Method4 indicated the presence of four methoxy groups in aglycone TS-1.

The position of four methoxy groups were established by the alkaline degradation of the the aglycone which gave two products 2,4 dihydroxy 5,6 dimethoxy benzene (I) and 3,4 dimethoxy benzoic acid (II) thereby indicating the presence of methoxy groups at position 6,7,3',4' in the Aglycone. A survey of literature revealed that the aglycone is identical with 5 hydroxy -6,7,3',4' tetramethoxy flavones (III). The identity of the aglycone was further confirmed by m.p .

Study of sugar moieties : The aqueous hydrolysate obtained by the hydrolysis of the glycoside gave brown colour with aniline hydrogen phthalate and reduced Fehling solution confirming the presence of sugar moieties. On paper chromatographic analysis the aqueous hydrolysate revealed the presence of D- glucose and L – rhamnose.

Quantitative analysis of the sugars : The quantitative analysis of both the sugars in the glycoside was achieved by the procedure of Mishra and Rao and revealed that both the sugars are present in 1:1 ratio. Thus one molecule of the aglycone is attached with one molecule of D- glucose and L- rhamnose in the glycoside.

Periodate oxidation of the glycoside : The glycoside on oxidation with sodium meta periodate consumed 3.04 moles of periodate with the liberation of 1.02 moles of formic acid for one mole of the glycoside. This indicate the presence of a disaccharides and also that both the sugars moieties are in pyranose from which shows that C_1 -OH group of glucose is attached to C_4 -OH group of rhamnose and also confirm that three vicinal hydrogen atoms are present in glucose and two vicinal hydroxyl groups are present in rhamnose.

Position of attachment of sugar in the aglycone- The sugar linkage in the glycoside was established by comparing the properties of the glycoside with that of the aglycone. The aglycone produced red colour when spotted on filter paper and sprayed with p- toluene sulphonic acid and on subsequent heating whereas the glycoside did not , thereby showing the presence of free hydroxyl group at position C-5.

The hydrolysis of the glycoside with enzyme showed the appearance of one spot corresponding to D- glucose indicating that D glucose was attached to L- rhamnose through α -linkage and which could be hydrolyzed by an enzyme emulsion.Periodate oxidation confirm the presence of glucose and rhamnose. *S.potatorum* Linn seeds yielded a water soluble polysaccharides as D- glucose and Rhamnose in the molar ratio 1:3 moles by Gas, TLC, Column, and Paper chromatographic analysis. For periodate oxidation the purified seeds polysaccharide was oxidized with sodium metaperiodate with the usual manner. It consumed 3.12 moles of periodate and liberate 1.36 moles of formic acid per equivalent for each anhydrohexose sugar unit of the polymer after 60 h. Presence of (1→4)-0- α - type and (1→6)- β - type linkage obtained after methylation results are also confirmed by the periodate oxidation results. Polysaccharides were containing free hydroxyl groups resulting in the consumption of Periodate oxidation reaction (Harold, 5)

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2. Johnson, D.A. (1940). *Plant Microtechnique*. McGraw- Hill Publishing Co. Ltd., New York, PP-29
3. Kapil, R.N. and Arora, S. (1990). Some fascinating features of orchid pollen. *J. Orchid Soc.*, **4** (1): 9-28.
4. Rashid, S., Ashraf, M., Bibi, S. and Anjum, R. (2000). Antibacterial and antifungal activities of *Launaea nudicaulis* Roxb. and *Launaea resedifolia* L. *Pakistan J. Biol. Sci.*, **3** (4) :630-632.

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